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generalisation

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Executive Summary

The main objective of the Arctic PASSION project is to co-create a coherent, integrated Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS) to enhance monitoring of the immense impacts of climate change in the Arctic region. This effort is undertaken in close cooperation with Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and focuses on integrating diverse Arctic observations, improving data management, optimising observing networks, and developing new, user-oriented services. WP5 aims to demonstrate the societal and economic value of the resulting Arctic services (ASs) developed in Arctic PASSION. Clear communication of these benefits is crucial to increase understanding of the importance of the pan-AOSS, guiding improvements, and justifying current and future investments. Deliverable 5.3 builds on the work of Deliverable 5.1 (Description of a versatile benefit assessment approach and Arctic resilience societal indicators for the pan-AOSS) and Deliverable 5.2 (Toolset for societal benefit estimates).

Toolset compiled in Deliverable 5.2 is applied to each AS. First, the societal benefits are assessed via value chain analysis (VCA), where the value creation of each AS is represented in a stepwise process, with an emphasis on the benefits for society and end users. The findings are complemented by previous literature. In addition, VCA guides the selection of suitable ASs for further economic evaluation. Economic evaluation is conducted for AS6 (Improving safety for shipping in the polar seas, POLARIS) and AS8 (Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety, LIS). For AS5 (Air Quality Forecast for Arctic Communities, AURORAE) a more general assessment of the potential *value of information* on air quality is presented. The main evaluation and valuation methods are avoided cost (or cost-loss) approach and benefit transfer.

Findings of the report highlight the various types of benefits resulting from the Arctic services, especially for local communities living in the Arctic but also for the scientific community. Benefits for the local communities living in the Arctic are especially emphasised in AS1 (Event Database) by preserving the Indigenous Knowledge, Traditional Knowledge and Local Knowledge combined with Community Based Monitoring, and AS7 (Arctic marine climate change and living resources) by supporting local and scientific data needs, encompassing inclusive decision-making and enhancing local capacity. While the information is mainly targeted towards Indigenous communities (AS1) and local communities (AS7), it also promotes ethical knowledge sharing between the knowledge holders and the scientific community. AS2 (ALEX) benefits the local communities by allowing monitoring of surface changes and enabling informed decisions related to activities sensitive to permafrost thaw, such as site selection in subsistence, infrastructure and leisure. AS3 (State of the Arctic Environment) offers a way to access comprehensive information on the current state of the environment, supporting a wider understanding of the environmental indicators' changes in the Arctic. Similarly, AS4 (INFRA) and AS5 (AURORAE) contribute to better awareness and understanding of wildfires and air pollution migration and deposition in the Arctic which can have great benefits, for example, through healthcare savings. Respectively, AS8 (LIS) provides information about the lake ice coverage and AS6 (POLARIS) about the sea ice related risk to ships in the Arctic. Accurate information about the lake ice results in safety improvements, avoided (in-situ monitoring and recreational) trip costs, optimised production in hydroelectricity and flood risk monitoring. AS6 provides information to ships sailing in ice-covered Arctic seas to make more informed navigation decisions, transferring to avoided social and private costs.

Public investment in large-scale climate and environmental information and monitoring systems requires accountability and evidence-based decision-making, which calls for more inclusive and comprehensive

societal benefit assessments to ensure that public funds are allocated efficiently and equitably for all. Evaluating impacts of large-scale projects and initiatives, however, involves complex, long-term, and often diffuse outcomes and challenges which is why more narrowly scoped assessments focusing on individual climate services or end users are often more precise but poorly include the net benefits for society. Moreover, ex ante evaluations of *new* climate services are highly uncertain due to a lack of data on the actual use of the service. As such, developing transparent and scalable methods for measuring broader benefits of pan-AOSS will be crucial in ensuring that future initiatives and investments align with societal needs and values.

1. Introduction

Climate change affects the Arctic more than any other region in the world. It is estimated that the rate of warming is four times faster than elsewhere in the globe (Rantanen et al., 2022), affecting widely on local ecosystems, Indigenous livelihoods and local economies. To efficiently prepare and adapt to the impacts of climate change in the Arctic, monitoring and anticipating the changes is critical. Yet, there is a clear gap in monitoring for the Arctic when compared to other regions. The Arctic PASSION project aims to answer this need by co-creating and implementing an integrated Arctic observing system, the Pan-Arctic observing system of systems (pan-AOSS), to monitor the impacts of climate change in the Arctic.

The purpose of WP5 in the project is to demonstrate the value of information services (hereafter “Arctic services” or “AS”) produced when creating the pan-AOSS. Demonstration of societal and economic value in understandable, comprehensive and comparable manner is essential when communicating the benefits of both the pan-AOSS and particular Arctic services to wider audiences. More specifically, clear communication of societal and economic benefits supports justifying (also future) investments and gives insights to service developers on places of improvement. Deliverable 5.3 builds on the work started in Deliverable 5.1 (Description of a versatile benefit assessment approach and Arctic resilience societal indicators for the pan-AOSS) and Deliverable 5.2 (Toolset for societal benefit estimates) by applying the approaches and methods to the Arctic services created in the project. Toolset for societal benefit estimates (D5.2) guides the selection of evaluation and valuation methods while the approaches presented in D5.1 guided the selection of methods that are presented in D5.2. In this report, the content of deliverables 5.1 and 5.2 are applied to assess the societal benefits and economic impacts of the Arctic services created in the project. Presented approaches allow for comprehensive assessment of the societal benefits and economic impacts, not excluding non-market and intangible benefits.

The report is structured as follows. First, the evaluation process is briefly described (as in D5.1 and D5.2). After, the results of the societal benefit assessments and economic evaluations are presented for each Arctic service. Value chain analysis (VCA) serves as a starting point for the evaluation and is conducted for all services. Evaluation continues by reflecting the findings to existing literature if quantitative assessment is not feasible due to reasons such as different purposes of the assessment and availability of utilisable data. For AS6 (Improving safety for shipping in the polar seas, POLARIS) and AS8 (Lake ice service, LIS), a quantitative, more detailed economic evaluation is conducted. Additionally, for AS2 and AS8, Spatineo web traffic analysis is conducted, and the results are utilised in the economic assessment in the case of AS8. The summary of all results is presented after the service-specific results. Further discussion, including the limitations and other aspects that must be considered when interpreting the results, is presented in section five. Conclusions are given last.

2. Evaluation process

The evaluation process for Arctic services applied in this deliverable is explained in-depth in Deliverable 5.2 (Toolset of societal benefit estimates). It should be noted that no uniform approach for the evaluation of climate services exists due to the highly context-dependent nature of the benefits of climate services (Perrels, 2020), which is why the purpose of the Guidebook created in D5.2 is to provide a general understanding on the evaluation process and the possible evaluation and valuation approaches. Here we provide a short summary of the Guidebook and the toolset.

The evaluation of the socioeconomic benefits of information services is a multidimensional and complex process which must take into account various factors, such as availability of data, maturity of the service, and types of values the benefits possess. In simplified, high-level form, the evaluation process for information services can be presented as three steps: value chain analysis, evaluation and valuation. The fourth step is the decisions and actions based on the results of the analysis.

Figure 1. Process steps of economic evaluation (as in D5.2, Juvonen et al., 2025)

Value chain analysis (VCA) serves as an inherent starting point for the economic evaluation process as it offers a general understanding of the impacts and the information differential of an information service in qualitative terms, and can be conducted regardless of uncertainty on the user groups and uptake of an information service (Perrels et al., 2012). VCA gathers important information on the service's production chain as well as potential user groups and use purposes. Incorporating end-user engagement in the qualitative assessment is crucial since the value of a service is created through the actions of a user, after all. Interviews and surveys targeted towards the end users can be used to support the assessment of the service's impacts. Especially if the production of the service is not yet precisely specified and/or if there exist variations in the ways of production, delivery and precise characteristics, VCA is very helpful to get the definition phase for economic evaluation well organised and conducted.

As presented in D5.2, the basic idea of a value chain is to show how the production of a service is organised with special attention to the use of resources in and the (incremental) value of output at each stage. When analysing information services, the VCA typically shows how the data is processed into information and information formats and further to (specialised) services, what decisions users make based on the information provided by the service, and how their actions create value. Especially with information services, the value of a service stems from the decisions and actions taken by the end users – the society. In the case of Arctic PASSION and the eight developed Arctic services (originally pilot services), the decision to use VCA was well justified as VCA could be carried out for all (pilot) services, regardless of the maturity (e.g., public availability) of the service at the time of the evaluation. Carrying out VCA for each service allows service developers to qualitatively report on the benefits of the service (based on initial

communication with the end users), even if these are difficult to quantify later in an economic evaluation. This allows reporting of the non-market benefits and intangible impacts. For reporting the production stages and anticipated benefits of each Arctic service, a survey for the service developers was conducted (see Appendix 1). The VCA supported our decision on which services are mature enough to be subject to an economic evaluation. Email communication and collection of feedback on the preliminary VCA results with the service developers took place after the VCA survey to validate the findings.

The eight developed Arctic Services are:

- Arctic Service 1: Event Database of CBM using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge
- Arctic Service 2: Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX)
- Arctic Service 3: State of the Arctic Environment
- Arctic Service 4: Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA)
- Arctic Service 5: Air Quality Forecast for Arctic Communities (AURORAE)
- Arctic Service 6: Improving safety for shipping in the polar seas (POLARIS)
- Arctic Service 7: CBM for Arctic marine climate change, noise pollution & impacts on marine living resources
- Arctic Service 8: Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety (LIS)

Figure 2 below shows an example of a value chain for a weather and climate information service (WCIS) – in this example, a service providing terrain moisture information. For each Arctic service, an illustration of the value chain of the service was created, based on the VCA survey and end-user engagement, including interviews and surveys. Each service's value chain visualises the specific value-adding steps, resources and outcomes the service provides. The picture also includes information outlining the requirements needed to progress from one stage to the next (the boxes below). The concept of value chain analysis (VCA) is presented in detail in D5.1 (Perrels et al. 2022) and D5.2 (Juvonen et al., 2025).

Figure 2. Example of a value chain for weather and climate information service (WCIS)

As presented in deliverable 5.2 (Juvonen et al., 2025), services may choose to remain at the **qualitative level of assessment**, either due to a lack of quantitative data, the service's maturity, or the service developer's interest. For these services, VCA is deepened via findings of end-user engagement and previous literature that are compiled to gain a comprehensive insight on the potential benefits. For Arctic services AS1, AS5, AS6 and AS8, preliminary **value tree analyses** (VTAs) based on expert opinions were conducted in D5.1. For AS1, VTA findings (i.e. contribution to different Societal Benefit Areas, SBAs) are

reflected in findings of the VCA and literature. By **Societal Benefit Areas** (SBAs) we are referring to the framework which identifies twelve most relevant social benefits connected to the Earth Observation systems with focus areas of particular importance for the Arctic society (Figure 3) (IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017). VTA and societal benefit assessment are based on expert knowledge and can give qualitative estimates of the resource importance for the downstream part of the value chain and provide insight into how the services contribute to defined SBAs, thus providing the framework for advancing in depth quantitative analyses of the societal benefits of the considered effects (Keeney et al. 1990, IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017).

SAON's Arctic Societal Benefit Areas (2017)	
	1. Disaster Preparedness
	2. Environmental Quality
	3. Food Security
	4. Fundamental Understanding of Arctic Systems
	5. Human Health
	6. Infrastructure and Operations
	7. Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes
	9. Resilient Communities
	10. Sociocultural Services
	11. Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes
	12. Weather and Climate

Figure 3. Twelve Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs) in the Arctic (defined by IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017).

Based on the results of the qualitative assessment, an **economic evaluation** approach is selected, and the impacts are given a monetary estimate where feasible and advisable. Even with the process map and step-by-step guidelines in place, choosing appropriate evaluation and valuation methods remains complex, especially when estimating a *new* climate service (Perrels, 2020). Evaluation method selection is relatively structured, driven largely by available data and the desired scope of analysis. In contrast, selecting **valuation** methods is more challenging due to the intricacies of assessing non-use values, externalities, and spill-over effects. However, valuation methods offer greater flexibility; they can be adapted, combined, and tailored to fit specific contexts, sometimes even using select elements from different methods. In this report, avoided costs (AS6 and AS8) method is applied. The economic evaluation process and all methods are comprehensively explained and discussed in the *Guidebook*, D5.2. (Juvonen et al., 2025).

To add empirical evidence of the use of each Arctic Service as well as to support of economic evaluation methods, a **web traffic analysis** of applicable Arctic services was performed. This process includes using advanced spatial web service analytics tools provided by Spatineo to investigate the usage of the online service that disseminates data from the service to the users. This provides results as to the volume of usage as well as analysis on the kinds of users for the services. In the context of Arctic Passion, the originating country of the users as well as the type of organisation in question were used. Both are derived from anonymised end-user IP address information. Arctic services 2 and 8 were feasible for web traffic evaluation by Spatineo.

3. Results

Section 3 presents the results of the potential benefit assessments for each Arctic service (AS). The scope and depth of each assessment vary depending on the service's level of maturity, the availability of relevant data, and the specific objectives of the evaluation. For all Arctic services, a Value Chain Analysis (VCA) is conducted, which outlines the production processes, identifies potential societal benefits, and incorporates insights from end-user engagement where applicable. These findings are further supported by evidence from existing literature. For Arctic Services 6 and 8, a detailed economic impact evaluation is carried out. Societal benefit assessments are provided for Arctic Services 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7, with the depth of analysis varying according to the quality and availability of data. Additionally, for Services 2 and 8, Spatideo web traffic tool analysis is carried out.

3.1. Arctic Service 1: Event Database of CBM using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge

The Event Database is a unique repository of Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge observations of past climate, ecological and environmental changes as well as new, present-day observations. It focuses on socio-ecologically relevant events, particularly significant ecosystem changes, captured by holders of Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge who observe and document this information at the frontline. The information is provided on maps with written translation from local languages into English, completed by reanalysis of data when necessary. Hence, previously neglected or unobserved changes in the Arctic are accessible for larger audiences through an online portal (www.arcticseas.org). Observations can also be compared with scientific findings to provide a deeper understanding of events, which can for example, support climate change adaptation and risk mitigation in the Arctic.

The information captured and provided in the Event Database is regularly updated by communities living in the Arctic areas of Alaska, Canada, Greenland, Finland, Russian North and the Faroe Islands, and it will emerge as a central node for consented Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge observations that can be adopted in other regions and communities as appropriate. In this way, Arctic Service 1 will contribute to strengthening Arctic monitoring capacity and diversifying monitoring practices, as well as the collection of Indigenous Knowledge based on free, prior and informed consent (FPIC). There is no similar service available.

3.1.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 4. Value chain of Arctic service 1.

Data and Production of the Service

The data for the Event Database is obtained from Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge holders through interviews and discussions, which have been curated and consented by the knowledge holders with a variety of different types of materials and data sources. To obtain observations, years of background contacts, trust building, skills to read simultaneously cultural-ecological indicators, Indigenous Knowledge and science, are needed. Consented large volumes of Indigenous Knowledge should not be subjected to data analysis as such, thus, the curation, translation and re-analysis of data needs to be done by a suitable, culturally trained person. Indigenous Knowledge needs to be approached very carefully and with nuanced skills to understand its operational framework.

The production steps for the service include 1) the initial information from Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge holders as well as historical and spatial data, 2) curation, translation and re-analysis of obtained data, 3) creating the online service and maintaining it (hunting for bugs and problems) and, 4) release and dissemination. Credibility and usefulness of the information rely on consistent maintenance of the portals, which is essential to safeguard access to Indigenous Knowledge and prevent its misuse. Actors and entities involved in the process are Indigenous communities consenting to the work, local coordinators, central Indigenous NGOs or similar for the region, a science team, a linguistic team, reindeer herders, hunters, fishers, and a data processing unit. No special skills for participating partner communities were required. Together with Snowchange, all participating communities in the service development are: Unalakleet, Dease Lake, Gwichin Settlement Area in NWT, Attu, Sevettijärvi, Ponoï area, Khanty-Mansia, Lower Kolyma and Faroe Islands.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

The Event Database of CBM combines Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge about the ecologically and historically relevant events and changes in the Arctic. The content of the database includes new baselines, understandings, and meaningful outcomes as Indigenous and local communities in the Arctic wanted to share their knowledge of the changing Arctic from their homelands. The approved databases are both in actual long-form and in story map summaries as well as videos produced by the knowledge

holders. The purpose of the Event Database is to make the local voices heard, support scholars, Indigenous people, and local communities as well as provide information about Arctic change, its meaning, significance and the role of Indigenous Knowledge in larger Arctic observation systems to the general public. As the focus has been on the local preconditions, needs and importance, the stories from different ecoregions vary.

The Event Database is available through the online portal (www.arcticseas.org) where users can proceed to the actual community databases. It is an open-access data portal based on the Circumpolar Arctic map (MAP BOX). The web-based materials are gathered under ESRI's Storymaps, including a large variety of written sources, pictures and films. The retrieval and use of the information does not demand registration, special skills and/or particular equipment, nor do users add information from other sources before gainful use of the service information. However, access to the internet is required and can be an issue in some local communities; either a lack of connection or hardware or the costs to use the internet. For example, very few older people have access to the internet, hence elders may not be able to access Indigenous Knowledge online. However, access to the internet is required and can be an issue in some local communities, either due to a lack of connection or hardware or the costs to use the internet. For example, very few older people have access to the internet, which can restrict elders' ability to access Indigenous Knowledge online – however they are more likely the knowledge holders in the first place. Credibility and usefulness of the information rely on consistent maintenance of the portals, which is essential to safeguard the access to Indigenous Knowledge and prevent its misuse.

Users and Uses of the Service

The primary user groups of the Event Database are Arctic Indigenous and local communities and researchers focusing on the Arctic region. Other prospective users are scholars and the wider public (politics, media/communication, etc.) interested in Indigenous cultures and socio-ecological changes in the Arctic regions. One of the main objectives of the service was to get the local Arctic voices heard, preserve Indigenous Knowledge and enable wider dissemination of Indigenous and local findings. Through the service, local Arctic communities have the opportunity to preserve and disseminate their knowledge both within and beyond their communities, including Indigenous Knowledge reflecting the gendered ways of knowing, for example, from women of *Tsiigehtchic* and *Sevettijärvi*. Conversely, researchers and people outside the Arctic can seek information and knowledge about the changing Arctic respectfully with consent.

The users and scope of use are not tracked in the service, nor can the user groups be monitored through open source. It is expected that the use purposes for Indigenous peoples will be different from those of the scientific community. As the service is archiving Indigenous Knowledge, the primary interest of Indigenous people is most likely the preservation and use of their own community's knowledge records. Respectively, researchers are expected to use the service for data collection. Technically, it is possible to monitor the portal, but it is not possible to monitor the use of the service, as there are no specific indicators defined. Further quantification of the impacts of (different) uses is impossible, as the service does not monitor the activities of users.

The economic evaluation of AS1 is not conducted due to the lack of quantitative data about the impacts and costs of the service, as well as the sensitive and intangible nature of the benefits of the service. In economic terms, the service generates value for others (altruistic value), future generations (bequest value), and for existing (existence value). These values could be defined through stated preference

method such as contingent valuation or choice experiment estimating willingness-to-pay (WTP) (or willingness-to-accept, WTA). Instead, the societal benefits of AS1 are assessed qualitatively based on literature and VCA results. VCA results are based on the communication between service developers and the end users. In other words, primary data collection is conducted by the service developers, who have established the necessary trust with local communities over time. The main (qualitative) benefits of the service can be seen as strengthening and diversifying the monitoring capacity in the Arctic, supporting adaptation and risk mitigation in the Arctic, preserving and disseminating Indigenous Knowledge and local knowledge with consent as well as promoting community-based monitoring (CBM) and Indigenous-led science.

3.1.2. Societal benefits

To be able to evaluate the impacts of AS1, understanding of the value creation process, its order of magnitude and components, as well as its enabling and disabling (pre)conditions should (at least) give *approximate* quantification of quality, volume and price factors, response probabilities and mechanisms related to the production and use of the AS1. As the Event database is a newly launched unique service, adequate approximations from existing service products are unlikely to be found, and there is insufficient primary data available on its use. Hence, valuation will depend on VCA, preliminary VTA, literature as well as interviews and surveys made by service developers.

A key element in AS1 is including diverse information sources, especially oral Indigenous histories and local knowledge, to build richer, more reliable repositories of near- and long-term environmental changes and their impacts. Hence, the developed AS1, a joint repository (and associated information retrieval service), is an entirely new service, which is assumed to function at regional scales in the first place, without excluding options for use at other scales. These kinds of repositories, along with related information services, represent a new type of regional-scale infrastructure that could also be adapted for other scales. Because the information in the repository is interconnected, a coordinating structure – with expertise and support – could enhance its value, similar to regional climate action bodies. The system also includes feedback loops, where user interaction leads to learning, improved impact tracking, and continuous refinement of the repository.

Figure 5 shows a *preliminary* value tree analysis (VTA) for AS1, which is based on expert interviews but does not necessarily represent all involved categories of actors and their coverage of different value chain segments (Perrels et al., 2022). Preliminary VTA for the Event database in D5.1 estimated that AS1 supports the following outputs of local communities: Sociocultural Activities, Environmental Information Services, Food Services, Research Services, Natural Resource Services, Ecosystem Services and Communities Services. These identified benefits are linked to the sub-societal benefits that are then connected to the 12 essential Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs) in the Arctic (see Figure 3). The preliminary VTA defined that AS1 promotes the following SBAs: Sociocultural Services, Environmental Quality, Food Security, Fundamental Understanding of the Arctic Systems, Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes, Natural Resources, and Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes. For the more comprehensive VTA of AS1, see Perrels et al., 2022.

Figure 5. Preliminary Value Tree for AS1. (Perrels et al., 2022).

The results of the VCA and the literature are in line with the initial estimates of the benefits of AS1, as the Event Database provides means to gain a comprehensive understanding of Indigenous-led and Indigenous-focused conservation and monitoring in the Arctic, and provides information on socio-ecologically relevant ecosystem changes, thereby supporting the Indigenous Peoples and local knowledge way of living in the Arctic. A unique shared data repository combining scientific and Indigenous Knowledge of temporal, linguistic and spatial scales and dimensions will strengthen and diversify monitoring capacity and support adaptation and risk mitigation in the Arctic. Due to the growing understanding and recognition of the extent and severity of climatological and biological changes in the Arctic affecting ecosystems and climate change on a whole planet, the information provided by AS1 is also relevant and valuable for scientists all around the world.

Recent studies highlight the importance of bottom-up guiding protocols in increasing community engagement and equitable outcomes in Arctic research (Herman-Mercer et al., 2023). Community-based monitoring (CBM) in the Arctic is increasingly supported by a wide range of stakeholders due to its capacity to integrate traditional knowledge with scientific methodologies to monitor environmental changes in the Arctic (Johnson et al., 2015). CBM initiatives have expanded significantly, particularly in North America, with First Nations and Inuit communities and in environmental sciences (Kouril et al., 2016). Successful CBM programs bring together various partners and knowledge systems to develop adaptation tools and enhance local adaptive capacity (Tremblay et al., 2009). Since Indigenous conservation methods often prioritise local needs, traditional practices, sovereignty, and self-determination (Bucshman & Sudlovenick, 2024), collaborative initiatives and projects ensure that Indigenous communities in the Arctic are involved in shaping the global discourse around conservation approaches, mechanisms, and strategies, that differ from conventional global approaches. While CBM programs offer local-scale data for community decision-making they also have the potential to contribute to broader Arctic observing networks (Johnson et al., 2015).

Indigenous Knowledge and community-based monitoring (CBM) have increasingly gained recognition, particularly in biodiversity monitoring and conservation, due to their ability to support long-term data collection in remote regions. This approach not only strengthens conservation efforts but also offers a model for how regional, national, and international initiatives can respectfully and effectively engage with Indigenous Knowledge systems and practices, especially in the Arctic context (Bucshman & Sudlovenick, 2024). Furthermore, CBM is often more cost-effective than scientist-led monitoring, enhancing wildlife surveillance across protected areas and a broad range of species (Soifer et al., 2024). Despite these benefits, challenges persist in sustaining long-term CBM efforts and ensuring that research outcomes align with community priorities and needs (Herman-Mercer et al., 2023). Beyond environmental applications, Indigenous Knowledge and CBM also offer valuable contributions in other fields. For instance, they play a significant role in disaster risk reduction by empowering communities and improving project implementation (Baumwoll, 2008) and enabling local participants to actively engage in adaptive policy-making and management processes that directly affect their communities (Quinn & duBois, 2005). In the context of entrepreneurship, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge can drive innovation by addressing local challenges and validating community-based ventures (Mehta et al., 2010). However, growing interest in utilising Indigenous Knowledge in various sectors, including multilateral organisations, NGOs, and educational institutions has sparked debates about the nature of Indigenous Knowledge and its scientific validity (Srikantaiah, 2008). In addition, the digitisation and recording of Indigenous Knowledge – often done without community ownership – raises critical concerns about intellectual property rights (Janke, 2008). To address this, Brush and Stabinsky (1996) propose recognising Indigenous Knowledge as a form of intellectual property. This could ensure both its conservation and equitable economic returns for communities that choose to share it, while validating its legitimacy within broader knowledge systems.

In the Global South, Indigenous Knowledge also plays a crucial role in fields such as medicine and agriculture, where it enhances both traditional and modern practices (Khor, 2001). While assigning a precise monetary value to this knowledge remains challenging, its economic potential is undeniable. However, valuing Indigenous heritage goes beyond market-based assessments and it requires frameworks that safeguard rights and cultural integrity. Venn and Quiggin (2006) argue that price-based valuation methods should be replaced or complemented by approaches incorporating quantitative constraints, which better reflect the cultural and non-commercial significance of Indigenous Knowledge and heritage.

At its core, Indigenous Knowledge is a vital part of cultural identity and continuity for Indigenous communities (Janke, 2008). Many communities choose to keep their knowledge private (Goldberg, 2012) or share it only with informed consent, as in the case of AS1. This underscores the need for respectful and consent-based engagement. Supporting Indigenous-led strategies, community-level initiatives, and traditional practices helps ensure that research and policy reflect Indigenous priorities, values, and needs. This requires investment in Indigenous-led research, management, and long-term partnerships grounded in mutual respect and mentorship. Indigenous scholars, communities, organisations, and governments are best positioned to lead conservation efforts and respond to the complex challenges they face (Bucshman & Sudlovenick, 2024). Despite ongoing global challenges and limited funding for Indigenous and local knowledge systems (Soifer et al., 2024), community-based monitoring (CBM) initiatives show promising. While collaborative projects and initiatives, such as Event Database, contribute to scientific understanding and sustainable monitoring of environmental changes in the Arctic, it also empowers communities by preserving cultural heritage and creating locally meaningful repositories of knowledge.

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3.2. Arctic service 2: Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX)

The Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX) offers data on land surface changes in Arctic permafrost regions, derived from remote sensing analyses. Interactive maps deliver insights into surface transformations, disturbance hotspots, and areas at risk of permafrost thaw and erosion. Designed to enhance communication of scientific findings, ALEX employs customised visualisations and story maps to make complex data more accessible and easier to understand. This tool is tailored for non-scientific audiences, including stakeholders, rights holders, and communities across the Arctic.

3.2.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 6. Value chain of Arctic service 2.

Production and Data of the Service

For mapping the disturbances on permafrost, and to quantify landscape change, hydrological dynamics and permafrost vulnerability, ALEX uses remote sensing time series at high spatial resolution throughout the entire Arctic region. The dataset visualising landscape changes utilises multi-spectral imagery of Landsat-TM, ETM+ and OLI sensors and the ESA's Sentinel-2 mission covering a 20-year period from 2003 through 2022 (2005 through 2024 in progress). Datasets are available in Google Earth Engine (GEE). To handle large data of images, Python code and a processing pipeline were developed. Python code is publicly available at https://github.com/initze/GEE_HotSpot. Tasseled Cap Transformation (TCT - a method used in remote sensing to transform spectral data from satellite imagery into a new set of composite bands) is then applied to all cloud-free pixels in images with less than 80% cloud cover from the months of July and August. As part of the change analysis multispectral indices for *greenness*, *wetness*, and *brightness* and their change over time are derived to obtain robust trend parameters. Finally, a regression is used to calculate the trends for each Tasseled Cap indices.

Subsequent production stages include first exporting the image tiles from GEE and creating an optimised image file (Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF, COG) using the developed Python code. Then, the data is moved to AWI's geospatial data unit where a Web Map Service (WMS), compliant with the standard of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), is set up to serve the data on the internet. Metadata is published via the

PANGAEA repository, a member of the World Data System (see Nitze, Lübker and Grosse, 2024). The Leaflet map library and additional JavaScript code are used on the client-side. The web portal is hosted at the AWI Computing and Data Center on a virtual machine using a containerised Docker environment. The system is based on the Apache webserver technology and PHP as the main server-side programming language. For the process, an experienced remote sensing expert is mandatory along with advanced computer hardware. Besides production of the service, these resources are also needed for bug-fixing, the extension of functionality, and for adding of additional content and datasets.

ALEX is fully produced by AWI's permafrost research team and the Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX) web portal is the final product. Quality levels of information provided by ALEX cannot be defined, yet the quality of the information is dependent on the radiometric quality of the input imagery. The availability and radiometric quality of the input imagery tends to be higher in the lower latitudes and lower in high latitudes.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX) provides easy access to information on land surface changes, hot spots of disturbance, and potential areas of active permafrost thaw and erosion on the pan-Arctic scale. Information is provided visually on maps to help interpret the type and intensity of the changes with seamlessly integrated story maps. The story maps combine map content with multimedia and narrative storytelling which provides an interactive approach for communicating the information and engaging with the end users. Via ALEX, the main permafrost region disturbances are identified across continental-scale spatial domains, also allowing quantitative assessments. The key permafrost region disturbances include lake drainage, coastal erosion, thermokarst lake expansion, retrogressive thaw slumps, fire scars, and infrastructure expansion.

The Permafrost Service is provided in several formats. The main entry point is the website (<https://alex.awi.de>) that can be accessed on both computers and smartphones. A Web Map Service (WMS) is offered to more easily re-use the data in existing portals or applications and geographic information system software. The dataset (in the format of a COG) can be bulk downloaded from the PANGAEA repository. The dataset is also available as a layer in the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment for programmers.

To use ALEX, users are required to have a device (smartphone, tablet, laptop, PC) with internet connection and knowledge of how to use websites. Use of ALEX does not require any additional information from other sources. However, it is feasible to overlay other datasets with the service data to derive further insights, if needed. ALEX is free of charge and licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY-4.0), and this is expected not to change. Uncertainties in using the information provided by ALEX include potential errors in the interpretation of the colours used for visualisation. Service developers have taken several measures to avoid this, including the provision of an interactive legend (planning on-going), examples for locations and story maps to explain the changes seen in the change map. When it comes to WMS, usefulness depends on how reliable (is the content available) and fast (short loading time of the content) it is.

Users and Uses of the Service

Users can be distinguished by the uses of the service into the following groups: local community members, planners, stakeholders, landowners, public service employees, researchers, and the general public. Additional user groups can potentially be found in the future.

To find out more about the users of the Permafrost Service and how they benefit from it, a multi-track approach was taken. During multiple research visits to Canada and Alaska, the service developers introduced the ALEX tool to all the identified user groups. They used the feedback from end users to identify potential applications and to improve the tool to better meet their needs. In order to receive well-structured information on the ALEX tool, an online end-user survey was also conducted (see Appendix 2). In addition, the Matomo software, which tracks website visits, alongside the Spatineo web service was installed on the ALEX website. The Spatineo web service tracks WMS usage within the ALEX tool. Furthermore, the service developers received valuable feedback from expert users who have integrated the WMS into their systems. Information gathered through the communication between service developers and end users was shared with the WP5 through the VCA survey and other types of communication.

First, local communities can benefit from the use by monitoring the land surface changes around their village, home, cabin, and camp sites to see where coastal erosion occurs, or lakes change. In addition, wildfire sites can be located through the service. Information on all aforementioned permafrost changes can be used to assess where cultural or traditional resources and places may be affected. Second, information provided by ALEX can be used by both private and official planners in fields such as construction (houses, camps), subsistence (fishing, hunting, harvesting) and leisure (travelling) to “determine hot spots of disturbances and to avoid areas of especially active changes in their planning”. The information can also guide the selection of sites for new infrastructure (e.g. buildings, roads) and support infrastructure vulnerability assessments and assessment of impacts on existing infrastructure in general. Stakeholders can also compare the impacts on their administrative region to other regions. Communication between the local communities and service developers has shown that the service can support the assessment of losses of allotments due to permafrost thaw and how the landscape may change in favour of other activities such as agriculture and animal husbandry. The service also holds value for research and education for the general public.

The end-user survey reached 15 potential service users mainly working in research and governmental institutions with “intermediate” understanding of permafrost processes and landscape changes in the Arctic (8 respondents). Out of all the respondents, five reported being private users and nine business or other professional users. One of the respondents chose not to specify their user group. The survey can be found in Appendix 1.

The Matomo Web Analytics software is used to track ALEX users; however, it is not possible to track the users who directly use the WMS service which would offer more valuable information. Currently, three more specific use cases are identified: In Transport Canada the service is integrated into Web-GIS for Enhanced Maritime Situational Awareness (EMSA), in the Department of Environmental Health and Engineering, Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium the service is in an internal dashboard / ArcGIS online map, and in NWT Centre for Geomatics, Government of the Northwest Territories, the data of ALEX is used in the ArcGIS Pro environment as a source of information on landscape change. Although not identified, other uses of ALEX are likely to exist.

Using Matomo, the user groups (see above) cannot be segmented based on demographics at this stage. The only way to segment the users into groups is based on the service they are using, the ALEX tool, the WMS, the GEE, and the PANGAEA data repository. Users of both ALEX and PANGAEA can be tracked. Different user groups are expected to have slightly different use purposes. For instance, the story maps are targeted primarily towards members of the general public and local community members while the data in the GEE and the repository will be used by researchers. The WMS is expected to be used by professionals such as people working in governmental or tribal institutions. Besides different uses, different user groups may also have different interests in spatial scales; local communities are more focused on the local scale, and governmental institutions are focused on national or regional levels.

3.2.2. Societal benefits

Accurate information on permafrost conditions in the Arctic holds significant societal and economic value. Permafrost underlies approximately 24 % (23 million km²) of the Northern Hemisphere's land area (Zhang et al, 2008). Rising global temperatures are accelerating permafrost thaw, which causes infrastructural damage through ground instability and ecosystem disruption that threatens the lives of local species and communities. Beyond damages to infrastructure, ecosystems and Indigenous ways of living, thawing permafrost releases significant amounts of greenhouse gases, notably carbon dioxide and methane, exacerbating global climate change. These additional emissions are projected to contribute an estimated USD 43 trillion in economic impacts by the end of the twenty-second century (Hope & Schaefer, 2016). Investing in comprehensive permafrost monitoring and predictive modelling is therefore economically prudent. By providing information on land-surface changes, ALEX can inform decision-making related to site selection for subsistence and leisure activities and planning of critical infrastructure for both private and public actors, and support monitoring of changes in the environment, potentially mitigating the huge cost of thawing permafrost. To demonstrate the potential impacts of ALEX, we present the societal and economic costs of thawing permafrost from literature to give an indication on the magnitude of the potential benefits of providing information on land surface changes.

Changes in permafrost affect the livelihoods and cultural identities of Indigenous and local communities living in the Arctic. Subsistence is a question of both livelihood and cultural identity for Indigenous and local communities and is dependent on the Arctic ecosystems that are widely impacted by permafrost degradation (Ramage et al., 2022). Activities related to subsistence are also closely incorporated into the knowledge of the local environment (Ramage et al., 2022), which is changing at a rapid pace, affecting the livelihoods of Arctic residents (Krause, 2022). Adding to subsistence, places themselves can hold symbolic and spiritual importance and significance for people's identity; when places disappear or are impacted by permafrost degradation, it may widely affect the people living in the area (Crate et al., 2017; Crate, 2022). By providing information on the changes in the environment, location and the pace of the changes, ALEX can guide site selection in for subsistence activities, including hunting, whaling, trapping, herding and gathering all kinds of plants and hence can support Indigenous peoples' and local communities' livelihoods and adaptation to climate change.

Climate change-induced permafrost degradation increases the risk of infrastructure damage (Manos et al., 2025; Suter et al., 2019; Hjort et al., 2018; Melvin et al., 2016). These damages are driven by the thickening of the active layer and degradation of near-surface permafrost, which shortens the infrastructure lifespan and increases maintenance and replacement costs (Jin et al., 2024). It is estimated that ca. 70 % of infrastructure in the Arctic is located on permafrost with high potential for degradation

(Hjort et al., 2018). Entire villages are being relocated due to climate impacts (Granger, 2020) and critical infrastructure such as roads, pipelines, railroads, buildings and airports are at risk (Manos et al., 2025; Melvin et al., 2016). Damaged transportation routes may hinder local communities' access to supplies and services (TCRP, 2020). These impacts on infrastructure are already widely evident and the most fundamental infrastructure will be at risk even if the Paris Agreement target is reached (Hjort et al., 2018). Effective mitigation of permafrost-related infrastructure risks depends on a detailed understanding of permafrost characteristics and degradation processes. ALEX supports mitigation of permafrost-related infrastructure risks by providing information on surface changes, disturbance hotspots, and areas vulnerable to thaw and erosion. This information supports cost-effective infrastructure planning, as well as vulnerability and impact assessments of permafrost thaw on existing infrastructure. Better-informed planning may also reduce the risk of health issues that are associated with living in buildings damaged by permafrost thaw and improve the quality of life in general (Allard et al., 2023).

Several estimates for the costs of permafrost thaw on different types of infrastructure exist. Recent studies estimate that permafrost degradation could result in infrastructure damage costs ranging from USD 37 billion to USD 51 billion in Alaska alone under moderate to high emission scenarios (Hjort et al., 2022). Across the broader Arctic region, the cost of permafrost-thaw damage to roads, buildings, airports and railroads is expected to be up to USD 276 billion by mid-century, if carbon emissions and climate trends continue their current trajectory (Streletskiy et al., 2023). Suter et al. (2019) estimate that climate forcing increases the lifecycle replacement costs by USD 15 470 million when compared to the baseline, i.e., situation without climate change. To illustrate the level of impact on different types of infrastructure and for different regions, the projected mean replacement costs estimated by Streletskiy et al. (2023) are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Projected mean replacement costs of different types of infrastructure under the SSP245 and 585 scenarios for study area countries (results of Streletskiy et al., 2023). Million USD-2020.

Country	Roads		Railroads		Airports	Buildings	
	SSP2	SSP5	SSP2	SSP5	SSP5	SSP2	SSP5
Canada	11 914	23 496	2301	2646	101	2000	2359
Finland	3645	6941	0	0	0	1487	1854
Iceland	13	13	0	0	0	2	5
Norway	18 496	29 835	1562	2672	42	3502	3367
Russia	50 645	71 177	11 573	17 403	171	53 000	80 477
Sweden	5046	5543	1523	2091	0	1089	1498
USA (Alaska)	10 057	19 113	1075	2039	220	3029	3394

Table 2 compiles selected findings from studies estimating the projected infrastructure damage caused by permafrost degradation, depicting the magnitude of the potential impacts. Studies are not directly comparable due to differences in methods and data used. **If better planning of infrastructure helps to avoid even 1 % of the total damage, to which ALEX can contribute, the avoided costs range from 370 to 510 million USD by mid-century for Alaska alone** (see Manos et al., 2025). Note that the percentage cost

saving from improved information is unknown; the 1 % is solely used to illustrate the potential scale of avoided costs from better planning.

Table 2. Estimated damages of permafrost degradation on infrastructure.

Region / country	Study	Economic losses	Types of infrastructure	Scenario	Notes
Alaska (US)	Manos et al., 2025	37 (SSP245) to 51 (SSP585) billion dollars by mid-century	buildings, roads	SSP245, SSP585	highly detailed map of infrastructure was used
	Melvin et al., 2016	3000 (RCP4.5) to 4600 (RCP8.5) million dollars (USD-2015) by the end of the century	roads, buildings, airports, railroads, pipelines	RCP4.5, RCP8.5	damage without adaptation
Multiple	Streletskiy et al., 2023	182 (SSP245) to 276 (SSP585) billion dollars by mid-century (USD-2020)	roads, railways, airport runways, buildings	SSP245, SSP585	USA (Alaska), Canada, Russia, Iceland, Sweden, Finland, Norway
	Suter et al., 2019	71 408 million dollars by mid-century (RCP8.5, USD-2017)	roads, railroads, pipelines, airports/ports, buildings	RCP8.5	USA (Alaska), Canada, Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Russia

Cost reduction for infrastructure stemming from better informed decision processes is a physical impact that does have a market value; therefore, the monetary benefit of ALEX can in theory be assessed using the avoided cost (or cost-loss) method (see more in D5.2). However, the estimation of the monetary benefits of better-informed planning is complex; the temporal realisation of the benefit includes several uncertainties including factors such as learning. For instance, the initial investment to permafrost thaw resilient infrastructure is high, making better-informed planning of infrastructure a net cost in the beginning while inducing significant cost savings in the future. This makes selecting accurate discount rate and time span challenging. Moreover, to estimate the economic benefits of ALEX as accurately as possible, more information on the uptake and use of the service is required. At this stage, information on the first six months of ALEX has been collected through Spatineo web traffic tool analysis and initial impressions of potential use has been collected via end-user survey. While using this information is practically possible, more accurate results over a couple of years are required to obtain more reliable estimates. Significant increase in the user base is expected as uptake of ALEX progresses. Most users that engaged in the end-user survey were using the service for the first time, after all. In addition, benefits will likely grow as existing users gain greater proficiency in its use.

When assessing societal benefits of an information service, it is critical to consider the relative influence of different data types provided by ALEX, i.e. accounting for the information difference of a new service compared to existing services, as discussed throughout this deliverable. Since similar services are rare, the benefits of ALEX are likely to be significant and hold a high benefit potential, both monetary and non-monetary. The longstanding lack of monitoring and data on the impacts of climate change on the Arctic population is well recognised (Knapp & Trainor, 2015; Crate et al., 2017; TCRP, 2020), and ALEX has the potential to contribute to addressing this information gap. Even if ALEX's overall impact on infrastructure

decisions in detailed planning at the micro level is likely to be moderate when compared to the value of subsurface information, that is the main indicator of permafrost stability (Bjella et al., 2020), its contribution is still likely to be significant. Given the substantial monetary and non-monetary costs associated with infrastructure damage from permafrost degradation, even the slightest contribution of ALEX in infrastructure related mitigation can translate into significant benefits.

While ALEX can provide information that supports adaptation, it should be noted that information alone does not guarantee adaptation, especially in the case of permafrost degradation. In general, it is crucial to acknowledge the specific decision-making contexts and barriers of benefit realisation in socio-economic evaluations of climate services (André et al., 2021). Adapting to permafrost degradation requires major investments and technical expertise (TCRP, 2020), meaning that not everyone has the same opportunities to adapt. This is especially prevalent for the infrastructure related activities, but also for site selection in subsistence and leisure. Sites available for hunting and fishing can be located too far away after a relocation. Local communities most often do not have the monetary resources that are required for relocation or repair of the infrastructure. (TCRP, 2020.) The issue requires action and more available funding opportunities for the local communities. At the same time, there is a growing interest to invest in infrastructure in the Arctic (e.g., railroads, ports, harbours, pipelines) by the industries (The Polar Connection, 2019). Financial firm Guggenheim compiled an inventory of Arctic infrastructure projects, estimating one trillion dollars of infrastructure investment over the next 15 years (The Polar Connection, 2019), showing a high monetary benefit potential of careful planning. When planning these projects, voices of the Indigenous and local communities must be heard.

In conclusion, ALEX has large potential to generate benefit in infrastructure, subsistence and leisure, especially by supporting site selection. Better informed planning of infrastructure for both the selected site and required construction methods for the selected site can reduce the risk associated with permafrost thaw, thereby potentially reducing the associated costs. Information provided by ALEX can also support vulnerability assessments that provide important information supporting adaptation and preparation activities. For subsistence, information on land surface changes can support a selection of new sites, possibly supporting the livelihoods of people residing in the Arctic. Additionally, although ALEX is mainly targeted towards non-technical users, information provided by ALEX can benefit the scientific audiences. Feedback mechanisms of permafrost thaw are not fully understood, yet. Permafrost contains billions of metric tons of carbon, the amount of which may be released remains uncertain (Miner et al., 2022). Satellite observations may contribute to improving our understanding of how this process is unfolding (Westermann et al., 2015; Teshebaeva et al., 2021; Miner et al., 2022).

3.2.3. Spatineo web traffic tool analysis

In discussions during the project, it became evident that many of the Arctic PASSION pilot services' provider organisations have in place data policies which made transmission of finely grained browser-based or server log-based usage data to WP5 difficult or impossible. WP5 was however, capable of providing a third option that was acceptable to the Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX) service. The solution works by tracking the usage of map components in a service website (see Figure 7).

This option's implementation works via an invisible map layer. When end users use the pilot service map, the browser will request map images from Spatineo's servers and usage data can be collected outside the pilot service's organisation. The log information is anonymised and thus no personal data is collected or

stored. This approach allows tracking of pilot service website map usage. However, it does not track 3rd party websites, desktop GIS applications or other direct integrations to the ALEX Web Service data. The usage data for ALEX was collected from 2024-09-04 to 2025-03-16.

Figure 7. Diagram of how usage analytics can be collected by an external analysis service provider without having to transmit log files from the pilot service provider's servers.

For this analysis, a unique requestor IP address was determined to represent a single user. A single user will make several requests over time. A request is a single access to the service to retrieve data for a geographic bounding box. A session is defined as a day during which a user has made one or more requests. The IP address needs to be seen as a proxy for an individual user or organisation using the service:

- All usage from a corporate network will typically come from the same IP address and thus appear as one single user
- An individual using the service from different networks will show up as multiple users

Also, due to GDPR regulation IP addresses were anonymised before storage and analysis by removing the last 8 bits of each address. This can, however very rarely, result in some individual users being calculated as a single user. It can also make classification (country, user type) less accurate.

Figure 8. Number of sessions per week.

Figure 9. Distribution of user types across all sessions.

Figure 10. Top 15 countries of origin across all sessions.

Figures 11–15 show examples of usage data from Spatineo Monitor.

Figure 11. Number of requests over time.

Figure 12. Service user location weighted by the number of requests

Figure 13. Geographical areas the users of the service have been interested in.

Not surprisingly, most users have been interested in Arctic areas when visiting the Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX).

Country	Addresses	Requests
Denmark	9	530,202
Canada	78	317,310
Germany	201	297,226
United States	240	185,166
Finland	13	36,460
France	14	24,492
United Kingdom	30	14,199
South Korea	8	12,633
Belgium	3	12,500
Switzerland	11	12,437
Download	748	1,521,373

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Figure 14. Top 10 countries by the number of requests to the service.

Organization/ISP	Addresses	Requests
ku.dk	2	528,828
██████████:32.0/24	1	129,261
██████████:a3::/48	1	100,513
t-ipconnect.de	39	88,233
██████████:27::/48	1	46,089
██████████:1.0/24	1	44,981
awi.de	1	40,543
rogers.com	3	33,220
██████████:213.0/24	1	23,295
telefonica.de	20	22,764
Download	748	1,521,373

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Figure 15. Breakdown of usage by segment (organisation or ISP), top 10 by number of requests.

Figure 15 shows that the largest user group by the number of requests is the University of Copenhagen (ku.dk). Other identified organisations in the top 10 are ISPs (t-ipconnect.de, rogers.com and telefonica.de). AWI itself is number 7 on the list.

This analysis to detect organisations or ISPs is based on a reverse DNS lookup of the IP address of the user. If no reverse DNS record was available, the anonymised IP address is shown. The anonymised IP addresses are further scrambled in the image as they offer no meaningful data in this context.

However, further analysis on the request spike in December 2024 shows that the access from the University of Copenhagen seems to be an automated process since the number of requests per hour is static over two days, day and night. Geographically, most requests were targeted around the Teshekpuk Lake in Alaska and Lena Delta Wildlife Reserve and Yakutsk in the Sakha Republic in Siberia. These areas could be identified by using Spatineo Monitor by focusing on areas of a heightened number of requests made to the ALEX service. Figure 16 shows the suspected automated request pattern over time as well as the relative amount of other usage during the period of expected automated usage of the ALEX service from the University of Copenhagen. The map shows areas of interest from the chosen user segment (Denmark) at a global scale. The layer information should be disregarded.

Figure 16. Usage over the period of assumed automated usage of the ALEX service from the University of Copenhagen.

During the analysis period, the ALEX team held four events that were determined to possibly affect the usage of the service. These events are listed in Table 3, and the start of each event is highlighted in Figure 17, showing the number of requests to the service over time.

Table 3. Events where the ALEX team held presentations about the permafrost service

Event number	Dates	Event
1	16.09.2024	Presentation of ALEX during a school visit of the UndercoverEisAgenten project at Moose Kerr School, Aklavik, Canada https://arcticpassion.eu/blog/Aklavik
2	9.-13.12.2024	AGU 2024, Washington https://www.agu.org/annual-meeting
3	9.-12.12.2024	ArcticNet 2024, Ottawa https://arcticnet.ca/ac2024-conference/
4	8.-10.01.2025	DACH Permafrost Conference, Davos https://www.wsl.ch/de/veranstaltungen-und-kurse/dach-permafrost-conference/

Figure 17. Number of requests over time and highlights the times at which highlighted events were made. Event numbering matches table 3.

Overall, there seems to be little trend showing increased usage after the events. However, the automated data access by the University of Copenhagen does coincide with two major events (AGU 2024 and ArcticNet 2024).

Figure 18. Areas of interest for ALEX users in North America.

Figure 19. Areas of interest for ALEX users in Greenland and North Europe.

Figure 20. Areas of interest for ALEX users in Russia.

Figures 18, 19 and 20 show the geographic hotspots by ALEX users by the number of requests. Usage is plotted on a grid for each figure and the grid cells are coloured based on the number of requests targeting that area. Note that the heatmap legend for each figure is different. The figures also contain vertical and horizontal artifacts due to the technical implementation of the ALEX map (tiled requests).

By combining the information of the user's user group (like in Figure 9) with the temporal variability of the usage (as seen in Figures 16 and 17) it is possible to get an even deeper insight of the users' behaviour. This kind of analysis was made in the work by Donner (2022), as presented in section 3.8.2.

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3.3. Arctic service 3: State of the Arctic Environment

The State of the Arctic Environment service is a website consisting of information about the state of the Arctic. It provides maps, consented Indigenous Knowledge and scientific information about selected Arctic features, so-called key indicators. Broad, pan-Arctic information about the key climate, environment and ecosystem indicators altogether gives users a better understanding of the status and changes of these interconnected parts of the Arctic system. The information on the website will be divided into four categories: terrestrial, cryosphere, marine and atmosphere. The service is currently under development, and it is not yet available online.

3.3.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 21. Value chain for Arctic service 3.

Data and Production of the Service

Data about the key climate, environment and ecosystem indicators (including terrestrial, cryosphere, marine and atmosphere) creates the base for the information that the state of the Arctic Environment is providing. Geographic information (GIS data) for maps, scientific information (written or graphical presentations), stories from the knowledge holders and website development skills are needed in the production of the service. The main institutions developing the service are the Nordic Polar Institute (NPI; lead), Met Norway (MetNo; data) and GRID-Arendal (website development, content review and edit). In addition, the selection of key indicators, scientific reviews of key indicators, data search and selection, editing, cartography, website development, and selection of stories (Snowchange) are also necessary for functional service. The selected indicators can be added or updated at a later stage.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

The service offers information about the climate indicators of the Arctic, both physical and biological, with extended text and indicator graphs. The service is offered in a Web GIS solution, but it has not been launched yet. In the future, the service is meant to complement existing services that rely either only on remote sensing data or only cover a single domain (e.g. ocean, cryosphere). The service is intended not for operational use, but rather to provide users with a comprehensive understanding of the current state

of the Arctic environment, as well as to offer insights into the observational data available for those seeking more detailed information and resources elsewhere.

Users and Uses of the Service

Prospective user groups are decision makers at various levels in government agencies, directorates, ministries as well as local communities. In addition, general public (if interested) and scientific community. It is supposed that some users will use the service to get a broader understanding, while others will focus on selected "domains" such as climate or ecosystem. Some will likely use it as a guide to find more detailed information elsewhere. Based on feedback through interviews with potential users it will mostly be used for educational purposes.

Users will need a screen device (e.g. computer) with access to internet to use the service. They also need to understand English, which is the language of the service. Users do not add supplementary information for gainful use, but information can be used in combination with other data sources. Former level of knowledge and interest in the Arctic environment and the specific key indicators may have an impact on the eventual usefulness of the information provided by the service.

The potential benefits of the service are having comprehensive data and information about the state of the Arctic under one portal. This can help users to save time in finding the information or lead them to the correct source of information they are looking for. Among policymakers, the service can also support better decision-making through credible, comprehensive and scientific information. Specifying how different (demographic) user groups are utilising the service could be possible with further (potential) end-surveys, but not through website analytics since users do not set up accounts or go through an info registration process to use the service. User registration is not desired because it can limit the number of users getting onboard. Tracking of the use purposes could be done through site analytics based on web server logs, but indicators have not been identified. Tracing the decisions made using the service is not possible in a current maturity of the service.

The economic evaluation of AS3 is not conducted due to the lack of quantitative data about the impacts (actions of the users) and costs of the service. Based on the VCA and current maturity of the service, the benefits of the service stem, for example, from the time saved when searching for relevant information about the Arctic. The economic value of time saved could be defined through a method called value of time (VoT). VoT is the value, measured either in utility or monetarily, that a person holds for a particular increment of time given some activity or purpose. VOT is often used in transportation modelling, policy analysis, and economic appraisal to value people's time in economic terms. (Fournier & Christofa, 2020.) However, in the absence of data on the impacts, time saved by users and the number of users, a hypothetical VoT analysis would involve too many assumptions for it to be meaningful for the study to be carried out. Hence, the societal benefits of AS3 are assessed based on the VCA and literature review.

3.3.2. Societal benefits

Recent research highlights the importance of monitoring key indicators to assess Arctic climate change and its impacts. Long-term observations reveal significant shifts in various components of the Arctic system, including intensification of the hydrological cycle, sea ice decline, and permafrost warming. These changes have cascading effects on Arctic ecosystems, altering carbon cycling, vegetation patterns, and animal distributions (Box et al., 2019.) Researchers also emphasise the need for urgent monitoring of food

and water security based on essential indicators in the Arctic (Nilsson et al., 2013). Certain environmental indicators, such as deep permafrost temperatures, vegetation biomass, and satellite-derived canopy reflectance, act as effective filters for detecting climate change signals amidst annual variability (Hobbie et al., 2017). Long-term monitoring of physical components, including the atmosphere, ocean, and sea ice, provides valuable insights into ongoing trends in the Arctic system (Richter-Menge et al., 2006). These studies underscore the importance of continued observation and analysis of Arctic environmental indicators.

To secure the overall well-being of the Arctic and in the Arctic, providing credible, comprehensive and science-based information for different stakeholders is crucial to meet the common good. Through the Arctic Service 3, all stakeholders will find information that combines different essential Arctic indicators and variables to create a bigger picture about the state of the Arctic environment. Improved awareness enables, for example, more efficient management of resources such as fisheries and extractive industries, while taking into account environmental impacts and local communities, potentially transitioning to benefit co-management in the Arctic (Cole et al., 2014; Petrov & Tysiachniouk, 2019). Addressing the ongoing and prospective challenges requires collaborative efforts to resolve conflicts and promote both prosperity and sustainable development in the region by building on collaboration between science and local knowledge. This knowledge supports sound, science-based strategies for addressing climate change impacts while balancing economic development and community needs.

The scientific community also seems to unanimously agree that monitoring changes and indicators in the Arctic is crucial for monitoring and understanding climate change around the world. Hence, enhanced understanding of Arctic processes and monitoring is crucial for predicting future trajectories of sea ice and climate change, which have global ramifications (Maslowski et al., 2012). This means that a better understanding of the state of the Arctic offers numerous benefits for both people living in the Arctic and those living outside Arctic regions. Current information about terrestrial, cryosphere, marine and atmosphere indicators in the Arctic included in AS3 provides valuable insights and information for monitoring climate change on a global scale.

Beside accelerating environmental changes in the Arctic, the region is undergoing rapid transformation, driven by economic expansion and rising demand for natural resources. Its future lies in the hands of a diverse array of decision-makers, including individual citizens, policymakers, governments, corporations, industries, environmental organisations, Indigenous communities, the scientific community, and others. With such a wide range of stakeholders - often holding conflicting interests - there is smouldering potential for tension (Cole et al., 2014). Enhancing awareness and understanding of the Arctic's changing conditions can support informed decision-making, foster cooperative governance, and help mitigate potential conflicts. Furthermore, a better understanding of the Arctic facilitates international collaboration, improves governance, and helps avoid conflicts in the region (Bigras, 2013). By providing comprehensive information about the state of the Arctic, AS3 can provide a broad range of information on key variables and changes in the Arctic to different stakeholders.

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3.4. Arctic service 4: Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA)

The integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA) service is a web mapping service designed to improve access to wildfire-related information and products from a variety of sources. Focusing on a local scale, INFRA enables the generation and dissemination of wildfire messages tailored to non-scientific end users, including municipalities, Indigenous peoples, and local communities. The service has been developed following a multilevel approach to be able to flexibly manage different groups of users and different needs. Level 0 is freely available to all and accessible at the [Italian Arctic Programme Portal \(PRA\)](#), and it currently covers areas in Sacha-Yakutia, Fennoscandia and Alaska. Levels 1 and 2 of the service are available but password protected, since they need specific management/governing responsibilities and/or resources (of expertise and budget) from the users. Level 2 has been applied in test mode for two seasons (2021, 2022) in Alaska and Sacha-Yakutia. It is planned to release an operational version for Italy and the Mediterranean region, where INFRA’s numerical weather predictions (NWP) outputs are freely available without extra costs. The NWP model is also freely available for operational implementation in Arctic areas. The PRA portal also includes comprehensive documentation and additional information to learn more about INFRA and how products and information at disposal are generated.

3.4.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 22. Value chain for Arctic service 4.

Data and Production of the service

The data for the INFRA service is extracted from the [Global Wildfire Information System \(GWIS\)](#), a joint initiative of the GEO and the Copernicus Work Programs. The only exception is a fuel map evaluated on an annual basis from MODIS observations (1 km resolution), making use of a new fuel type mapping methodology (Nestola et al., 2025). The information provided is based on satellite and ground-based forest fire observations, weather forecasts, and observations of land and vegetation conditions. INFRA is based on several modules and IT platforms, the most important being:

1. INFRA-AEGIS: A web-GIS platform through which it is possible to present, combine, and integrate all the informational layers produced by INFRA or collected from other sources and services.
2. INFRA-SENTRY: A platform to distribute information and messages to users. Messages can easily be handled and adapted to specific needs and generated following the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP).

INFRA modules are developed to be installed in a cloud computing service, increasing accessibility and flexibility of use. This also reduces the need for local hardware and software infrastructure in production. Higher levels (below) of implementation of INFRA require additional expertise and hardware.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

The INFRA service aims to simplify access to relevant information and products on wildfires and make it possible to transform, integrate and disseminate the information. The service offers users the current status regarding wildfire issues in the area of interest and enhances users' understanding of wildfire-related events by offering insights into patterns, perceptions, and risk assessments. The INFRA-AEGIS service also provides information on ignition risks, active fires, and burned areas (damage assessment). Evolution of risks up to 8–9 days is included. Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) has also developed a similar web service for monitoring Arctic wildfires and related risks. However, the service developed by FMI is aimed more towards research users and developers (see more at [Arctic Firedanger](#)).

The information is delivered through web-GIS layers on the INFRA-AEGIS IT platform, which is accessible via the web. Data is visualised on maps, with options to highlight areas of interest and calculate distances and areas. The information can also be provided in textual formats, either free text or based on pre-organised templates, and disseminated via phone, email, or other channels. Thanks to its modularity a multi-level implementation strategy is considered when aligning the use of the INFRA service to user interests, capacities, and resources. Depending on the level of implementation, phone (direct and SMS) and email can be involved. Third-party platforms, such as social media, may also be involved at a later stage. Summary of different levels of INFRA:

LEVEL 0: Collect, Integrate, Interpret and Transform Information

Level zero has been implemented up to the operational mode and made accessible for three target areas in [Sacha-Yakutia](#), [Fennoscandia](#) and [Alaska](#), each of about 1500 x 1500 km. The computing cloud environment makes it easy to add other target areas on demand. There is no limit to the area size at this level.

LEVEL 1: Produce And Disseminate Tailored Messages

INFRA-SENTRY will transform and distribute textual messages across mediums and platforms (SMS, e-mail, phone calls, social media, to other computer/services, etc.) through specific plugins. The system will store them in CAP (Common Alerting Protocol) Standard. Dissemination of information and alerts can be customised. It will be possible to order simple actions, such as automatically activating a relay.

LEVEL 2: Meteo Information, Additional Risk Indexes and Parameters

[Numerical weather prediction module \(MOLOCH 1.3 km resolution\)](#) developed at CNR-ISAC is added, supplying 13 additional information layers to INFRA-AEGIS. In addition to NWP outputs, several risk indices (e.g. fire behaviour and ignition risk) and other information parameters increase GIS information layers in INFRA-AEGIS.

LEVEL 3: Automatic Early Warning Observing Network

Information on wildfires arising from ground observing systems (based on automatic instrumentation) and/or individual inhabitants can also be managed. This level is not yet developed since it's dependent on the specific needs and resources at disposal to implement systems to collect in-situ data.

Users and Uses of the Service

Prospective users encompass individuals at risk of wildfire exposure, organisations, local municipalities, NGOs, fire management professionals, and emergency managers involved in wildfire management. Focusing on a local scale, INFRA provides the possibility to generate and distribute messages on wildfires that are tailored to non-scientific end users like municipalities, as well as Indigenous peoples and local

communities. Thanks to the modularity, users can adapt INFRA and the information it provides to best fit their own needs and activities – the service can cover a wide spectrum of specific needs oriented to the local and regional scale, as local wildfire services are strongly related to the characteristics of the area they cover, as well as the users and stakeholders they serve. These different user groups are expected to use the service differently. For example, emergency services and other governmental bodies may use the information for operational decision-making, while citizens may use it for personal safety. User information is not allowed to be collected automatically, so an end-user survey could be conducted to collect more information about the users and their use purposes. End-user engagement could also help differentiate users by age, gender, income, and organisational affiliation, as well as scope of use based on the demographic factors. In Level 1, user login is needed so once the service is launched, it would be possible to differentiate and monitor usage patterns, but with the current information, it is not possible to quantify the impacts of the service.

The platform is user-friendly and does not require advanced IT skills or equipment - only internet access and basic computer knowledge are needed to retrieve the information. At higher levels of implementation, SMS alerts and automatic early warnings may simplify the use even further. While still in its early stages, key uncertainties include the quality of user guidelines and the potential lack of user training. Improvements are underway to provide better instructions and interpretation guidance. Regulatory factors, such as access rules and responsibilities, could also affect service use. Users can integrate the service information with data from other sources, for example, checking multiple websites for weather forecasts. When compared to similar services, the INFRA service offers advantages through its focus on a local scale and tools designed to generate user-specific messages.

In the last year, developers of AS4 and AS5 started to explore the integration of INFRA with AURORAE and include information on air quality conditions during wildfires. Dialogue with Indigenous and inhabitants clearly indicates that there is strong attention and a need for this information. Such integration will provide a significant addition to the social benefit of INFRA.

3.4.2. Societal Benefits

The INFRA service addresses the need to better monitor, communicate and understand the wildfires in the Arctic that cause extensive damage to both human health and ecosystems. Recent studies highlight the increasing frequency and impact of wildfires in the Arctic, particularly in Siberia. The decadal frequency of wildfires in the Siberian Arctic tripled from 2001–2010 to 2011–2020, with a 2.6-fold increase in burnt area (Kharuk et al., 2022). As one might expect, while the number of Arctic fires has increased, the economic damage from wildfires has also increased. Economic costs of Arctic wildfires are far-reaching and include damage to biodiversity, infrastructure, and human health, particularly in regions like the Sakha Republic (Yakutia), where wildfires are a common threat (Zarovnyaeva & Danilova, 2021).

A comprehensive report by Butry et al. (2017) assesses wildfire management in the United States and outlines the full spectrum of wildfire-related costs and losses, providing both estimates and methodological approaches for quantifying them. These figures can support economic modelling (cost-plus-net-value-change) and enable estimation of the overall *economic burden* of wildfires, which means the total economic impact of wildfires on the U.S. economy. The report decomposes damages and losses into intervention costs (prevention/preparedness, mitigation, suppression, and cross-cutting) and direct and indirect wildfire-related (net) losses. The report estimated the annualised costs at \$7.6–\$62.8 billion

and annualised losses at \$63.5–\$285 billion, meaning that the total annualised economic burden of wildfire ranges between \$71.1 and \$347.8 billion (2016 USD) only in the United States. (Butry et al., 2017.)

One of the main concerns associated with wildfires is the severe impact of wildfire smoke on air quality, which poses significant risks to human health and results in substantial healthcare costs. Wildfire smoke contains harmful pollutants, including particulate matter and carcinogenic compounds such as benzo[a]pyrene. These fires are not only local threats but also contribute to broader atmospheric pollution. For example, global wildfires have been shown to account for 29.3 % of the annual average benzo[a]pyrene concentrations in Arctic air from 2001 to 2020 (Song et al., 2022). The resulting health impacts are profound: an estimated 21 000 excess (premature) deaths per year between 2001 and 2020 were attributed to wildfires in Arctic Council countries, with approximately 8 000 of those occurring in non-Arctic Council countries (Silver et al., 2024). These findings highlight the far-reaching and transboundary health consequences of wildfire pollution, underlining the importance of addressing wildfires not only as ecological disasters but also as major public health and economic challenge.

With further development and co-design, the INFRA wildfire risk service can play a critical role in preventing these damages and reducing associated costs. By integrating early warning systems, real-time monitoring, risk mapping, and decision-support tools, such a service can help citizens, local governments, and land managers take timely action to prevent exposure to harmful pollutants, ignition, manage vegetation, and respond more effectively to emerging fire threats (Bowman et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2022). Proactive use of wildfire risk information can reduce exposure to hazardous smoke, limit the spread of fires, and ultimately lower the incidence of smoke-related health conditions. In doing so, it can significantly decrease both the human toll and the economic burden associated with wildfire-related air pollution – especially in healthcare and emergency response costs.

Beside the extensive economic damage and losses arising from the wildfires, there are other various environmental impacts of wildfires. Tundra wildfires in Alaska release significant amounts of greenhouse gases that contribute to climate warming through positive radiative forcings (Moubarak et al., 2023). Arctic soils have historically stored large amounts of carbon, particularly in wet, boggy regions of Western Siberia, but increasing wildfires threaten to shift this region from a carbon sink to a carbon source by releasing stored carbon from soil into the atmosphere (Coogan et al., 2019). However, the long-term carbon dynamics in the Arctic remain uncertain because of the countervailing trend due to increasing aboveground carbon storage through enhanced vegetation growth (Kharuk et al., 2015; Kharuk et al., 2019). This is supported by remote sensing in the Arctic, where the 'greening of tundra' results from more favourable growing conditions, enhancing carbon sequestration (Vickers et al., 2016; Bhatt e al., 2016).

Kharuk et al. (2022) study on wildfire dynamics in the Siberian Arctic suggest that fire frequency and extent will continue to increase under current climate trends but the relationship of fire to climate is based not just on continuous climate trends, but on heat waves. In addition, with continued regional warming, the role of lightning as a source of wildfire ignition is likely to increase both because of the increased availability of dry fuel as well as from a direct increase in lightning frequency. While it's clear that extreme wildfires have substantial economic, social and environmental impacts, there is still uncertainty whether such events are inevitable features of the Earth's fire ecology or a legacy of poor management and planning (Bowman et al., 2017). Hence, better services for monitoring and calculating the risk and actions needed are vital in future wildfire management. In addition, commonly regarded as "remote unused land", the circumpolar Arctic is increasingly the focus of modern industrialisation, particularly for resource

extraction. The implications of increased wildfires, particularly in western Siberia, will pose additional challenges for natural gas and petroleum exploration and utilisation. These findings underscore the need for improved wildfire management and prevention strategies in the Arctic region.

Since one of the main economic concerns of wildfires is the costs for human health, INFRA is providing emission and air concentration maps originating from wildfires to AURORAE (air quality forecast service, AS5). Together, INFRA and AURORAE (AS5) may decrease morbidity and mortality from air pollution due to better awareness and communication of wildfires and air quality. The potential economic benefits from avoided costs of air pollution in the Nordic countries are estimated under the AS5.

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3.5. Arctic service 5: Air Quality Forecast for Arctic Communities (AURORAE)

The AURORAE (Air qUality foRecast foR Arctic communitiEs) service is a web interface consisting of a visual tool to monitor the air quality of the North European countries on a daily basis and to provide a two-day forecast of particulate matter (PM) concentrations. Air pollution is the main environmental health problem in the EU and AURORAE service aims to contribute addressing the issue by providing air quality forecast. The forecast is developed by combining information from in-situ observations and CAMS (Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service) forecasts to locally produce more accurate forecasts of atmospheric PM₁₀ (particulate matter with the diameter less than 10 µm) at about one hundred observational sites in the European Arctic and near-Arctic (Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Iceland).

The web page is designed for non-scientific users such as communities, stakeholders and citizens. The air pollution near-real-time concentrations and the forecast are visualised on the map as two separate layers, each monitoring station is represented as a dot – based on its colour the air quality is classified from good to unhealthy. Improved forecasts, historical observations and information on air quality at observational sites are then made easily accessible to citizens, policy makers and other stakeholders through a dedicated AURORAE website.

3.5.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 23. Value chain of Arctic service 5.

Data and Production of the Service

Production of the AURORAE forecasts requires historical and current hourly observations of PM₁₀ from stations in the European Arctic. Observations are obtained from EEA (European Environmental Agency) database of air quality *in-situ observations* in Europe and FMI (Finnish Meteorological Institute) observations from Finnish *air quality observational sites* as well as nine European CAMS models produced forecasts of PM₁₀ concentrations since January 2020. The EU’s CAMS provides monitoring and forecasting of air pollution concentrations produced by eleven mathematical models simulating atmospheric lifecycle of pollutants and assimilating *observations* over the whole Europe. At the global scale, CAMS provides

monitoring and forecasting of air quality and meteorological conditions. AURORAE uses forecasts of meteorological conditions from the global CAMS [model](#). It also downloads data from CAMS global maps of estimated wildfire PM₁₀ emissions and European maps of atmospheric concentrations of PM₁₀ originating from wildfires. Four years of historical observations and forecasts from 2020 to 2023 are used for the parameter estimation of the two NN (Neural Network) models. In-situ observations and CAMS forecasts in 2024 are then involved in the NN model validation and forecast comparison with CAMS model forecasts.

In the operational AURORAE implementation, the latest in-situ observations and CAMS forecasts are downloaded each day. The last 24 hours of observations from 106 stations are added to the historical archive. Together with the 48-hour forecasts by CAMS models, they are then used for the production of 48-hour long atmospheric PM₁₀ concentration forecasts at each station. The latest emission and air concentration maps of PM₁₀ originating from wildfires are downloaded from CAMS and interpolated on the Arctic PASSION's INFRA (Integrated Fire Risk Management) service geographical domain and provided to the users of the INFRA service. The download and forecast cycle are ready each day at around 1 AM CET.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

The AURORAE service offers air PM₁₀ forecast information for the following 48 hours at the monitoring stations in Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland. The format of the service is an interactive map with dots representing stations, coloured according to the health impacts of the observed and forecasted PM₁₀ concentration levels. Users can click on the selected dot and visualise the historical and real-time air pollution data as well as the 48-hour long forecast at each station. The users can also download historical data and forecasts in the form of text files. The service improves the PM₁₀ forecast at observational sites in Northern EU countries with the application of NN models. It also provides non-scientific users with an easily accessible web tool in which they can navigate to check air pollution in real-time close to their community, consult the forecast and download it as a text file.

The website is currently hosted at website (aurorae.azurewebsites.net) and linked from the Arctic PASSION project website (<https://arcticpassion.eu/data/>). The software developed in the service for the download of observations and CAMS forecasts, processing of data, production of NN forecasts, and the website graphical interface has a public license. The software will be available for download at the end of the Arctic PASSION project, affecting positively its societal benefit in the long-term. The software will provide a possibility to apply the service with local observations at any observational site in the European Arctic.

No third parties can influence the reception or have own access requirements to the service. The only barriers recognized are related to the used data source. Currently, the data used is openly accessible and covers Europe. If the forecast provided by the service was improved by using high resolution ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) weather forecast, it would require a subscription and an annual fee.

Users and Uses of the service

The service is not available in full operation yet, which limits the assessment of its users. However, the AURORAE service is aimed at citizens, communities and policymakers in the Arctic. AURORAE provides

information that combines local observations from stations in the Arctic and European CAMS model forecasts, producing more accurate air pollution forecasts at observational sites than those by the original CAMS models. It further provides a graphical web interface that facilitates access for the general public to information on past and current observations and two days long forecasts. Different user groups are expected to have different use purposes of the service. Observations and forecasts of atmospheric PM₁₀ concentrations can be used by citizens from local communities to plan their outdoor activities and reduce their exposure to air pollutants. For example, a citizen can use the service to check air pollution forecasts in their region and take action accordingly – close windows, wear a mask, and limit their displacement. Policymakers can use the historical and real-time information to respond to major local air pollution events, like those resulting from wildfires (announce warnings or give recommendations) and to implement effective policies for reducing atmospheric PM₁₀ pollution. The use of the service requires a laptop or other electronic device and an internet connection. No complementary information is required prior to using the service. At the current implementation level of the service, it is not possible to track the users and how the service is used.

According to the VCA and literature, the service generates benefits primarily by increasing the awareness of air pollution, which can lead to positive impacts on human health. Better awareness of air pollution, and being able to avoid it, can lead to savings in healthcare and prevent premature deaths in the Arctic due to air pollution. However, there are already existing services providing air quality information which can limit the additional benefits rising from AURORAE service. One similar competing service, for example, is [PlumeLabs](#) which provides forecasts based on a global network of stations and machine learning, which concentrates globally on big cities with traffic-induced air quality issues. CAMS also provides a graphical website access to their air pollution [forecasts](#), although it is more targeted to scientists. In all Nordic countries, the national hydro/meteorological services also provide air quality information through their website and mobile phone applications. Due to the maturity of the service and uncertainties relating to the share of benefits (and later on the share of users), the quantified impact of the AURORAE service cannot be assessed. However, an economic assessment of the avoided costs of air pollution information and the partial potential benefits from air pollution information are presented below.

3.5.2. Societal benefits

According to the European Environmental Agency (EEA, 2023), air pollution is the main environmental health problem in the EU, and 97 % of the urban population in Europe is exposed to concentrations of PM above the health-based guideline level set by the World Health Organisation (WHO). In 2015 exposure to PM_{2.5} was responsible for 4.2 million deaths, accounting for 7.6 % of all global deaths in a single year and, respectively for 103.1 million disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) accounting for 4.2 % of global DALYs (Cohen et al., 2017). In the Arctic, air pollutant concentrations are generally lower than in other parts of Europe, but due to specific weather conditions in more densely populated areas, air pollution can reach high levels that are well above the health safety limits recommended by the WHO. To tackle the huge negative impacts of air pollution, the European Commission set the EU Action Plan: "Towards a Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil". The initiative provides a vision for 2025 and targets for 2030, such as improving air quality to reduce the number of premature deaths. While the objective of the EU Action Plan is to reduce air pollution, AURORAE aims to raise awareness of air pollution so that people can avoid exposure to it, potentially creating health and well-being benefits for individuals and society. Health-related economic welfare benefits are not the only potential benefits from the AURORAE tool. The various

recommendations provided on the AURORAE website in case of peak pollution can result in lowering the overall emissions. For example, it is recommended to use bikes instead of cars, or to use less polluting/more efficient heating systems at home. Access to information about air pollution may encourage people to act to reduce pollution, particularly if pollution is high. This concept is based on the understanding that individuals need to first recognise a given condition as a problem and the action opportunities available, before they can be expected to respond accordingly (Bickerstaff & Walker, 1999).

The health implications of air pollution are extensive, spanning from respiratory illnesses and cardiovascular diseases, such as asthma, coronary heart disease and allergic sensitisation (Yang et al., 2012; Thurston et al., 2017; Eguiluz-Gracia, 2020), to even neurological disorders affecting cognitive functioning (Louis et al., 2023; Aguilar-Gomez, 2022). Air pollution causes health effects that impact individuals in both short-term and long-term. In the short-term, exposure to air pollutants can cause immediate health problems such as respiratory irritation, coughing, and shortness of breath as well as increase in hospital admissions and emergency room visits for respiratory and cardiovascular problems (Chen et al., 2024). Conversely, long-term exposure to high concentrations of PM increases the development of chronic respiratory diseases, including asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), leading to a decline in pulmonary function, which is associated with increased lung cancer morbidity in adults (Abbey et al., 1998; Fajersztajn et al., 2017; Nhung et al., 2017). Also, in the long-term exposure to air pollutants has been associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, such as hypertension and heart disease (Jo, 2022). Moreover, growing research evidence suggests that air pollution may have harmful impacts on the brain and contribute to the development of neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases (Xie et al., 2025). Studies also show that long-term exposure to air pollution may affect mental health and lead to an increased risk of depression and anxiety (Hautekiet et al., 2022), as well as have overall effects on subjective well-being (Welsch, 2006). Jung et al. (2025) found that during periods of peak air pollution due to wildfires, mental health-related ED visits, with conditions such as anxiety and depression, significantly increased.

Air pollution and its health effects are a complex global challenge that has varying impacts and responses across the world. These differences are mainly caused by factors such as the level of industrialisation, urbanisation, environmental policies, and socio-economic conditions (Manisalidis et al., 2020; Nascimento & Gouveia, 2024) as well as previous health conditions. People with pre-existing health issues, such as asthma, heart disease, and diabetes, are more vulnerable to the effects of air pollution (Chen et al., 2024). Children and the elderly also face a higher risk due to their developing or weakened respiratory systems. Exposure to polluted air during pregnancy can lead to a higher risk of complications such as preterm birth, low birth weight of newborns and reduced lung function at school age (Bekkar et al., 2020; Usemann et al., 2024). Additionally, socioeconomic factors affect vulnerability to air pollution (So et al., 2022), placing already vulnerable populations and individuals at higher risk for the adverse health impacts.

The primary economic benefits of reducing air pollution (or exposure to) stem from decreased mortality and morbidity rates, as well as enhanced environmental conditions (Williams & Phaneuf, 2019). Especially the reduction of fine particulate matter like PM_{2.5} would have substantial economic benefits through reduced mortality and morbidity. In the prevention of premature deaths, the reductions in PM_{2.5} have been the most significant factor (Williams & Phaneuf, 2019). Fine particulates have substantial non-fatal health and productivity impacts, even at relatively low concentrations. For instance, daily hospital

admissions of children vary with changes in fine particulate levels (Ward, 2015), and the productivity of indoor factory workers declines in response to local concentrations of PM_{2.5} (Chang et al, 2016).

Quantifying the economic burden of air pollution reveals the extent of its impact. For example, in Mumbai, India, the total health-related cost due to ambient air pollution in 2012 was estimated at USD 8 billion, based on a population of 12.4 million (Kumar et al., 2016). Beyond direct health costs, studies also explore how individuals value clean air through their willingness to pay (WTP) for pollution reduction. In a study conducted in China, residents demonstrated a willingness to pay an average of 869 Yuan (approx. €113 in exchange rates of 2020) to reduce PM_{2.5} exposure (Zhang et al., 2020). The study found significant variation in WTP based on demographic factors; males, older individuals (especially those over 60), and residents of Eastern China were found to have higher marginal costs (MC) for clean air. Additionally, individuals with lower levels of education showed a greater WTP, possibly reflecting their higher perceived vulnerability or reduced access to healthcare services. Further evidence by He and Zhang (2021) supports these findings by demonstrating that in Nanjing, China, residents' willingness to pay for improved air quality rises with increased pollution exposure. Specifically, WTP increases by 0.693% for every 1% increase in the current PM_{2.5} concentration. This suggests a growing recognition of the health risks associated with pollution and a stronger public demand for cleaner air as conditions worsen.

Due to the current developmental stage of the service and limitations in available data, it is not possible to quantitatively estimate AURORAE's potential reduction in air pollution-related costs. To illustrate the level of costs induced by poor air quality to health care, which better (more accurate or timely) information can potentially reduce, we are presenting the estimation of avoided costs for each country in which AURORAE operates. The focus is placed on non-market costs: welfare costs in **morbidity** (illness) and **mortality** (premature deaths). The costs and numbers are mainly based on reports on the economic cost of air pollution and economic benefits of air quality improvements by the OECD, done in 2016 and 2021, and European Environmental Agency estimates of morbidity and mortality (EEA, 2024). Following the OECD (2021) calculation of the economic cost of air pollution in Arctic Council countries, the report's results were scaled down to the individual Arctic countries concerned by the AURORAE services (Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Iceland). The OECD (2021) provides economic values per country per capita for morbidity and mortality due to air pollution caused by PM_{2.5}. Those values were multiplied by the population of each respective country to obtain a total cost of morbidity and mortality for all the European Arctic countries. Approach was chosen to obtain comparable units between the specific countries. We recognise that there are country-specific reports on the costs.

The major components of PM are sulfates, nitrates, ammonia, sodium chloride, black carbon, mineral dust and water. Value in the OECD (2021) report also comprises O₃. To separate what portion consists of the effects of PM_{2.5}, the EEA database was used. For each European Arctic countries, the proportion of attributable deaths due to PM_{2.5} was calculated from the total sum of attributable deaths due to PM_{2.5} and O₃. The value in the OECD (2021) report is the improved welfare cost gained from a 50 % reduction in air pollution (scenario of best available techniques used by Arctic Council countries). The values are thus doubled in this report to account for a 100 % air pollution reduction. The range of uncertainty of the cost is set to 40 %. This is estimated from differences in morbidity and mortality estimates between the two OECD reports (OECD, 2016; OECD, 2021) and the EEA (2024) estimates for each country. We also assume uncertainties due to slightly different methods for estimating health impacts and the projected Value of Statistical Life (VSL) in different studies.

The OECD report (2021) includes different factors in avoided costs due to reduced **morbidity**: *reduced respiratory diseases, reduced restricted activity days, and reduced working days lost*. Each value of USD per capita for projected welfare improvements from avoided illness was calculated for PM_{2.5}, and then estimated for PM₁₀ based on the constant correlation between PM10 and PM2.5 concentrations (Zhou et al., 2016). This value was multiplied by the population of each country concerned in the assessment. The results are presented in Table 4 below. As noted, these estimates are based on a complete (100 %) reduction of air pollution-related illnesses, which in practice is unattainable. The results, therefore, represent the theoretical maximum of potential cost savings that could be achieved if all health impacts attributable to air pollution were fully mitigated. The total avoided costs from avoided air pollution-related illnesses in the Nordic countries are estimated roughly at **USD 110 million annually** (Table 4).

Table 4. Welfare cost from morbidity in Arctic Council countries per category and per country (OECD, 2021).

Country	Reduced respiratory diseases	Reduced restricted activity days	Reduced working days lost	Total / country
Denmark	8 966 700	20 744 538	6 770 883	36 482 121
Finland	2 461 589	5 726 695	1 860 044	10 048 328
Norway	11 536 691	21 999 193	17 035 085	50 570 969
Sweden	3 253 183	7 700 547	2 437 869	13 391 599
Total / illness	26 218 163	56 170 973	28 103 881	110 493 017

Cost in **mortality** is defined here as premature deaths due to air pollution. OECD attribute a cost to these deaths with estimates of willingness-to-pay (WTP) based on stated preference (SP) studies (OECD, 2021). The projected welfare improvements from avoided mortality in Arctic Council countries are taken from the 2021 OECD report (Table 5).

Table 5. Attributable deaths due to PM2.5 in Nordic countries in 2022 and projected for 2025 (source: EEA, 2024 & OECD, 2024).

Country	Attributable deaths (PM _{2.5}) 2022 (EEA)	Percentage of deaths attributed to PM _{2.5} (among PM _{2.5} and O ₃) (EEA)	Projection attributable deaths (PM _{2.5} and O ₃) in 2025 (OECD)	Projection attributable deaths (PM _{2.5}) in 2025 (OECD)
Denmark	1 200	70	1134	794
Finland	70	14	850	119
Iceland	0	0	74	0
Norway	350	48	427	205
Sweden	480	40	811	325

The total welfare improvement in Nordic countries from avoided mortality is extracted from the 2021 OECD report, that used the VSL relying on the OECD methodology to calculate country-specific VSL value. The OECD applies a base VSL value of 3 million in 2005 USD, which is adjusted for each country based on its per-capita GDP relative to the OECD average (OECD, 2014). The adjustment takes into account differences in income levels and income elasticities across countries, with higher income elasticities

applied to lower-income countries. The total for all countries concerned is about **USD 1.8 billion annually** (Table 6).

Table 6. Projected welfare cost from mortality in Arctic Council countries for the year 2025. USD per capita, 2017 PPP exchange rates. (OECD, 2021)

Country	Value of statistical life (US dollars, PPP converted, Millions, 2017)	Total mortality cost (USD) per country per year
Denmark	4.98	890 894 157
Finland	4.39	146 867 257
Iceland	5.00	0
Norway	5.56	298 738 110
Sweden	4.83	414 175 355
Total for all countries		1 750 674 879

The total avoided welfare cost (mortality plus morbidity) attributed to PM_{2.5} is estimated at **USD 1.9 billion**. This cost does not include Iceland, as the effect of PM_{2.5} on morbidity and mortality on their population was estimated/reported as close to zero. The estimate has an uncertainty range of 40% due to the inherent uncertainty of cost evaluations and user numbers, which are both approximate values producing 40% different estimates in OECD and EEA reports. Taking this uncertainty range into account and converting the total cost in euros, we obtain a total improved welfare cost of **1.6 billion euros** (983 to 2 293 million euros).

While it is evident that air pollution causes serious health problems and premature deaths, putting a major economic burden on the health care system, the potential economic benefits for AURORAE are difficult to estimate for various reasons as discussed. First, AURORAE is a *new* climate service and is yet to be launched. Therefore, we do not have data on the actual use of the AURORAE. While it would be in practice possible to conduct an ex-ante assessment using assumptions on the use, that comes with significant uncertainty. Moreover, there are existing services providing air quality forecasts, as well as national hydro/meteorological services (NHMS) that provide warnings about the air quality. Even if we had information on the actual use, the challenge with AURORAE can be uncertainty regarding the *differentiation value*, i.e. the added value of AURORAE to the value generated by the existing services. Instead, to illustrate the magnitude of potential benefits to which AURORAE may contribute, we presented results of reports estimating the *avoided welfare cost resulting from a reduction in air pollution* in Arctic countries in general – not the value of AURORAE. It is important to consider certain factors when interpreting the results of the estimation. AURORAE provides information on PM₁₀, comprising particles that are smaller than 10 micrometers (µm). On the other hand, OECD reports estimate economic impacts of PM_{2.5} pollution referring to particles smaller than 2.5 µm. It is generally assumed that at each geographical location there is a strong and constant correlation between PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations (Zhou et al., 2016), meaning that reducing PM₁₀ exposure by a certain percentage by using AURORAE may contribute to lowering the PM_{2.5} exposure by the same percentage. In addition, reporting of the number of deaths and health issues due to air pollution may differ between countries.

Finally, air pollution is one of the major causes of health inequalities around the world, particularly for people of low socioeconomic status, women and elders (Wang et al., 2024). There is a clear disproportion of exposure to air pollution being imposed on marginalised communities. Raising awareness on air

pollution in more remote Arctic communities could contribute to lowering this inequality. Moreover, it has been demonstrated by Fazzini et al. (2023) that combining the latest local observations with forecasts from Copernicus improves the accuracy of air pollution forecasts provided by AURORAE with respect to the existing Copernicus service, but the increased forecast accuracy might not be of primary importance for a general user of air pollution forecasts. AUROARE also provides a regional prediction of air quality allowing for comparison between air pollution levels at different observing stations in the Arctic. It is also based on freely available software providing a tool for local communities to apply the same methodology at observing stations outside of the European Arctic. The additional advantages of AURORAE might further increase the societal benefits of the service.

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3.6. Arctic service 6: Improving safety for shipping in the polar seas (POLARIS)

The POLARIS (AS6) is an operational service to better quantify the risk to a vessel as it navigates through ice-covered waters. The service will improve the POLARIS risk assessment methodology by analysing historical ship traffic coincident sea ice conditions and extending the current method to add a forecasting capability. The POLARIS methodology provides a risk index outcome (RIO) score in near real time to estimate the operational limitations of ships within the local ice conditions and the ship’s corresponding ice class. The service will produce predicted forecasts from hours to days and weeks to months beforehand which can be used for ship-routing and safety decisions. The service is currently in pilot phase and under development. For now, a few selected users receive low resolution forecasts in graphical format automatically via email. Results of the VCA and economic evaluation confirm the initial findings made in the value tree analysis (VTA) presented in D5.1.

3.6.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 24. Value chain for Arctic service 6.

Data and Production of the Service

The POLARIS risk forecasting services are delivered by the Danish and Finnish meteorological institutes (DMI and FMI) that are using satellite data and numerical models for the automated production of POLARIS test products. Data on sea ice concentration, ice thickness, and vessel ice class are integrated to produce an index map that provides both analysis and forecast. The automated production of the service requires coding skills and satellite infrastructure. The information provided cannot be stratified nor segmented in terms of quality level meaning that the service does not provide uncertainty levels related to the information. From the end user's perspective, the quality of the information provided by the service (such as accuracy and timing) can influence the user's decision-making.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

The information provided by AS6 consists of forecasts and near real time RIO indexes (level of risk) that consider local ice conditions and the ice class of the ship. At the time of writing this deliverable, POLARIS is in its trial phase and no official format of the service is yet available. However, in the trial phase a few

selected users receive forecasts in graphical format (test products) automatically via email. The use and retrieval of the information may require marine or polar experience or education.

The forecasts are currently at lower resolution than what the developers would like them to be. Users are encouraged to report their experience in an open format. The feedback may consider matters such as resolution, coverage, product relevance, reliability, colours used and compatibility. The usability of the service is not affected by the channel (e.g. email attachment, web portals, navigation apps etc.) through which the POLARIS users receive the information. The eventual usefulness of the information is affected by product resolution, reliability and update frequency. It is crucial to note that since AS6 is in its pilot phase, analysing possible differences to an existing service has not been considered within the scope of this project.

The service should be considered as an add-on to existing products/services for decision support in polar waters, meaning that POLARIS users are assumed to use other information sources for navigation as well. However, as far as it is known by the service developers, there are no similar POLARIS forecast services producing RIO index maps, in operation currently. However, POLARIS is also available at the Polar view portal (<https://www.polarview.aq/arctic>) in which Arctic Passion test data is used. In addition, the DMI Ice Service has made POLARIS available, derived directly from routine ice charts. This product will be tested by selected users over the coming months, as of the time of writing this deliverable.

Users and Uses of the Service

Users and benefits of POLARIS have been mapped based on end-user survey results (Appendix 3) and communication with the service developers. This type of risk management and decision support services related to sea ice are considered relevant only for marine users operating in sea ice or very close to the sea ice edge. The vessels which have volunteered in testing the products include naval ships, research icebreakers and commercial vessels. More feedback and user experience are needed to identify differentiation in use purposes between users as users might use the service with different goals. It is not possible to disaggregate the data to determine how different user groups are utilizing the service.

POLARIS generates benefits by supporting decision-making related to route planning in polar seas by quantifying the risks associated with navigating through ice-covered waters. This provides ships a better understanding of risks to avoid accidents and improve safety as well as to optimize ship-routing and to avoid costs (incl. environmental damage), time, fuel, and emissions. Additionally, historical data can provide benefits by supporting operators in determining the appropriate ice class of ships required for specific Arctic routes. The use of POLARIS as a tool is a valuable tool for shipowners, operators, and regulators to assess the risks associated with operating in these challenging environments (IMO, 2016).

Referring to the Value Tree Analysis in Perrels et al. (2022), the important segment “ocean prediction” is an important feeder to marine services, but also services end-use sectors directly (and not only via marine services). This indicates that besides generating value through the support it gives to the shipping sector, the service creates value for research and other fields. Additionally, the Societal Benefit Areas of “disaster resilience” and “infrastructure and operations” indicate value for the sea ice service. In Perrels et al. it is highlighted that one ambition may be to extend the services towards local communities via the user domain “marine and coastal processes”. However, the service developers highlight that providing such information for communities would require much higher resolution of local forecast models which do not yet exist and the development of these would be far beyond the scope of this project.

According to the survey for Arctic ship operators (full survey in Appendix x), nowcasting and forecasting sea ice observation data is important for maintaining safety as well as ensuring optimal mix of time and fuel saving. Additionally, ship operators report its importance in time saving and fuel saving as separate goals. Other benefits reported include the support in route planning activities and schedules. The benefits of historical sea ice observation data were reported to include support in designing new vessels' ice class, planning operations as well as maintaining safety and saving time and fuel.

According to the historical analysis (unpublished report) (Arctic PASSION, 2024b), a recent trend shows increased shipping activity in high-risk ice conditions which are primarily found in the Russian Arctic and eastern Greenland. Non-ice-strengthened fishing vessels are the most frequently observed ship type operating in these risky conditions, followed by medium ice-strengthened cargo vessels and tankers. The report highlights that information about the riskiness of the ice conditions is especially valuable for vessels with lower polar classifications. Partial benefits of POLARIS are estimated in the next section for the avoided fuel and emission costs.

3.6.2. Economic evaluation

In the economic evaluation of Arctic Service 6, the avoided fuel and CO₂ emission costs generated through sea ice information are assessed. These avoided costs provide a partial economic value assessment for the Arctic Service 6. Korjonen (2025) has quantified these avoided expenses by applying avoided cost method using a monthly-aggregated AIS-based dataset from 2023 of individual vessels, along with historical price data. Here the results are presented in the context of AS6.

Data

The main dataset used in the analysis is from PAME's Arctic Ship Traffic Data (ASTD) System (ASTD, 2024). The dataset includes quantitative historical information on vessels operating within the Arctic region, with boundaries defined according to PAME (Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment) (see Figure 25a). Thirteen Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) lie within the boundaries of the PAME Arctic Area Proposal as well as open water areas and the Svalbard fisheries zone. Figure 25b illustrates the sea ice extent for March 2023 within the proposed Arctic area.

Figure 25. 25a) PAME Arctic area proposal. 25b) Sea ice extent in the PAME Arctic area Proposal in March 2023. Area of ocean (grid cell =1 km²) with less than 15 percent sea ice concentration is considered ice-free. Source: PAME, ASTD.

In 2023 the total number of ships operating in the PAME area was 11 543. Between 2013 and 2023, the trend in the number of ships has shown an increase (see Figure 26a). In 2020, around the beginning of the covid-19 pandemic, there was a sharp decline in the number of vessels. However, the trend has been increasing since then, although a small drop can be observed between 2022 and 2023. The number of vessels has increased on average 0.72% per year during the period between 2014–2023. This is significantly lower than the 6% annual increase reported by Müller et al. (2023), which is likely due to differences in the geographical boundaries used to define the Arctic. Besides yearly variation, the number of vessels fluctuates also within the year, with the highest number of ships occurring during the summer months (see Figure 26b). The variation in the number of vessels is primarily driven by changes in the number of conventional vessels, while the number of ice-class vessels remains relatively constant throughout the year.

Figure 26. 26a) Annual count of vessels from 2014 to 2023 and 26b) Count of ice-class and conventional vessels throughout the representative year (2023) in the PAME Arctic Area Proposal.

In this analysis, data from 2023 is utilized. The dataset consists of 61 910 observations that represent monthly aggregated information about vessels. The panel structure is uniquely identified by a ship ID and month. Table 7 presents the summary statistics.

Table 7. Summary statistics.

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. dev.
Fuel consumption per month (m3)	61 909	119.1	303.6
CO ₂ emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	385.8	977.3
CO emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	0.9	2.2
Nox emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	7.6	22.9
SO ₂ emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	0.6	2.3
Distance sailed per month (nautical mile)	61 901	1320.8	1360.8
Hours sailed per month (h)	61 901	480.9	275.4
Vessel age (years old in 2024)	61 909	24.5	16.8
Volume (gross tonnage)	56 491	14319.4	26634.1

The ASTD data quality is considered “very accurate” as described in PAME’s data information document (2023). The data is based on Automatic Identification System (AIS) which is a maritime navigation safety

communications system. Regulation 19 in the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) requires that navigational equipment must be installed on all ships of 300 GT (gross tonnage) and larger in international voyages and cargo ships of 500 GT and larger in domestic voyages as well as on all passenger ships regardless of their size. AIS signals provide information such as ship type, position, course, speed and other information related to safety. In ASTD the ships position is recorded every 6 minutes. ASTD only includes signals transmitted by ships that carry an AIS Class A transceiver. This means vessels with Class B transceivers, which provide similar benefits for smaller vessels with lower cost and simpler installation, are not included. Although the quality of AIS data in the ASTD system is considered high, it does not cover 100% of all ship traffic since numerous factors can affect the transmission and receipt of AIS signals. For example, technical failures due to faulty infrastructure, erroneous onboard installation of AIS transceiver, problems with data links and networks, manipulation of AIS signals, data noise as well as satellite coverage limitations must be considered. (ASTD Data Information Document, 2023)

The fuel price data is provided by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA, 2024). It contains average bunker fuel prices in USD\$ per metric ton for various fuel types across 20 major global bunkering locations, including Busan, Colombo, Durban, Fujairah, Gibraltar, Hong Kong, Houston, Istanbul, Los Angeles/Long Beach, Las Palmas, Mumbai, New York, Panama, Piraeus, Rotterdam, Santos, Shanghai, Singapore, St. Petersburg, and Tokyo. The dataset focuses on three key fuel types: IFO 380, a bunker fuel with a maximum sulphur content of 3.5%; VLSFO, a very low sulphur fuel oil with a maximum sulphur content of 0.5%; and Marine Gas Oil (MGO), a clean and bright distillate fuel with a maximum sulphur content of 1.5%. The used price data spans the years 2020 to 2023. The calculated average fuel price is 599.33 euros, adjusted to 2024 prices using an average annual global consumer price index (World Bank, 2024) and the exchange rate USD/EUR (European Central Bank, 2024). The fuel price ranges from 267.58 to 1 046.43 euros. The social avoided costs are quantified using CO₂ costs. The range of variation for EU ETS CO₂ prices for the period 2020–2023 is used as an approximation for the social cost of carbon (SCC) from the Trading Economics (2024) website. On March 16th, 2020, the price of one tonne of carbon dioxide reached its lowest point, at 18.13 euros, adjusted to 2024 prices using the global annual Consumer Price Index (CPI). In contrast, the price peaked at 108.18 euros on March 6th, 2023, also CPI-adjusted. Over this period, the midrange price of CO₂ per tonne was €63.15. During the previous four years, the prices were much lower ranging from around 3 to 30 euros.

The average fuel and CO₂ prices have been adjusted to 2024 prices using the average global Consumer Price Index (CPI) from the World Bank for the period 2014–2023. The global CPI was selected due to the international nature of the shipping industry. On average, prices have increased by 3.136% annually during this period (World Bank, 2024). The analysis utilizes the average exchange rate of 0.9214 for US dollars to Euros, as reported by the European Central Bank (2024) for the period between January and November 2024.

Methods

The evaluation is based on a benefit potential study as defined in Perrels and Juhanko (2023). The approach focuses on analysing how and to what extent an investment or measure (in this context, the implementation of a sea ice service) is affecting one or more economic sectors (here the shipping sector). A benefit study provides building blocks for a complete cost-benefit analysis or cost-effectiveness analysis (Perrels et al., 2013). As a valuation method, the avoided cost framework is used. Avoided costs assessments are based on the idea that in order to value a new weather service, the benefits of the

service are compared to non-use or use of older version of the service (Perrels & Juhanko, 2023). In other words, the avoided or saved cost after implementation of the service is, in fact, the benefit of the service.

According to standard economic theory, value of information is based on its ability to improve decisions making. Value of Information can be defined as shown in Equation 1.

$$I = \text{utility with information} - \text{utility without information} \quad (1)$$

where parameter I refers to the value of information. In shipping, ice information helps route planners to plan their routes better which assumably shortens shipping distance and/or reduces power usage in icy waters. The route shortens as route planners know where the ice is and how risky and challenging it is to access certain areas with the corresponding ice class of the vessel. With this information ships also avoid getting stuck in ice or in case of facing inaccessible ice, avoid having to turn around and find a better route. Less power is needed when route planners can avoid areas in which more power is needed to get through (high resistance of ice) which means that costs can still be avoided, although the distance gets longer. Here the assumption is that the information about ice, makes it possible for route planners to find a shorter or more easily accessible route than without the information. In the valuation technique the savings in operating costs are assumed to equal the benefits i.e. the avoided costs that stem from avoided fuel and CO₂ emission costs the information provides (see illustration in Figure 27). In other words, the benefits equal the value of information as presented in equation 1.

Figure 27. Simplified illustration of vessel's optimized route with sea ice information (blue) compared to the route without sea ice information (red) with detours and additional power usage (zigzag pattern). The vessel sails towards the x-mark. Note: Going through the ice is either impossible or entails an increase in fuel consumption because of increased resistance of ice.

The total avoided fuel costs are calculated using the following equation:

$$AF = [(FP \times FC_1 \times TA) + (FP \times FC_2 \times TA) + \dots + (FP \times FC_n \times TA)] \times ADOP \times ACC \quad (2)$$

Where AF refers to the total avoided fuel costs. The right side of the equation sums up the avoided fuel costs from all vessels (1 to n vessels) that use the service. The factor FP refers to the fuel price whereas FC refers to the fuel consumption in cubic meters. The factor TA refers to the share (%) of the total fuel consumption which can be avoided through sea ice information. The factors $ADOP$ and ACC refer to the adoption of the service i.e. to the share (%) of the vessels that use the service and to the accuracy of the service.

The total avoided CO₂ costs are calculated using the following equation:

$$AC = [(CP \times CC_1 \times TA) + (CP \times CC_2 \times TA) + \dots + (CP \times CC_n \times TA)] \times ADOP \times ACC \quad (3)$$

Where AC refers to the total avoided CO₂ costs. The right side of the equation sums up the avoided CO₂ costs from all vessels (1 to n vessels) that use the service. The factor CP refers to the tCO₂ price whereas CC refers to CO₂ emissions in metric ton. The factor TA refers to the share (%) of the total CO₂ emissions that can be avoided through sea ice information. As above, the factors $ADOP$ and ACC refer to the adoption of the service i.e. to the share (%) of the vessels that use the service and to the accuracy of the service.

The benefits of climate services will vary in magnitude over time. The benefits of new climate services tend to increase over time because of the learning curve or lagged adoption. This is caused by the fact that it takes time for users to build trust for the service and make the best choices corresponding the information from it (Anderson et al., 2015). Also, the specific realized conditions in the observed year affect the value. For example, in a year with challenging ice conditions the value of a sea ice information may be higher than on years with less challenging sea ice conditions. For calculating the present value (PV) for benefits, Equation 4 is used:

$$PV \text{ benefits} = \sum \frac{AF}{(1+r)^t} \quad (4)$$

Where $PV \text{ benefits}$ refer to the total benefits of the service over the observed time frame. On the right side of the equation AF refers to the total avoided fuel costs (or respectively AC for total avoided CO₂ costs) in the specific year t and r is the discount rate. A sensitivity analyses with 1%, 3% and 7% discount rates are conducted.

For calculating the present value for costs, Equation 5 is used:

$$PV \text{ costs} = \sum \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \quad (5)$$

Where $PV \text{ costs}$ represent the total costs of the service over the observed time frame. On the right-hand side of the equation C_t refers to the total costs for the specific year t and r represents the discount rate. The net present value (NPV) is calculated by subtracting the net present costs from the net present benefits. However, due to estimating only partial benefits, the total NPV cannot be estimated in this analysis.

Assumptions and uncertainty

The following base values are set for key variables (see Table 8), with their underlying assumptions detailed next. Table 8 also presents the value ranges used in the sensitivity analyses.

Table 8. Base values for key variables

Key variable	Base value	MC Simulation or basic sensitivity analysis
Fuel price (€/m ³)	€599.33	€267.58 – €1046.43 (Uniform distribution)
CO ₂ price (€/tCO ₂)	€63.15	€18.13 – €108.18 (Uniform distribution)
Service accuracy (%)	90%	85–95% (Uniform distribution)
Service adoption (users of all considered vessels, %)	10%	0.1%, 1%, 10%, 100%

Many studies assume a 100% accuracy of the service meaning that the forecasts are perfect. The accuracy of climate information refers to the degree to which the information reflects the actual climatic conditions. However, the benefits are highly dependent on the conditions that occur compared to those conditions from the perfect forecast scenario. Therefore, no valuation study should claim to determine the value of "perfect information," but it can consider it as a potential upper bound for the value of the information. The accuracy of warnings about sea ice conditions often depends on the skill of those responsible for forecasting these conditions (Anderson et al., 2015). Mironov et al. (2021) study the sea ice forecast accuracy by analysing sea ice processes in autumn 2021 in the Russian Arctic Seas. They show that the overall accuracy of long-term ice forecasts was 75% whereas the accuracy of short-term forecast of ice conditions varied between 85% and 95%. The accuracy of temperature forecasts within a 24-hour timeframe, provided by the FMI, is 90% (FMI, 2024). This evaluation assumes a baseline accuracy of sea ice forecast to be 90% and conducts a sensitivity analysis to assess how changes in accuracy change the estimates of the benefits.

In particular when considering new services, also the rate of adoption of the new service may require assumptions, although typically the rate of adoption is expected to increase over time. In some instances, adoption rates may approach 100% (e.g., households using weather forecasts). However, for many sector-specific services, adoption tends to be lower due to challenges in communicating services or limited opportunities for users to act on improved or new meteorological and hydrological information. Factors that may impact the behaviour of potential users and the rate of adoption of the service include 1) How well the service is communicated to the user; 2) Characteristics of the service (for example, accuracy); 3) Decisionmaker characteristics (for example, risk aversion, or prior knowledge of information); 4) Decisionmaker environment (for example, government programmes and policies that might affect adoption of services); and 5) Availability of resources and management options for changing behaviour in response to information. (Anderson et al., 2015) Conducting a sensitivity analysis helps assessing the impact of these factors. This analysis assumes the base adoption rate to be 10% of the analysed vessels since the representative sea ice service is assumed to be an additional supporting service to the existing ones. However, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to see how avoided costs change if the share of users who benefit from the information is changed.

As mentioned before, the Arctic Service 6 is assumed to function as an add-on service, complementing the existing services. However, this assessment does not attempt to separate the portion of benefits attributable to AS6, as distinguishing these from the benefits generated by other services ships use routinely is not feasible with the available data. To determine a specific share of the overall benefit to this service, one would need insight into the marginal utility it provides relative to other services. In the absence of such data, assumptions must be made. For instance, one could assume that either 100% of the observed benefit is derived from this particular service or assign it a proportional share based on the total number of services used and assuming benefits are distributed evenly across all services. Due to this uncertainty, and to avoid over-reliance on assumptions, the potential benefits are instead expressed in the form: what is the benefit if a 1% reduction in fuel consumption can be achieved through the use of AS6?

In addition, it is challenging to predict how people and businesses will respond to forecasts in any given year. In this analysis, this uncertainty translates to difficulty in estimating the extent to which sea ice information will reduce fuel consumption or emissions by vessels. Some ships may not reduce their fuel consumption at all while other ships may reduce it by several percentage points. Given this uncertainty,

the chosen approach of expressing benefits as avoided costs per 1% reduction in fuel consumption (or corresponding CO₂ emissions) over a given timeframe remains particularly useful.

This evaluation conducts both a basic sensitivity analysis when one variable changes at a time and a Monte Carlo (MC) simulation to examine the range of outcomes when multiple variables vary simultaneously. MC Simulation is particularly effective in scenarios where multiple sources of uncertainty or variability influence the estimates. The approach involves selecting a large set of random initial positions and using numerical simulations to observe how a system evolves (Black et al., 2017).

Study setting

In the analysis all conventional vessels without an ice class inside the PAME's Arctic area proposal during 2023 are considered since they are assumed to primarily benefit from sea ice information. Also, fishing vessels are excluded from the analysis since they are assumed to choose routes without the aim of minimizing route distance. Fishing vessels are assumed to spend time seeking and catching fish rather than simply sail and minimize distance. Research vessels, similarly, may follow specific patterns in an area or stay in one location to take measurements, but this is not considered in this thesis since the dataset does not segregate specifically research vessels.

Firstly, avoided costs are calculated for the whole year and then for the winter season from the beginning of November until the end of April since the Arctic's ice extent begins to increase around October and the ice edge retreats again around May (ASTD, 2024). The aim is to get an overall picture about how much costs can be avoided in the Arctic as a whole. During the winter season, there is a greater extent of ice coverage; however, certain regions become inaccessible. In contrast, during the summer season, some areas may be ice-free, while others remain covered with ice and floating ice threats ships. In addition, climate change increases dynamic and uncertain ice conditions that vary annually which should be taken into account when using data considering data from one random year.

Secondly, the differences in avoided costs between ship types are calculated. The benefits are calculated for winter months (January, February and March) which is the time of year with the greatest ice extent. Thirdly, differences in avoided costs are studied by observing how the benefit varies between Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). The EEZs differ among other things in size, ice conditions and shipping activity. In the EEZ-level analysis the 3-months period from January to March is used. The goal is to assess to which extent different ship types and regions could benefit from ice information during the winter months.

In total 7 287 vessels without an ice class sail in the Arctic during the representative year (2023) when fishing vessels are excluded. These vessels' fuel costs sum up to around 3.1 billion euros per year and the CO₂ costs sum up to around 252 million euros per year. The total fuel costs of the 5 214 vessels sailing in the Arctic during the 6-month period (January, February, March, April, November and/or December) in 2023 are approximately 1.3 billion euros whereas the total CO₂ costs are approximately 430 million euros.

Results: Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs

Every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption saves 2.8 million euros in fuel costs per year. The corresponding savings in CO₂ costs are 940 000 euros per year. Over the six-month period (November to April), each additional 1% reduction in total fuel consumption results in savings of 1.2 million euros in fuel costs and 390 000 euros in CO₂ costs per winter season.

The ship type-level analysis, conducted for the winter months (January, February, and March) shows that bulk carriers achieve the greatest savings, with every 1% reduction in fuel consumption translating to 105 000 euros in fuel cost savings and 35 000 euros in CO₂ cost savings (see Table 9). The EEZ-level analysis conducted for the winter months (January, February, and March), indicates greatest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs within the Alaskan and Norwegian EEZ (see Table 10).

Table 9. Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs by ship type, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption during winter months (January–February–March).

Ship type	Avoided fuel cost, €	Avoided CO ₂ cost, €	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (MGO/MDO)	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (residuals)	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (LNG /battery power)
Bulk carriers	105 098	35 221	13	543	1
Chemical tankers	26 360	8 818	15	109	16
Container ships	97 909	32 837	14	503	2
Crude oil tankers	39 741	13 346	42	156	13
Gas tankers	99 813	33 570	0	531	0
General cargo ships	53 333	17 680	4	268	7
Oil product tankers	5 517	1 749	4	24	0
Refrigerated cargo ships	7 196	2 353	1	36	0
Roro cargo ships	31 074	10 439	2	96	67
Cruise ships	12 517	4 201	7	51	8
Offshore supply ships	14 838	4 983	70	2	7
Other activities	84 694	28 096	349	88	8
Other service offshore ships	8 311	2 594	20	21	0
Passenger ships	70 891	23 769	85	199	93
In total	657 292	219 656	626	2 627	222

Table 10. Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs by EEZ, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption during winter months (January–February–March).

Area	Avoided fuel cost, €	Avoided CO ₂ cost, €	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂
Alaskan EEZ	120 384	40 282	638
Canadian EEZ	75 783	25 258	400
Faeroe islands EEZ	6 354	2 133	34
Finnish EEZ	8 991	2 968	47
Greenlandic EEZ	648	215	3
Icelandic EEZ	4 076	1 362	22
Jan Mayen EEZ	0	0	0
Norwegian EEZ	115 211	38 394	608
Open Waters Arctic	14	5	0

Open waters Barents Sea	1 424	480	8
Open waters Bering Sea EEZ	345	116	2
Open waters Davis Strait	0	0	0
Open waters North Atlantic	0	0	0
Open waters Norwegian Sea EEZ	230	77	1
Russian EEZ	111 890	37 504	594
Svalbard Fisheries Zone	2 065	693	11
Swedish EEZ	1 372	455	7
United Kingdom EEZ	26	9	0
United States EEZ	41 113	13 740	240
In total	489 926	163 691	2 615

Based on the proximity to the major shipping routes (Northern Sea Route (NSR) and the Northwest Passage (NWP)) as well as on the levels of shipping activity, measured by the number of individual vessels sailing these regions, the avoided costs are calculated for four ship types in four areas. The results indicate that largest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs can be reached in the Alaskan EEZ by container ships (see Tables 11 and 12).

Table 11. Avoided fuel costs in major EEZs by ship type, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption during winter months (January–February–March).

	Bulk carriers	Container ships	General cargo ships	RoRo ships	Chemical tankers
Alaskan EEZ	42 500	43 221	3 744	8 275	2 667
Canadian EEZ	23 852	19 300	2 438	6 498	1 703
Norwegian EEZ	10 800	896	4 541	342	2013
Russian EEZ	10 083	7 584	6 548	648	859

Table 12. Avoided CO₂ costs in major EEZs by ship type, €/1% avoided in total CO₂ emissions during winter months (January–February–March).

	Bulk carriers	Container ships	General cargo ships	RoRo ships	Chemical tankers
Alaskan EEZ	14 241	14 524	1 250	2 786	897
Canadian EEZ	7 975	6 454	813	2 182	572
Norwegian EEZ	3 633	299	1 511	114	673
Russian EEZ	3 374	2 549	2 185	218	288

Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to address uncertainty in service adoption, using adoption rates of 0.1%, 1%, 10%, and 100%. These rates represent the proportion of potential users benefiting from sea ice information. Other variables are kept fixed. The analysis was performed for both 12-month and 6-month time frames (see Table 13).

Table 13. Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption in the 12-month period (January to December) and in the 6-month period (January, February, March, April, November and/or December).

	0.1% users	1% users	10% users	100% users
Avoided fuel costs (12-month)	28 104	281 040	2 810 403	28 104 034
Avoided CO₂ costs (12-month)	9 401	94 014	940 136	9 401 356
Avoided fuel costs (6-month)	11 566	115 659	1 156 592	11 565 922
Avoided CO₂ costs (6-month)	3 867	38 673	386 735	3 867 349

Monte Carlo Simulations

A Monte Carlo (MC) simulation was performed to evaluate the sensitivity associated with price variability and information accuracy. Service adoption is excluded from the Monte Carlo Analysis because it is assumed to have a dominant influence on the distribution and consequently, it is analysed separately through the basic sensitivity analysis (previous section). The MC simulation comprised 1 000 iterations, during which key variables were varied within the ranges specified above in the Assumptions and uncertainty -section (Table 8). The weights of the ranges were distributed according to a uniform distribution. Table 14 shows the Monte Carlo summary statistics.

Table 14. Monte Carlo summary statistics (1 000 iterations). Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption.

	Avoided fuel costs, 12-month period, €	Avoided fuel costs, 6-month period, €	Avoided CO ₂ costs, 12-month period, €	Avoided CO ₂ costs, 6-month period, €
Mean	3 120 874	1 255 849	932 878	391 138
Minimum	1 200 489	492 117	257 919	111 270
Maximum	5 113 764	2 085 590	1 673 115	692 821
Standard deviation	1 070 761	443 417	392 349	165 129

Figures 28a and 28b show the distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles derived from the Monte Carlo analysis of avoided fuel and CO₂ costs over the 12-month period. Similarly, Figures 29a and 29b illustrate the corresponding distributions for the 6-month period.

Figure 28: Distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles derived from the Monte Carlo simulation of avoided fuel (28a) and CO₂ (28b) costs for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in the 12-month period.

Figure 29: Distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles derived from the Monte Carlo simulation of avoided fuel (29a) and CO₂ (29b) costs for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in the 6-month period.

Figure 30a presents the Monte Carlo distribution of avoided fuel costs per ship type during the 3-month winter period from January to March, while Figure 30b shows the corresponding avoided CO₂ costs, both influenced by variations in fuel and CO₂ prices as well as service accuracy.

Figure 30: Avoided fuel costs (30a) and avoided CO₂ costs (30b) for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in January, February and March (2023). The solid boxes represent the interquartile range (middle 50% of the data) for each set of observation, with the median value shown as a horizontal line inside the box and the mean value as a cross (x). Whiskers show the upper and lower quartile of observations.

Figure 31 presents the Monte Carlo distribution of avoided fuel and CO₂ costs across major EEZs during the 3-month winter period from January to March, influenced by variations in fuel and CO₂ prices as well as service accuracy.

Figure 31: Avoided fuel costs (31a) and CO₂ costs (31b) for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in January, February and March (2023). The solid boxes represent the interquartile range (middle 50% of the data) for each set of observations, with the median value shown as a horizontal line inside the box and the mean value as a cross (x). Whiskers show the upper and lower quartile of observations.

Scenario based present value calculations

To evaluate the future benefits of sea ice information, the present value (PV) of benefits is calculated for the period 2024–2100 under three scenarios, reflecting different assumptions about future trends.

- Scenario 1: In the first scenario, it is assumed that benefits will grow by 0.72% annually, consistent with the observed 0.72% annual increase in the number of ships in the study area between 2014 and 2023.
- Scenario 2: The second scenario assumes that benefits remain constant throughout the period.
- Scenario 3: The third scenario considers the potential impact of diminishing sea ice, as the Arctic Ocean is projected to experience ice-free summers as early as 2040 or 2050, while the annual freezing and melting cycle persists (AMSA Report, 2009). This scenario assumes that benefits will gradually decrease each year, halving by 2100 compared to 2024 (arbitrarily assigned), to account for the reduced need for sea ice navigation services in an increasingly ice-free Arctic.

The development of benefits (avoided costs) is presented in Figure 32 over time from 2024 to 2100 (not discounted). As initial benefit, the avoided cost from the entire Arctic in the 12-month period is used. It should be noted that the 76-year timeframe may not reflect the lifespan of a specific sea ice service.

Figure 32: 32a) Avoided fuel cost and 32b) Avoided CO₂ cost for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption when sea ice information value changes between 2024–2100. (Not discounted) In scenario 1, the benefits increase, in scenario 2, the benefits remain constant and in scenario 3, the benefits decrease over time, as described above.

Tables 15 and 16 present the present value (PV) of benefits from 2024 to 2100 across various scenarios, while also evaluating the sensitivity of these values to changes in the annual discount rate.

Table 15. Present value of the benefits through avoided fuel costs per 1% avoided fuel consumption

Discount rate	PV for scenario 1, €	PV for scenario 2, €	PV for scenario 3, €
3%	101 270 650	84 059 981	68 257 094
1%	193 174 356	150 416 371	113 382 540
7%	44 326 863	39 929 279	35 443 039

Table 16. Present value of the benefits through avoided CO₂ costs per 1% avoided CO₂ emissions

Discount rate	PV for scenario 1, €	PV for scenario 2, €	PV for scenario 3, €
3%	33 877 036	28 119 727	22 833 349
1%	64 620 644	50 317 252	37 928 703
7%	14 828 213	13 357 134	11 856 398

Costs of the service

The cost of Arctic service 6 includes personnel costs as well as costs of equipment and infrastructure. Some of the costs occur only in the development stage. Expenses related to the labour involved in development, sum up to 50 000 euros per year. In the maintenance stage, costs of labour, costs related to data processing and service provision as well as costs for durable goods, equipment and infrastructure sum up to 36 500 euros per year. When including development costs, the production of the service costs annually 86 500 euros. The mature service costs are annually 36 500 euros (see Table 17).

Table 17. Annual cost of the service

Development costs per year	Maintenance costs per year
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Labor costs related to development, obtaining observations, data processing and service provision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Labor costs related to obtaining observations, data processing and service provision Costs of durable goods, equipment and infrastructure associated with data processing and service provision
In total 50 000€	In total 36 500€

Costs and partial benefits

Assuming that the development costs are included in the first five years from 2024 to 2028, followed by only maintenance costs until 2100, the present value of costs at a 3% discount rate is approximately 1.3 million euros. With an adoption rate of 10% the present value of benefits, which is counted in tens of millions, significantly exceeds the present value of costs, even when accounting only for partial benefits

gained through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs (see Table 18). The present value of benefits, shown in Table 18, represent a range of the benefits generated through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs for each 1% reduction in total fuel consumption. All scenarios presented above (see Scenario based present value calculations - section) are included into the range of benefits and 10% and 0.1% adoption rates are applied.

Table 18. Comparing the present value of costs and partial present value of benefits gained through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs in the time frame 2024–2100. All scenarios presented earlier are included into the range of benefits and 10% and 0.1% adoption rates are applied.

Discount rate	PV of costs, €	PV of benefits (10% adoption rate), €	PV of benefits (0.1% adoption rate), €
3%	1 320 711	53 286 413 – 200 733 623	532 864 – 2 007 336
1%	2 196 198	59 155 075 – 257 795 000	591 550 – 2 577 950
7%	723 590	47 299 437 – 151 311 243	472 994 – 1 513 112

Discussion: Avoided costs

The main results of this analysis indicate that every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption by vessels in the Arctic saves annually 2.8 million euros in fuel costs and 940 000 euros in CO₂ costs. In the analysis covering the 6-month period (November to April), each additional 1% reduction in total fuel consumption results in savings of 1.2 million euros in fuel costs and 390 000 euros in CO₂ costs per winter. Both results indicate significant benefits compared to the costs of the service which are 86 500 euros annually when development costs are included and 36 500 when the service is mature. However, it is important to note that the satellite infrastructure is assumed to be pre-existing, and its associated costs are not included which might transfer to underestimated service costs. In addition, the development costs cover only those expenses incurred during the project, and any costs related to the work of developing the methodological aspects prior to the project are not included. It should also be noted that an adoption rate of 10% is assumed for the service in these numbers. When using the 12-month period results and the adoption rate of 0.1% the avoided fuel costs sum up to 28 00 euros annually and the avoided CO₂ costs to 9 400 euros annually per 1% of avoided fuel consumption. Using these numbers, it would require nearly a 2.5% reduction in fuel consumption to reach a point where the avoided CO₂ costs and avoided fuel costs cover annual costs of the service (with development costs). However, avoided fuel and CO₂ costs are not the only sources of benefits, which indicates that the total benefits actually exceed the costs with less effort.

When analysing the avoided costs by ship type during the 3-month winter period (January, February, and March), the results show that bulk carriers achieve the greatest savings, with every 1% reduction in fuel consumption translating to 105 000 euros in fuel cost savings and 35 000 euros in CO₂ cost savings. Bulk carriers cover the highest share of ships sailing in the Arctic and non-ice class bulk carriers emit the most CO₂ during the winter period. Further, the results show greatest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs within the Alaskan and Norwegian EEZ during the 3-month winter period. In the Alaskan EEZ, every 1% reduction in fuel consumption translates to 120 000 euros in fuel cost savings and 40 000 euros in CO₂ cost savings. There is no traffic and consequently no avoided costs within the Open waters North Atlantic, Open waters Davis Strait and Jan Mayen EEZ during the 3-month winter period (note that only vessels without an ice class are considered). In addition, within the EEZs largest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs can be reached in the Alaskan EEZ by container ships which generate avoided fuel costs of 43 000 euros and avoided CO₂

costs of 14 000 euros for every additional 1% avoided in fuel consumption. It should be noted that the results from the analysis considering the EEZs present avoided costs only at EEZ-level and whether ships sail through multiple EEZs is not considered. Put differently, if a ship sails through multiple EEZ, the 1% reduction in fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions are considered to take place in all these EEZ separately. Another matter to point out is that all EEZs are not fully covered, since just the area that fits within the borders of PAME Arctic Area Proposal is considered. For example, a large part of the United Kingdom EEZ locates outside this area.

Andersson and Ivehammar (2015) showed that each 1% reduced in sailed distance could result in potential savings of 37 million euros annually in Northern Europe. In a later study Anderson and Ivehammar (2017) indicated that each 1% reduced in sailed distance could result in potential savings of 102.4 million euros in the Baltic region. Their results show significantly greater benefits compared to those observed in this analysis. However, it is important to note that Andersson and Ivehammar employed a higher price for emissions and incorporated additional cost categories into their analysis. Furthermore, their study focused on different geographical area that vary among other things in shipping activity levels and ice conditions.

Results robustness

As shown by the results, the implementation of a sea ice service can be highly beneficial across the Arctic. However, the valuation is challenging because the value-creation process is both dynamic and interactive causing uncertainties (Anderson et al., 2015). Environmental cost and benefit functions tend to be highly nonlinear, unlike in this study. Usually, the damage caused by GHG emissions does not increase linearly with the level of emissions but rather increase quickly after some threshold is reached (Pindyck, 2007). In this study it was assumed that every additional tCO₂ was at the same cost.

Also, the number of users benefiting from sea ice information remains highly uncertain. It can be assumed that all vessels operating in the Arctic rely on sea ice information to some extent, suggesting that the benefits could be calculated based on an adoption rate of around 100%. However, when focusing on the benefits provided by an individual ice information provider such as the POLARIS, the adoption rate decreases due to the high and growing number of service providers and already existing knowledge and sea ice services. In the sensitivity analysis the avoided costs are calculated assuming adoption rates of 0.1%, 1%, 10% and 100%. For example, in the 12-month period fuel costs can be avoided by 28 000 euros annually if assuming an adoption rate of 0.1%. However, when assuming a 100% adoption rate the, the avoided fuel costs sum up to 28 million euros annually.

The EU ETS carbon price was used as an approximation for the social cost of carbon (SCC). The EU ETS carbon price serves as a lower-bound estimate since it fails to account for the full SCC i.e. the economic cost caused by an additional ton of carbon dioxide emissions (Nordhaus, 2017), which is generally much higher. This pricing approach may underestimate the true cost of carbon emission, leading to an underestimation of the benefits calculated in this analysis. It should also be noted that the CO₂ price significantly depends on the chosen time frame.

The fuel price data was based on fuel prices in 20 major ports in the world. Applying non-Arctic data risks misrepresenting the realities of fuel usage in this area. However, using fuel prices from around the world is assumed suitable because of the international nature of the shipping industry. Furthermore, the analysis relies on the average prices of three fuel types without weighting them according to their actual

distribution or considering specialized fuels required for arctic low-temperature conditions. Fuels that are for low temperatures, might come at a higher price (Lasserre, 2015). It should be also noted that the fuel price data is drawn from the period encompassing the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing war in Ukraine, both of which have caused unprecedented volatility in global energy markets and influenced fuel prices in ways that do not accurately reflect long-term trends or the typical economic conditions (Martínez-García et al., 2023; Sakib et al., 2023).

Assessing the accuracy of sea ice information is challenging as it depends on the benchmark for "perfect" information and the extent to which biases in ice data are acceptable. In addition, ice information is dependent on other climate data which affects the accuracy of ice information (Wei et al., 2023). In this analysis, the accuracy was based on a study by Mironov et al. (2021), conducted in the Russian Arctic under autumn conditions, which is not comprehensive.

Fuel and CO₂ prices, as well as the service accuracy are included in the Monte Carlo analysis which shows the distribution of avoided costs generated by every additional 1% avoided in fuel consumption as these key variables change. The avoided fuel costs in the 12-month period vary between 1.2 million euros and 5.1 million euros whereas avoided CO₂ costs between 260 000 and 1.7 million euros. In the 6-month period avoided fuel costs vary between 490 000 and 2.1 million euros whereas avoided CO₂ costs between 110 000 and 690 000 euros. These results show that prices along with service accuracy have a great impact on the benefits. Figures 28 and 29, which present the distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles, show that the number of occurrences varies between approximately 40 and 120 across the percentiles when considering avoided fuel and CO₂ costs for both the 6-month and 12-month periods.

A further uncertainty of this analysis considers the magnitude of fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions that can actually be avoided. This thesis presents avoided costs as a linear benefit function, quantifying the benefits generated by each additional 1% reduction in fuel consumption to address this challenge. However, the level of avoidance varies between voyages. Du et al. (2022) show that an oil tanker achieves 1.39% reduction in fuel consumption and 1.59% increase in economic benefit per voyage through dynamic route planning algorithm in ice free waters. Forsman and Andersson (2015) show that in one month in the Sea of Kattegat, it is possible to reduce fuel consumption with 10.9% by optimising routes using STM (Sea Traffic Management). Mussells et al. (2017) provide an example from the Hudson Strait in the Canadian archipelago where vessels become beset for hours to days at a time. The average distance the MV Arctic (the studied vessel) travelled in the Hudson Strait, during the studied time period, was 625 km. However, the distance might increase if the vessel turns around because of ice or risk of besetment and looks for a better route. According to Mussells et al. during the study period the ship was beset 9–66% of the full transit time and the distance ranged from 561 km to 872 km. The difference between the maximum and minimum distance is hereby 311 km indicating that the actual saving in distance and fuel consumption can vary significantly between transits. These examples show that there is potential for shorter routes as well as fuel and emission savings at varying levels in both ice-free and icy waters.

Other uncertainties to be considered, are related to predetermined routes, ice breaker assistance and lack of ice in some parts of the study area. According to a personal communication with a sea ice expert from the Finnish Meteorological institute (personal communication, October 15, 2024), the potential benefits that can be gained through route optimizing, are narrow in Finland's seas because ships in Finland tend to use predetermined routes and are always assisted by ice breakers when there is ice which makes sea ice information less relevant for optimizing routes. As outlined by the expert, the need for ice breaker

assistance is not likely to decrease through milder winters as ice conditions are becoming more unpredictable and dynamic.

According to another personal communication with a marine researcher from the Finnish Meteorological Institute (personal communication, November 5, 2024) the most southern sea areas across the PAME Arctic Area Proposal, including the Norwegian, Greenlandic and Baltic seas, will not benefit from route optimizing (based on sea ice information) because of lack of ice and because potential route optimizing benefits are narrow. These two statements about the southern regions, specifically, 1) the lack of sea ice in the southern part of the study area (PAME Arctic Area Proposal) and 2) the limited opportunities for route optimization by using sea ice information, indicate that the results of this analysis for the entire area, including the southern regions, particularly over the 12-month period, might represent an overestimation of the potential avoided costs.

Additionally, this analysis excluded ice-class vessels and fishing vessels. Ice-class vessels cover about 25% and fishing vessels about 15% of all vessels in the study area in 2023 (the shares overlap). Sawyer and Dupost (2015) show that the use of satellite imagery in winter navigation results in nearly 1 million euros in annual fuel cost savings for icebreakers in Finland and Sweden, indicating the benefits of ice information for ice breakers. However, ice breakers and ice-class vessels are omitted from the analysis because risk-related information is particularly valuable for less capable vessels with lower polar classifications, as indicated in Arctic PASSION (2024b). However, when applying these results to the POLARIS framework, it is important to note that the service provides risk information for various ice classes. As a result, focusing solely on vessels without an ice class may lead to an underestimation of the benefits.

Future implications

It is uncertain how the benefits of sea ice information are going to develop in the future. In the scenario analysis three different cases were studied. As shown above in Table 18, all considered scenarios demonstrated higher benefits than costs with a 10% adoption rate, when the discount rate ranged from 1% to 7%. However, several other factors that were not considered in the scenario analysis and some of which may interact simultaneously, are likely to influence the future avoided costs and should be considered in future research.

For shipping between the northern and southern part of the globe the Arctic routes may serve shorter transit times, lower fuel and overall costs, improve network connectivity and lower carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gas emissions (Theocharis et al., 2018). The decision between Arctic routes and southern alternatives influences the Arctic shipping activity and further the economic benefits generated through sea ice information. However, multiple studies (for example Wang et al., 2021) suggest that using Arctic routes are, in fact, not as economically profitable as thought. In addition, some major corporations have decided not to ship via the Arctic at all because of environmental concern (Ocean Conservancy, 2024) potentially decreasing the interest on Arctic shipping further (Akbayirli & Tuna, 2022). The results in the literature indicate that, although Arctic routes can be more cost-effective and energy efficient when comparing to traditional routes, especially in the long term, they can mainly be used as seasonal alternatives for bulk and specialized shipping in the short term (Theocharis et al., 2018).

Literature review of other potential benefits in shipping

The benefits of sea ice information are concretized specifically through shipping, as this sector is assumably the primary user of such information in the Arctic region and, therefore, the most relevant beneficiary of such information. This analysis estimated potential partial benefits through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs. However, to determine the total economic value of a climate service, all benefits must be identified, including financial, environmental, and social gains, regardless of who receives them or where they occur (Anderson et al., 2015). This sub-chapter provides an overview of cost categories related to shipping that might impact the benefit of sea ice information. According to an unpublished questionnaire about the use of sea ice information services the benefits of nowcasting and forecasting sea ice observation data comes from improvements in both safety and optimal routing (see Appendix 3).

The economic expenditures of shipping can be divided into private and external costs which together comprise the societal costs. Private costs include expenditures such as fuel, capital and maintenance costs that fall to individual shipping operators. External costs are non-internalized costs to society that are not accounted for in the market (Fahlen & Ahlgren, 2010). Shipping externalities refer to the negative impacts or unintended consequences of shipping activities that affect society, the environment, or specific communities. The external and private costs of shipping are listed in Table 19.

Table 19. Private and external costs of (Arctic) shipping.

Private costs of shipping	Externalities of shipping	Examples of external costs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel • Capital and maintenance • Crew salaries • Insurance • Route fees • Ice breaker assistance tariff • Ice pilot fee • Harbour stays • Rescue costs and other costs related to accidents • Lost revenue caused by accidents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GHG emissions • Air pollution • Underwater noise • Spread of invasive species • Antifouling paint and biofouling on ship hull • Solid waste, ballast water, bilge water, black water, grey water, scrubber wash water, stern tube oil, tank cleaning • Accidents (oil spills, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health damage and premature deaths (continuous exposure to externalities such as air pollution) • Biodiversity loss/extinction of species and disruption of local ecosystems • Impacts on local communities and culture • Deaths and environmental damage (accidents)

Private costs + external costs = Total societal costs of shipping

Private costs of shipping include fuel costs, capital costs, crew costs and operational costs like repairs, maintenance, insurance and administrative costs. Other costs that are not related to ships operating in open waters include port costs like taxes, fees, discharge operation or demurrage (Grifoll et al., 2018; Toscano et al., 2021) and costs related to accidents like fuel spills (Afenyo et al., 2019). Chen et al. (2023) point out that the economic cost of Arctic navigation is relatively higher than in conventional waters, since cost of ice-class vessels is around 0.5 to 1 time higher and Arctic navigation requiring more special equipment, technical support and ice area insurance. On the other hand, Sarrabezoles et al. (2016) argue that, regarding insurance costs, no dramatic price increases for Arctic shipping have been observed. They suggest that this is due to the experience of most Arctic operators, which indicates that they have gained

credibility in the eyes of insurance firms. Consequently, this might not be the case for new shipping operators. Other additional costs in the Arctic include ice braker assistance tariffs (Li et al., 2023a), transit tariffs for sailing along routes such as the NSR (Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015) and ice pilot fees in case the route planner does not have the minimum level of knowledge in navigating in ice-covered waters (Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015). A further aspect to consider is the cost of time. Time has an economic value because it can be used for alternative purposes (Becker, 1965). From the perspective of sea ice freight, the value of time saved during transit is especially significant for high-value or time-sensitive cargo (Wang et al., 2016). Andersson and Ivehammar (2017) estimate a total cost (including labour cost, fuel cost, emission cost and capital cost) of €29.2 million per day for shipping in the area between south of Frederikshavn in Denmark and Gotenburg in Sweden including the area up to the northernmost part of the bay of Bothania.

Beyond private costs, shipping involves externalities that are not directly covered by the shipping operator themselves. Increasing shipping activity in the Arctic increases environmental challenges associated with ship operations including their impacts on climate change, air quality, and marine biodiversity. Like other transportation modes, ships emit CO₂ and water vapor, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and particulate matter such as black carbon which reduce air quality and worsen climate change (AMSA Report, 2009). The majority of GHG emissions from shipping consist of CO₂ which has also the greatest global warming potential (Nunes et al., 2017). Also, black carbon has a significant influence on the retreating of the sea ice including its effects on snow and ice albedo which makes it a particular concern in the Arctic (AMSA Report, 2009). Sulphur dioxide, on the other hand, is observed to cause cooling, warming, acid rain and drought dependent on changing concentrations of its levels: too much SO₂ causes global warming and mass extinctions while too little causes cooling and drought. Currently human activities release an amount of SO₂ into the atmosphere that contributes to global warming and widespread extinction of many species (Ward, 2009).

The marine environment is further impacted by the waste streams related to propulsion and engine operations including bilge water from the machinery spaces, stern tube oil from the lubrication of the propeller shaft, scrubber wash water from exhaust gas cleaning systems for the reduction of emissions of sulphur oxides into the atmosphere, ballast water from maintaining ship stability, biocides used in antifouling paints to prevent hull growth, cooling water as well as tank cleaning residuals (Jalkanen et al., 2021). Waste streams stemming from humans on board consist of food waste, black water (sewage), and water from galleys and showers (grey water) as well as other solid waste (Jalkanen et al., 2021). Additionally, ships introduce alien species to new areas (Afenyo et al., 2019; Dobrzycka-Krahe & Medina-Villar, 2023) and generate noise (Jalkanen et al., 2022) primarily caused by propeller cavitation (Jalkanen, 2018) disrupting local ecosystems. For example, Taylor (2021) argues that the population of the orca has been negatively affected by the underwater noise stemming from commercial vessel traffic, tied to international trade. In the Arctic context key arctic species, such as walrus and narwhal have been identified to be particularly sensitive to ship noise (Huntington, 2023). Jalkanen (2022) reports a significant increase in shipping noise emissions in the Arctic between 2014 and 2020. However, the increase is notable in the Arctic because shipping noise emissions in this pristine region have historically been relatively low (Jalkanen, 2022).

In addition to noise, Inuit have reported that whales such as beluga follow tracks by icebreakers which increases the risk of ice-entrapment mortality events if the open water freezes behind them (Huntington, 2023). In addition, Huntington (2023) underlines that in Arctic areas ice conditions may cause vessels to diverge from established shipping routes to avoid hazards which might, besides possible detours and increased fuel consumption, lead to environmental disturbances in additional areas. Besides environmental externalities, other externalities of shipping include for instance negative health impacts (Nunes et al., 2021), premature deaths (AMSA Report, 2009) and impacts on Indigenous and non-Indigenous people in the Arctic (Lavengood, 2021; Olsen et al., 2019). Studies show that marine traffic has multiple social and cultural impacts on local people in the Arctic (AMSA, 2009). For Indigenous people the marine environment is a source of livelihood: traditional fishing and hunting activities as well as recreation activities are disturbed by the marine traffic (Olsen et al. 2019; Huntington et al., 2023).

According to Grifoll et al. (2018) who analysed a typical Short Sea Shipping (SSS) vessel, capital costs account for over 50% of the total shipping costs, while fuel costs represent approximately 25%. However, their analysis included only capital costs, fuels costs, crew costs and costs regarding repairs, maintenance, insurance, and administrative costs meaning that for example port costs, possible accident costs and externalities were excluded. Leviäkangas and Hautala (2009) showed that the services provided by the FMI (Finnish Meteorological Institute) can save annually 14–28 million euros in accident costs related to waterways and marine transportation in Finland. These results indicate that the benefits calculated in this analysis cover only a fraction of the potential benefits of sea ice information.

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3.7. Arctic service 7: CBM for Arctic marine climate change, noise pollution & impacts on marine living resources

The Arctic Service 7 provides information on Arctic marine climate change, noise pollution and impacts on marine living resources collected via community-based monitoring (CBM). The objective of the service is to support food security, sustainability, as well as building local capacity and decision-making in Greenlandic coastal communities. The monitoring of the marine climate and noisescape in coastal areas, is conducted in collaboration with the communities of Qaanaaq, Savissivik, Siorapaluk and Qerqertat in Northwest Greenland.

Besides supporting local and scientific data needs, the service encompasses inclusive decision-making and enhances local capacity. The service ensures critical integration of Indigenous Knowledge and engages communities in co-creation, linking to Arctic Service 1. Sound recording and oceanographic sensors are integrated onto the infrastructure local people use for traditional fishing and hunting activities, as well as for means of transport, i.e., sleds and small boats. Together with the local communities a visual integrated Atlas will be created. The Atlas will consist of annual sound recordings and of marine activities as a tool to empower the communities to manage their environment and advance dialogue on sustainable pathways for marine activities. Besides the Visual Atlas, the service is provided in the form of collaborative and inclusive project development, local meetings and workshops as well as training sessions and knowledge sharing. The service is currently in pilot phase and is under development.

3.7.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 33. Value chain for Arctic service 7.

Data and Production of the Service

The service is a collaborative project with the communities in the Qaanaaq area. Year-round data is collected on physical parameters and passive acoustic recordings. The data is collected in an array of locations through the fjord, selected by the local hunters. The data provides observations on seasonal and

yearly variations in ambient noise, the presence of hunting animals and changes in the habitat with climate change. Also, information on the effect of traffic in the hunting area from the increasing activities of cruise ships, military, extraction and science ships will be provided. The service gathers questions from the local community and discusses how to use scientific activities to answer the local questions and needs.

The production of AS7 involves a six-stage process. Firstly, deployment plans are formulated during local meetings, followed by the programming and deployment (1). Then field trips are organised to deploy the instruments (2). Once the instruments have been deployed, they are later recovered in the field (3). Following recovery, all collected data is downloaded and securely stored on servers (4). This data is then analysed and prepared for end users (5) after which the data is uploaded to the Visual Atlas (6). Finally, local communities and other users are informed about the new data upload. Scientists are involved in all six stages while local community members are involved in stage 1, local hunters in stage 2 and logisticians in the first four stages.

The planning is carried out by scientists, Greenlandic logisticians and hunters. The sea ice work needs local specialised knowledge, and technical scientific knowledge is needed for the programming, deployment and recovery. Specialised computer skills and computer programs are needed for the analysis of the data and preparation for the Visual Atlas. Locals are currently being trained in deployment and recovery of the instruments, and the next step is training in programming and downloading of the instruments. The information is extracted in two ways: through data recorded in the fjord and through local meetings in which local knowledge is gathered. Both information sources are output from the service and used by users. The information cannot be stratified or segmented in terms of quality level.

Information and Dissemination of the service

The service consists of collaborative and inclusive project development, local meetings and workshops, training sessions, knowledge sharing and a Visual Atlas to visualise the data collected. The Visual Atlas is under development, as it is developed in collaboration with the community, to meet their communication needs and wishes. These service products will provide users with information about seasonal and yearly variations in ambient noise, the presence of hunting animals and changes in the habitat with climate change. Also, information on the effect of traffic in the hunting area from the increasing activities of cruise ships, military, extraction and science ships will be provided.

The Visual Atlas will be the main channel for data dissemination, and it will not involve third parties that could influence the reception or have own access requirements. Scientists will analyse the data before it ends up in the visual Atlas. No special skills are needed to use the service use because the local users are part of developing the format the data is presented in, and no factors have been identified to impact the eventual usefulness of the information. Users are not expected to add information from other sources. The value chain of the regular service will look similar to the one in the pilot phase. The service is open to everyone in the pilot phase and there is no regulatory factors or barriers affecting the use of the service.

Users and Uses of the Service

The service's main target group is local grown-ups of any age and gender living in the local communities. For the governmental end users, no specific demography is targeted. Other target groups include the Arctic Council, the EU and international scientists of any age and gender. Currently, in the pilot phase, the service is used by the local community, the Greenland Government management and lawmakers. Future

potential user groups include international scientists, the Arctic HUB and Arctic Council working groups. A broader use in the local community is expected once the Visual Atlas is distributed.

To some extent, user groups can be segmented based on demographics. When it comes to governmental users, it is difficult to segment the users based on demographics while for the users in the local community it is not. Many hunter families work closely together and if the hunter in the family uses the service, it is often used by the spouse as well. More information on the gender aspects in the Arctic PASSION project can be found in Deliverable 8.4 (will be published in M50). In the future, the goal is to track the users of the Visual Atlas to understand how and how often it is used. For local communities, number of attendees of the meetings and collaborators in the project could serve as an indicator to measure the use of the service by the local community. It is possible to measure a minimum estimate of how and how often the service is used by others than the local community. The aim is that in the future the users of the Visual Atlas can be tracked. However, this also depends on the direction the local community directs the Visual Atlas towards.

The users of the service are diverse and will have different uses for the service. The local users will use the data directly to track changes in their local environment and potentially use it to support adapting to the changes. Governmental users will usually consult the service developers, i.e. the leading scientists, directly. Governmental users have invited scientists and local hunters connected to the service to attend workshops, meetings and conferences to share experiences and discuss the output of the local meetings and the data recorded.

It is possible to quantify or at least give a minimum estimate of the actions taken or not taken by the governmental users. For the local users, that is an intricate task since it is difficult to track the choices of each individual. However, local users could be asked to tell if they took any actions or chose not to take them based on the service output.

Additionally, as users use the data in very different ways, it is difficult to compare and quantify how different demographic users utilise the service. However, this can be quantified by contacting different organisations, ministries or working groups. On the other hand, for the local users, tracking the demographics will depend on the Visual Atlas and the form it takes. However, in local workshops and meetings the demographics can be identified for those participating in them. Many of the international or government users have contacted the service developers, which makes it possible to track who uses the service.

The local community will use the data to understand the changes in the location of their hunting animals and sea ice, as well as to understand the effects of traffic noise on the narwhal hunt and on the animals' well-being. The Greenland government can use the information to advise new lawmaking and management in the area. Management of nature and hunting can use the service to gain knowledge about the activities in the area, local needs and hunting animals. In the future, international scientists and working groups under the Arctic Council are expected to use the service.

Further economic evaluation of the Arctic Service 7 is not conducted due to the lack of quantitative data about the impacts (note that the service is not mature yet) and costs of the service. The societal benefits of AS7 are assessed qualitatively based on literature and VCA results. VCA results are based on the communication with service developers.

3.7.2. Societal benefits

Climate change is particularly affecting the Arctic, threatening the food security and sovereignty of those most dependent on intact sea ice ecosystems. The combined effects of climate change are expected to be negative to both Arctic marine mammals and the Indigenous people who hunt them (Hovelsrud et al., 2008; Berner et al., 2016). By supporting local and scientific data needs as well as enhancing community capacity, AS7 contributes to addressing these challenges.

The Arctic Service 7 aims to improve the understanding of the changes in the distribution of hunting prey and ecosystems caused by factors such as climate change and shipping traffic. Several studies have shown that climate change has an impact at multiple levels of the Arctic food chain from several species of ice algae all the way up to the top predator Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*). In addition to changes in trophic levels, prey patterns, competition between species and parasitism could be influenced (Crepin et al., 2017). Also, marine invasive species, like crabs, could expand to sub-Arctic and Arctic waters (De Rivera et al. 2011), due to warmer waters and increased human activities.

The AS7 aims to especially improve the understanding of the effects of traffic noise on narwhal hunt and animals' wellbeing. Shipping traffic generates noise (Jalkanen et al., 2022) primarily caused by propeller cavitation (Jalkanen, 2018). Overall, anthropogenic noise can impact marine mammals through several mechanisms, including (a) disruption of behaviour (e.g., feeding, breeding, resting, migration), (b) masking of important sounds, (c) temporary or permanent hearing loss, (d) physiological stress or physical injury, and (e) changes to the ecosystems that result in a reduction of prey availability (Moore et al. 2012). For example, Taylor (2021) argues that the population of the orca has been negatively affected by the underwater noise stemming from commercial vessel traffic, tied to international trade. In the Arctic context key arctic species, such as walrus and narwhal have been identified to be particularly sensitive to ship noise (Huntington et al., 2023). Jalkanen (2022) reports a significant increase in shipping noise emissions in the Arctic between 2014 and 2020. However, the increase is notable in the Arctic because shipping noise emissions in this pristine region have historically been relatively low (Jalkanen, 2022). Sound plays a critical role in the survival of numerous marine species, particularly Arctic whales, who rely on it to navigate their surroundings, find food, and communicate with each other (Huntington et al., 2015). In addition to contributing to underwater noise, vessels present several other threats to marine mammals. For instance, Inuit have reported that whales such as beluga follow tracks by icebreakers which increases the risk of ice-entrapment mortality events if the open water freezes behind them (Huntington et al., 2023).

Food security is “a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life” (FAO, 2001). In recent years, food security has become a crucial issue in the circumpolar Arctic region. Factors affecting the foods and food systems of the region include both natural phenomena as well as geopolitical, socio-economic, and cultural aspects. Especially in the Nordic part of the circumpolar Arctic, traditional food supplies are under pressure causing adverse implications on the availability of safe and nutritious foods for many communities. (Hossain et al., 2021)

By enhancing the understanding of the changes in the distribution of hunting prey, Arctic Service 7 may offer potential improvements in food security in the Arctic region. For centuries, Arctic Indigenous groups have relied on gathering, fishing, hunting large land and sea mammals (van Luijk et al., 2022) and reindeer herding (Lindqvist, 2009) for their sustenance. Changes in local wildlife populations or habitat use caused

by shipping traffic can have a significant, deleterious effect on local Indigenous communities in the Arctic region, because local inhabitants still rely heavily on the harvest of wild foods as a key part of their diet (Ford, 2009; Kinloch et al., 1992). Country food which refers to traditional foods harvested from the land and sea, is central to economic, social and cultural identity for Arctic communities (Tyrrell, 2007). Arctic fisheries have been estimated to have an economic value of US\$1.26 billion per year when considering direct-use values (O’Garra, 2017).

Also, management and policy decisions regarding Arctic marine mammal resources are linked to the health, well-being, and culture of Indigenous communities (ICC-Alaska 2016). As such, these decisions are directly relevant for food security and sovereignty in the Arctic (Heeringa et al., 2019). Research suggests that the extent and immediacy of data uptake in decision-making is increased when local communities are tied to the production of information (community-based-monitoring) (Danielsen et al. 2007; Conrad and Hilchey 2011), although this tends to be limited to local rather than regional or national decision-making processes (Danielsen et al. 2010).

The Arctic Service 7 engages local communities in the co-creation of the service. Traditional Ecological Knowledge includes multiple bodies of knowledge accumulated over many generations (Drew 2005). This kind of knowledge is accrued through trial and error and transmitted to future generations orally or through practical experience (Drew 2005; Ohmagari and Berkes 1997) making it an important role in food security for the people in the Arctic (Pearce et al., 2015). Incorporating local knowledge ensures that the data collected is relevant to local communities. In addition, locals advising where to locate monitoring stations, when to install and remove instruments and how to work with dynamic sea ice, creates value by reducing the risk posed to instruments (Mahoney et al., 2009).

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3.8. Arctic service 8: Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety (LIS)

The Lake Ice Service (LIS) for Arctic Climate and Safety is part of the Finnish Environment Institute’s Earth Observation service. It delivers near real-time data on freshwater lake ice conditions by combining satellite imagery with in-situ observations from both community-based monitoring and governmental sources. The service offers a powerful tool for visualizing spatiotemporal data, whether through interactive maps or statistical time series which again serves as a valuable resource for tracking current lake ice conditions, studying long-term trends, and supporting communication, warnings, and educational purposes. Results of the VCA and economic evaluation confirm the initial findings made in the value tree analysis (VTA) presented D5.1 for the most part.

3.8.1. Value Chain Analysis

Figure 34. Value chain analysis of LIS.

Production and data of the Service

The dataset includes earth observation-derived lake ice and water temperature data, satellite-based true-colour images, SAR-images, in-situ data of governmental network and community-based monitoring. Technical infrastructure and coding skills are needed to production and maintenance of the service. Users are involved in the development of the service through continuous feedback mechanisms. These parties are citizens and local communities, governmental research institutes, policy makers, industry, security services, private sector, students and scientific purposes. According to positive user feedback, these feedback mechanisms have increased the usability of the service. As a next step in the development of the service, statistics on lake ice will be included in the service. LIS is developed and maintained by Syke (Finnish Environmental Institute). Third parties cannot influence the content of LIS or have own access requirements.

Information and Dissemination of the Service

The Lake Ice Service (LIS) monitors and presents lake ice conditions by integrating Earth Observation-derived data, in-situ measurements from governmental networks, and community-based monitoring. It also enables users to analyse satellite imagery and share observations, such as cracks in the ice cover. The LIS is accessible through Syke's Tarkka web map platform, which is openly available. The most effective way to track service usage is through regular user surveys. Additionally, monitoring changes in user numbers over time helps gauge the overall engagement with the service. Similarly, analysis using Spatineo's web tool reveals that user activity peaks in the spring, suggesting a high demand for information on ice melting during this period. Results of Spatineo's web tool analysis are presented in section 3.8.2 and utilised in the economic evaluation of the service. Information on the demographics of the users is not yet available, but it is expected that there are differences between the user groups. Use of the service does not require any special skills or specific equipment besides a computer or mobile phone and an internet connection. Usefulness of the information provided by LIS may be affected by the risk of misinterpretation as the extent of the lake ice does not necessarily depict the safety of the ice and ice thickness observations are sparsely located. It is more suitable for locating areas of open water and ice cracks.

Users and Uses of the Service

Currently, the LIS is utilised by a diverse range of users for various purposes, including citizens, local communities, policymakers, industry professionals, security services (such as rescue teams and border guards), the private sector, students, and researchers. Uses of the LIS seem to be more diverse when compared to the anticipated user groups in VTA analysis presented in D5.1. However, use of the Sami organisations has not been recognised but should be assessed in the future. In addition, the future user base of LIS is expected to expand to include media professionals as well. Citizens represent the largest group of users and likely remain the primary audience, while the distribution of other user groups is expected to be more balanced. Insights into both current and prospective users have been and can be gained through surveys and interviews.

In the hydroelectricity sector, the LIS is employed to optimise the hydropower production and to plan the production in a way that promotes the accumulation of river and lake ice in the autumn and decreases the risk of flooding in the spring. Thereby use of LIS potentially reduces infrastructure-related flood costs. LIS is used to assess the flood risk also by ELY centres which also may lead to avoided flood damages. In Finland, flood-related damage is estimated to range from 7 000 € to 50 000 € per building, with approximately 25 000 buildings located in designated flood risk areas (Michelsson & Saari, 2009; Finnish Environmental Institute, 2021). Furthermore, LIS contributes improving early warning systems by providing data that support the timely implementation of flood mitigation measures (Verta & Triipponen, 2011). While LIS offers potential for significant cost avoidance, quantifying its direct contribution to reduced flood and infrastructure damage remains challenging due to the influence of numerous external factors, including location-specific vulnerability and the presence of other mitigation measures such as elevated power sockets (Poussin et al., 2015). Nonetheless, the availability of lake ice extent data reduces the need for in-situ monitoring by ELY centres and the hydropower sector and supports targeting the in-situ monitoring trips that are unavoidable, resulting in measurable savings in operational costs. Additionally, this information may prevent unnecessary travel and reduce the associated loss of

recreational time for citizens (Arctic PASSION, 2024b). The avoided travel expenses are estimated in the economic evaluation in section 3.8.3.

For research, the information provided by the LIS on timings of lake ice accumulation and break-up is essential and can be utilised in for instance climate modelling and forecasts (Heinilä et al., 2021). Using satellite-based data on lake ice extent is more efficient than collecting data via in-situ monitoring trips as it has higher spatial and temporal resolution (Heinilä et al., 2021), which may also lead to avoided costs stemming from time savings in data acquisition. In addition, information from the service helps to better understand and identify new user needs, which - in turn - are important when planning potential targets for development. Developing the service benefits its users and increases the total value of the service.

The Lake Ice Service (LIS) offers potential safety benefits, particularly for professional users operating in ice-covered environments. The Finnish Border Guard utilizes the LIS to assess the safety of routes located on ice. If the service contributes to the avoidance of injuries or fatalities, the associated non-market and market-based benefits could be substantially higher than currently estimated. For example, the prevention of a single fatality per year could increase total benefits by 1,8 to 5,4 million USD-2005, equivalent to approximately 2,5 to 7,6 million (EUR-2024), depending on the applied value of a statistical life (VSL) (OECD, 2012). In addition to VSL, avoided productivity losses are commonly used as indicators of economic benefit. In the United Kingdom, the average productivity loss associated with an accident-related fatality was estimated at 555 660 GBP-1997, corresponding to approximately 1 043 900 in EUR-2024 (OECD, 2012). Assuming that the Finnish Border Guard relies on a similar number of information sources as the average professional user (see section 3.8.3), productivity loss and VSL estimates are scaled by a factor of 0,22. This results in an avoided productivity loss of approximately 122 250 GBP-1998, or 230 000 in EUR-2024, and a VSL ranging from 0,4 to 1,2 million USD-2005, equivalent to 0,6 to 1,7 million in EUR-2024. However, the lake ice extent data may lack sufficient spatial and temporal resolution to capture near-shore conditions and is limited under cloud cover or darkness which may negatively affect the safety benefits. In addition, while LIS offers information on both thickness and extent which are both essential for accurate safety assessments, ice thickness observations are sparsely located. Consecutive LIS observations may still provide indicative insights into ice firmness over time.

Careful planning of hydroelectric production supported by the LIS and other sources may allow for avoided environmental losses which also enhance recreation in the river. This is because the hydroelectricity sector monitors the lake ice situation not only to optimise the production, but also to ensure that the water level in the river does not pulsate, causing harm to ecosystems and ecosystem services of the river. However, the impact is uncertain and if hydropower plants use the service to optimise their production without considering the impacts the optimisation has on the environment and recreation possibilities near the hydropower plant, the benefit of the LIS for the hydropower plant might be a net cost to society. Especially during summertime hydropeaking affects negatively recreational ecosystem services (Virk et al., 2024). Negative impact on recreational ecosystem services may also decrease the housing and cottage prices in the riverside (Klizentyte et al., 2024).

3.8.2. Spatineo webtool results

Usage of the of Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety (AS8) was analysed both at an early stage of development (Jan 2019 - Nov 2021) as well as a later stage of development (Jan - Dec 2024). However, due to major changes in the Lake Ice service platform, comparative analysis is difficult: 1) The platform

changed both data sources used, 2) the later version of the software requests data from the backend services differently, 3) users of the later period were categorized into user types using a different method that led to slightly differing groupings. The analysis in this chapter focuses on results from 2024. For an analysis for the prior period, you can refer to earlier work (Donner, 2022). See chapter 3.2.3 for the definition of the terms *user* and *session*.

Figure 35. Identified user groups viewing the Lake Ice Extent product, separated monthly.

Figure 36. Number of sessions per month, grouped by user type.

In both periods, the visualisation of the usage data (Figures 35 and 36) shows that the Lake Ice Extent product is most interesting to users during Spring, at the time of the ice break-up season. The users in the

“general” group are mostly citizens or people in small companies. This matches earlier findings (Donner, 2022). However, there is a major difference with the off-season usage of the service. While no definitive cause could be identified, this could be attributed to the current platform of Tarkka being used also in other use cases than Lake Ice Extent which are relevant throughout the year. Users might for example add the Lake Ice Extent layers to the application when using Tarkka for other purposes, and such user will show up as a session for these numbers.

Peak usage in terms on sessions per month has more than tripled (3.7x, from roughly 1400 to 5138 during April). Even assuming, that baseline number of sessions during off-season (approximately 700 per month) is representative of the usage leaking from users not focusing on Lake Ice Extent, the usage has tripled (3.2x, from 1400 to 4437) in terms of number of sessions.

Figure 37. Number of sessions per month, grouped by origin country.

Analysis of the users’ origin country shows that the service is appealing mostly to Finnish users. This is in alignment with the Lake Ice Service’s goal to support local communities.

Figure 38. Relative distribution of user groups in 2024.

Figure 39. Geographic distribution of requested data locations from Tarkka in April 2024.

The geographic area the users of the Lake Ice Extent service were interested in correlates with the areas of Finland with higher population and lake densities. This is in line with the analysis of the user groups: the individual users of the service focus on their localities and the areas of their vacation homes.

With this detailed data of the use of the service, WP5 and the pilot service provider can identify trends in service usage. The trends in the use of the service can either support the assumptions regarding the use made by the pilot service developers or reveal new and unexpected use-cases. If the usage data reveals unexpected behaviour, it is possible to identify benefits for the users that were not considered in the development phase of the pilot service. It is highly recommended that web site cookie policies and terms of service include clauses to inform the user of the tracking.

3.8.3. Economic evaluation

Based on the results of the VCA analysis, avoided travel expenses due to better targeted and avoided in-situ monitoring trips and recreational trips are estimated in the economic evaluation. Lehtinen (2024) has quantified these avoided travel expenses by applying avoided cost (or cost-loss) method. Here the results are presented and updated with more recent data covering year 2024 for the recreational use. The benefits EO data in the Arctic have been assessed using the LIS as a case study subject also by Donner (2022), who conducted a value tree analysis (VTA). Her results are indirectly utilised in the analysis conducted by Lehtinen (2024). In addition, for more information, Dewulf and Mamais (2022) have conducted a socioeconomic benefit study on Syke's TARKKA service platform, where the LIS is located. The economic evaluation is structured as follows. First, used data and the context-specific application of the methods presented in D5.2 (Toolset of societal benefit estimates) is demonstrated and clarified in relation to the LIS. This is followed by the evaluation results.

Data

Available data comprises of interview results, user survey results, Spatineo web traffic tool data on number of users (see 3.8.2, for more detailed information on the method see 3.2.3. and Deliverable 5.2), and previous literature. Results of five interviews in total were utilised: one with the representative of ELY centre, three with the hydroelectricity sector representative and one with sea ice researcher. Conducted interviews were semi-constructed. Interviewees were asked for what purposes they need lake ice extent information, how do they use the information, what other sources they use, how often these sources are used and what are the benefits of using the sources. These interviews were complemented with a follow-up interview with the hydroelectricity sector representative and additional questions sent via email to both the representative of ELY centre and the hydroelectricity sector to obtain information that is essential for avoided cost calculating including one-way distances to in-situ monitoring sites, number of in situ-monitoring trips and working hours that in-situ monitoring trips take. Although sea ice and lake ice have different features, sea ice researcher was interviewed to gain understanding on the role of lake ice information on safety. Interview questions are in Appendix 8. A survey targeted for users of the LIE service was conducted in early 2023. Survey was located on the web page of the service and the responses of the survey have been anonymised. Survey has 44 responses, and its questions regarded uses of the service, how frequent and beneficial the use is, and what kind of impact it has had on decision-making. Respondents were also given an opportunity to address any targets for development. Survey can be found in Appendix 4.

Methods

Avoided travel expenses

To quantify the avoided costs for the LIS, travel expense formula adopted from the travel cost method is utilised. Cost of an avoided trip is estimated by summing all the expenses used for the trip including the actual travel costs, equipment costs and cost of time (Boyle et al., 2017). Avoided travel expenses were calculated using Equation 1 presented by Boyle et al. (2017):

Equation 1. Travel expenses

$$p_n = \left\{ (0,33 * \left(\frac{y_n}{1553} \right) * t_n) + (c_n * d_n) \right\},$$

in which p_n is the cost of an avoided trip, y_n is the annual income of the user, t_n is the round-trip travel time to the lake, c_n is the cost of travel per kilometre, and d_n is the distance to the lake. Annual income is divided by the average annual working hours in Finland 2023 to obtain hourly wage (Official Statistics of Finland, 2024b). In estimation of value of time it is estimated that it is related to one's wage with the assumption that it is feasible to switch between working time and leisure flexibly. Multiplying the value of time by 0,33 is often used as a measure of value for recreational time. (Boyle et al., 2017.) In calculation of avoided trip expenses of professional users, value of time is multiplied by one instead of 0,33 to account for the total hourly wage.

In travel cost analysis, the trip expenses are calculated for each individual and include often other information such as other costs (Boyle et al., 2017). For simplification purposes, cost of avoided trip is extrapolated for all users based on averages provided by Official Statistics Finland (2019; 2024a) and Trafi (2019). These averages include median salary (Official Statistics Finland, 2024a) and in the case of recreation, average distance to a summer cottage (Official Statistics Finland, 2019). Average of cost of

using a car per kilometre is calculated by Trafi (2019). Cost of an individual trip is multiplied by the number of trips avoided. In the case of professional users, the number of avoided trips and lengths of the trips were directly enquired from hydroelectricity sector and ELY centre representatives. Hypothetical total avoided costs were estimated by aggregating the avoided costs of the interviewed hydroelectricity company and ELY-centre for all hydroelectricity companies and other ELY centres. In Finland, there are 15 ELY centres and 220 hydro power plants in total (ELY centre, 2024; Energiateollisuus, 2024). It is assumed that each of these actors must do same number of in-situ monitoring trips to water bodies nearby without the information provided by the LIS.

When it comes to recreation, estimation of benefits in the form of avoided travel expenses is highly intricate due to complexities of human behaviour. It is not feasible to calculate avoided costs by using the LIS in recreation accurately. However, the survey results indicate that the LIS does affect decision-making in recreation. Level of avoided costs if every user was to avoid one trip per year is estimated based on the share of users that use the service for recreational activities. In year 2024, 77,9 % of the LIS users are “isp” users, which includes citizens (see section 3.8.2). It is assumed that “isp” user refers to recreational user, which means that the service had 14 190 recreational users in year 2024. It is assumed that cost of avoided trip consists of trip to the site and back.

Impact of an individual source of information

The LIS users can utilise also other sources to monitor the lake ice extent, meaning that the avoided costs do not fully stem from using the LIS. In addition, different information sources are used to complement each other. Distinguishing avoided costs using the LIS is attempted in the analysis by multiplying avoided costs by the contribution of an individual information source. As more precise information on the marginal contribution of each source is lacking it is assumed that each source has an equal weight in the contribution to benefit creation and that the sources cannot be used to complement each other. This simple estimation is presented in Equation 2.

Equation 2. Contribution of an individual source to avoided costs

$$\textit{impact of an individual source} = \frac{1}{n_{\textit{other sources}}}$$

At most, six other sources are used by the hydroelectricity sector and two other sources are used by ELY centres. Hence, avoided costs of hydroelectricity sector are multiplied by 0,16 and by 0,5 in the case of ELY centres. It is more difficult to assess the impact of other sources in decisions related to recreation. Here we assume that the user seeks information from one other source in addition to the LIS (e.g., weather forecast, other satellite data provider or activity specific source such as a map of skiing routes combined with in-situ observations of other skiers). The number of other sources of information used by the Finnish border guard and other public authorities is unknown. As they are professional users, it is assumed that they utilise average number of information sources used by other professional users meaning that the potential avoided costs of safety improvements are multiplied by 0,22.

Benefit-cost ratio (BCR)

To assess the net impacts of the LIS, the attributable production costs of the service are compared to the benefits, in this case being avoided costs, i.e. the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) is calculated. BCR is calculated using Equation 3,

Equation 3. Benefit-cost ratio

$$BCR = \frac{\text{benefits}}{\text{costs}}$$

where benefits refer to the sum of monetised and quantified benefits of the service per year and costs are production costs of the service.

Results

The total avoided costs and the adjusted avoided cost based on the number of other sources by user group are presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Avoided costs using the LIS, 2024 (EUR-2024).

Sector, user group	Avoided costs per year	
	total	adjusted based on number of other information sources
Recreation (consumer)	1 140 000 €	570 000 €
Energy sector (producer)	317 000 €	53 000 €
ELY centres	20 000 €	10 000 €
Total	1 219 000 €	649 000 €

For the professional users, one-way distances of in-situ monitoring trips range from 20 km to 110 km and often take several hours, if not the whole day, as the monitored sites are often located in places that are difficult to access. By using the LIS and other sources, 1652 in-situ monitoring trips were avoided by the professional users in total per year when it is assumed that every ELY centre and hydropower plant in Finland use the service. On average, avoided cost of an avoided in-situ monitoring trip is 204 €. In total, 338 000 € worth of in-situ monitoring trips were avoided. Avoided costs using the LIS by the professional users are 63 000 € when it is assumed that the impact of the LIS is 0,16 in decisions of hydroelectricity sector and 0,5 in decisions of the ELY centre. As the LIS and similar services support the planning and targeting of unavoidable in-situ monitoring trips, avoided costs are likely higher.

For recreational users, estimated avoided travel expense per trip is 80 €. When every recreational user avoids one trip per year using the service, avoided travel expenses in recreation are 320 000 € on average annually (Table 21). Avoided costs are 160 000 € per year on average when it is assumed that the impact of the lake ice service on decision in recreation is 0,5. Avoided recreational trips due to unsuitable lake ice conditions also represent an avoided loss of leisure time. Avoided costs in recreation are estimated separately in Table 21 for each year. The level of estimated avoided travel expenses has varied throughout the analysis period. It should be noted that the composition of the Tarkka service (where the LIS is located) has changed in 2024 which explains the difference in number of users when comparing years 2021-2023 to year 2024 (see section 3.8.2).

Table 21. Assumed level of avoided travel expenses in recreation. The composition of the Tarkka service (where the LIS is located) has changed in 2024 which explains the difference in number of users when comparing years 2021-2023 to year 2024 (see section 3.8.2).

Year	Travel expenses avoided in recreation if every user avoids one trip annually	
	total	adjusted based on assumed number of information sources
2020	109 000 €	54 500 €
2021	152 000 €	76 000 €
2022	86 000 €	43 000 €
2023	113 000 €	56 500 €
2024	1 140 000 €	570 000 €
Total for 2020–2024	1 600 000 €	800 000 €
Average for 2020–2024	320 000 €	160 000 €

Present value of costs and benefits

The present value (PV) costs and benefits for the time frame between 2024 and 2100 are presented in Table 22. The total present value of benefits represents the benefits generated through the usage of AS8. For ELY Centres and the energy sector, the number of users is assumed to remain constant. In contrast, benefits for recreational users are projected to increase over time. Specifically, the estimated range of benefits accounts for scenarios in which the annual growth in recreational users varies between 0.1% and 1% annually. The Spatineo webtool analysis indicates an average annual user growth of approximately 8% between 2020 and 2023: however, this growth rate is likely not continue over the long term. Consequently, a more conservative growth range of 0.1% to 1% per year is applied in the projections. The benefits are compared with the costs of the service. It is assumed that development costs are included during the first five-year period from 2024 to 2028, after which only maintenance costs persist through to the year 2100. Discount rates of 3%, 1% and 7% are applied. For a detailed explanation of the present value calculation methodology, see the economic valuation of AS6 in Section 3.6.2 (Methods).

Table 22. Comparing the present value of costs and partial present value of benefits in the time frame 2024–2100.

Discount rate	PV of costs, €	Energy sector	ELY centres	PV of benefits, €	
				Recreation 0.1-1 % annual user growth	In total
3%	602 501	9 493 476	601 646	34 950 565 – 44 406 271	35 552 211 – 54 501 393
1%	1 031 331	16 987 563	1 076 582	63 083 738 – 86 910 891	81 147 883 – 104 975 036
7%	313 141	4 509 490	285 788	16 424 256 – 18 776 669	21 219 534 – 23 571 947

Costs of the service and benefit-cost ratio (BCR)

The personnel costs of the LIS have been approximately 96 000 € during the whole 8-year development period. In the development stage, costs of outsourced services are ca. 10 000 € / year and maintenance

costs are ca. 10 000 € / year. For non-development stages, the LIS has personnel costs ca. 15 000 € and 3 000 € travel costs annually. Costs of observations cannot be reliably estimated and thus are not considered in the analysis.

Table 23. Costs of Arctic service 8

Development costs per year	Maintenance costs per year
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of labour, outsourced services and maintenance during the development phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of labour, co-development and education, travelling costs, use of observations (not included in the cost estimation)
In total 18 000€	In total 32 000€

Benefit-cost ratio (BCR) is calculated only for the year 2024. For non-development stage BCR is 1/20, and for non-development stage the BCR is 1/35. The ratio is probably lower due to not including observation cost. If direct economic impacts (i.e. production optimisation by the industries) are added to the calculation, BCR is probably higher. Same applies if using the service contributes to avoided mortality.

Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis is conducted to address the main uncertainties of the quantified avoided costs for year 2024. Uncertainties regarding recreation (Table 24) and professional users (Table 25) are assessed separately. Main uncertainties in recreation regard the behaviour of the users. Especially the number of avoided trips is challenging to estimate. If half of the users avoid travel expenses of one recreational trip per year, avoided travel expenses would be 570 000 € in total whereas if every user avoids two trip expenses per year, avoided travel expenses in recreation would be 2 281 000 € (see table 24). Number of recreational users is also uncertain as it is assumed that “isp” user equals recreational user. If the assumption of one avoided trip per user is kept constant and number of users was to increase by 25 %, avoided travel expenses would be 856 000 € and vice versa, if number of users decrease by 25 %, costs would be 1 426 000 €. Impact of other sources on the level of quantified avoided costs is also highly uncertain. If the impact is 25 % lower than assumed (0,5), avoided costs in travel expenses in recreation would be 285 000 € per year, and if the impact is 25 % higher than assumed, avoided travel expenses are 856 000 €.

Table 24. Sensitivity analysis of annual avoided travel expenses in recreation, 2024

	Number of recreational users		Number of avoided trips per user		Significance of the LIS in relation to other sources	
change	- 25 %	+ 25 %	0,5	2	- 25 %	+ 25 %
avoided costs	856 000 €	1 426 000 €	570 000 €	2 281 000 €	285 000 €	856 000 €

While the interview with ELY centre representative showed that every ELY centre uses the LIS, it is uncertain whether all hydropower plants utilise the service. If 25 % less hydroelectric companies use the LIS, avoided in-situ monitoring expenses would be 238 000 €, and if half of the hydroelectric companies use the service, the expenses would be 159 000 € (see table 25). As it is assumed in the analysis that every hydroelectric company utilises the LIS, increase in the number of hydroelectric companies is not assessed.

Number of avoided in-situ monitoring trips seems to affect the results considerably. If number of avoided trips was to decrease by 25 %, avoided in-situ monitoring trips would be 262 000 €, and if the number would increase by 25 %, total avoided in-situ monitoring costs would be 413 000 €. Impact of other sources was assessed as well. When impact of other sources is 25 % lower, avoided in-situ monitoring expenses in professional use are 47 000 € and vice versa, when impact is 25 % higher, they are 79 000 €.

Table 25. Sensitivity analysis of avoided annual in-situ monitoring costs of professional users (hydroelectricity, ELY centres)

change	Number of hydroelectric companies using the service		Number of avoided in-situ monitor trips		Significance of the LIS in relation to other sources	
	- 25 %	- 50 %	- 25 %	+ 25 %	- 25 %	+ 25 %
avoided cost	238 000 €	159 000 €	262 000 €	413 000 €	47 000 €	79 000 €

Limitations and uncertainties

User behaviour plays a central role in the economic evaluation of the LIS but also represents a major source of uncertainty, making estimating the number of avoided trips due to the LIS service in recreation challenging. Additionally, the simultaneous use of multiple climate services complicates attribution of avoided costs to any single service. Users combine information from several sources, whose perceived reliability and usage vary. For instance, the LIS service limitations in resolution and data availability under certain conditions reduce its individual impact. Uncertainty also arises from the assumptions used in cost estimations, including trip lengths, user income levels, number of recreational users, and vehicle costs. Data limitations such as shared IP addresses, regional differences in monitoring needs, and unaccounted-for drone costs further affect the accuracy of results. Finally, the small sample size limits the generalisability of findings. Broader representation across professional and recreational users, as well as input from relevant agencies such as border guards and emergency services, would have strengthened the analysis and improved reliability of conclusions regarding safety and cost impacts.

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4. Summary of the results

Table 26. Summary of the results

Arctic service	Information	Users (inc. potential)	Societal benefits	Type of assessment				
				Value chain analysis (VCA)	Economic evaluation	Value tree analysis (VTA)	Qualitative evaluation	Spatio-temporal analysis
AS1: Event Database of Community-Based Monitoring using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge	Written data of oral records of past and recent events/changes in landscapes, cryosphere, and ecosystems in the Arctic and new instrument-based observations	Indigenous communities Arctic researcher Scholars People interested in the Arctic	Strengthening and diversifying monitoring capacity Support adaptation and risk mitigation in the Arctic Preserve and disseminate IK Promoting CBM and Indigenous-led science	x		x	x	
AS2: Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX)	Visualised information on land surface change, hot spots of disturbance, and potential areas of active permafrost thaw and erosion	Local communities Private and official planners Research and education General public	Better understanding of the state of permafrost Better informed site selection (construction, leisure and subsistence) Reduced risks and costs associated with infrastructure	x			x	x
AS3: State of the Arctic Environment	Current state of Terrestrial Cryosphere Marine Atmospheric indicators in the Arctic	Decision makers at various levels Citizens living in the Arctic Academics and Arctic researchers	Collecting information under one portal: Time saving More informed decisions Easier to track the state of the Arctic environment	x			x	

AS4: Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA)	Wildfire risks, ignition risks, active fires, and burned areas (damage assessment)	Citizens in the Arctic Local organisations and governments Emergency services and rescue department	Increased communication, information and preparedness of wildfires: Savings in damages and costs (direct and indirect) Potentially avoided mortalities Damage assessments	x			x	
AS5: Air Quality Forecast for Arctic Communities (AURORAE)	Real-time air pollution data for Arctic communities in Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland	Citizens Communities Policymakers in the Arctic	Better awareness of air pollution: Preventing health problems Healthcare savings	x		x	x	
AS6: Improving safety for shipping in the polar seas (POLARIS)	Forecasts and near real time RIO indexes (level of risk) that consider local ice conditions and the ship's ice class	Marine users operating in sea ice or close to the sea ice edge	Better understanding of risks to: avoid accidents and improve safety optimize ship-routing and to avoid costs (incl. environmental damage), time, fuel, emissions etc. Plan investments (which ice class to choose for specific routes)	x	x	x		
AS7: CBM for Arctic marine climate change, noise pollution & impacts on marine living resources	Seasonal and yearly variations in ambient noise, presence of hunting animals and changes in the habitat. Effect of traffic in the hunting area.	Local community Greenland Government Management of nature and hunting Researchers	Support food security and sustainability Building local capacity and decision-making Better understanding of impacts of climate change and traffic, adaptive capacity	x			x	
AS8: Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety (LIS)	Near real-time data on freshwater lake ice conditions presented visually. Observations on lake ice thickness.	Research and education Industries (e.g., hydroelectricity) Public authorities (e.g., ELY centres, Finnish border guard) Recreation	Provide data to support research Safety improvements Avoided and reduced in-situ monitoring and recreational trip costs Production optimisation (hydroelectricity) Flood risk monitoring	x	x	x		x

5. Discussion

Societal benefits and significance of the Arctic Services and pan-AOSS

Results presented in this deliverable demonstrate wide variety of benefits for various user groups of the Arctic services (ASs) developed in the Arctic PASSION project. In particular, benefits for the local communities living in the Arctic regions are clear and possess several types of values ranging from direct use values (such as optimised route planning) to indirect use values (such as better information supporting research) and from tangible values (such as avoided travel expenses) to intangible values (such as preservation of Indigenous Knowledge). These benefits are realised through multiple pathways, with one of the most important being the ability of the ASs to support informed decision-making across the Arctic from subsistence and leisure activities to infrastructure planning. Co-creation of these services also plays a key role in helping to elevate Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge as a vital part of how monitoring and related activities are carried out in the Arctic.

Economic evaluations for AS6 and AS8 indicate significant economic benefits (e.g. avoided travel costs, including fuel and time) and further demonstrate the potential benefits of Arctic services in general. As the ASs keep developing further, uptake of the services increases and users learn to use them more effectively for their needs, the economic, as well as societal, benefits are expected to grow. For instance, AS2 holds potential significant monetary savings in avoided infrastructure damage due to permafrost degradation, and AS5 may decrease the welfare costs of air pollution in the Nordic countries. Although the results of the assessments already show reasonable economic benefits, it is also important to note that the quantified results presented in this report represent only a part of the full picture. Usually, only one type of benefit or objective is selected for valuation, which means the total economic benefits are likely to be much greater than what is captured. It is also expected that the Arctic services, also other than AS2, AS5, AS6 and AS8, may generate indirect economic benefits via mechanisms such as increased productivity.

Despite a growing body of research, significant gaps remain in the understanding of the environmental and social consequences of rapid climate change in the Arctic (Bigras, 2013; Knapp & Trainor, 2015). Besides the concern of fragile ecosystems and Indigenous livelihoods, Arctic communities face complex challenges, including large-scale industrial development and escalating health and social concerns. Due to climate change, the region is drawing increasing international attention due to its vast resource potential, emerging shipping routes linked to diminishing sea ice, and unresolved issues related to international boundaries and sovereignty. Research and knowledge-based strategies that integrate multi-jurisdictional regulations, environmental considerations, and local perspectives are essential for managing cumulative impacts (Bigras, 2013). Hence, the benefits of an integrated pan-AOSS are likely wide-scale as the produced information is less fragmented and systematic, improving the accessibility and usability of the information. Arctic services contribute directly to addressing the urgent needs of Arctic communities, in addition to some of the services delivering information related to the Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) (see Deliverable 6.3). Furthermore, the services increase the knowledge about the state of the Arctic which supports monitoring and understanding climate change in a global scale.

To ensure that the ASs reach their end users and the full benefit potential of the services is achieved, continuity of the services after the project should be made sure. This is crucial from the value creation perspective: generated benefit tends to grow as the end users pick up the most effective ways of utilising the information provided by a climate service. Solving this issue is outside the scope of this deliverable but is part of project's legacy planning. Recommendations by the Arctic PASSION consortium for ensuring the long-term establishment of the pan-AOSS were gathered in a publications based on an Arctic PASSION deliverable by

Grosfeld et al. (2025). Sustainable coordination, support for SAON's ROADS process and for Indigenous contribution, enhancing the sharing of logistical platforms, equal inclusion of Indigenous peoples, long-term funding, and improved data management are called for, among other recommendations. The need for basing monitoring and observations on societal needs is also well recognised. Interdisciplinary research is required for understanding the socioeconomic and environmental interdependencies.

Assessment of intangible and non-market benefits generated by the Arctic Services is complex

Demonstration of the societal benefits in monetary or other quantified terms support communicating the benefits of the Arctic services to wider audiences, including actors such as financing institutions. While monetary estimates may be easier to grasp by a wider audience, communication of the benefits cannot be narrowed down to consider only the monetary estimates. Many benefits, particularly social or environmental ones, carry value that is not easily captured in monetary terms. When the impacts affect vulnerable groups or when the value of a service lies in non-use values, such as existence or altruistic values, that are inherently difficult to monetise, assessment of intangible benefits can come with ethical considerations. For instance, attempting to translate the value of preserving Indigenous Knowledge into monetary terms overlooks the broad array of values tied to it and may be ethically questionable. In such cases, as illustrated in AS1, assigning monetary value may lead to misleading or biased outcomes and is therefore not recommended. Yet, we all – Indigenous People, service developers, researchers and funders alike – need to make choices about resource use. In terms of societal information services, it is sometimes easier to estimate costs in advance rather than impacts; hence collecting and comparing the costs can help weigh up the different options in terms of the quality of the resources used. For quantifiable impacts, this can be done by applying cost-impact approach. Implicitly, this weighing of options against a limited budget is done all the time.

Furthermore, it is important to pay close attention to the context in which the assessment is carried out, including who is conducting it, for what purpose, and who is impacted by the results, either directly or indirectly (OECD, 2018). In the case of CBA, some of the main issues more formally are the *issue of standing* (whose benefits and costs are considered and whose are not) and the *distributional effects* (how the benefits and costs of an information service are distributed across different groups). The outcome of the assessment can be significantly shaped by these factors. Excluding the impact of asymmetrical distribution of benefits and costs for certain groups, such as women, can result in decisions, made based on the results of a CBA, that fail to address the needs, contributions, and vulnerabilities of these groups (Kabeer, 1992; Watt et al., 2017). Gender is one key dimension in these considerations. In the Arctic PASSION project, whenever possible, the gender perspective has been intentionally integrated into the overall assessment process through a dedicated Deliverable 8.4 which explores how gender plays a role in Arctic research, with a particular focus on environmental monitoring activities. Additionally, it is important to critically reflect on the assumptions underlying the analysis. These assumptions can shape the results in significant ways, and understanding their influence is a key part of responsible and transparent assessment (OECD, 2018). Yet, it is often mandatory to make assumptions to be able to conduct an economic evaluation since we cannot, for example, know the exact actions of every user. Given these limitations, economic evaluations should be viewed as decision-support tools rather than definitive measures of value.

Novelty as a limitation in estimating societal benefits of the Arctic Services

The selection of an evaluation method depends heavily on the available and utilisable data and the selected scope of the analysis, meaning that conduction of formal ex-ante economic assessments such as CBA of climate services come with a high uncertainty (Perrels, 2020). To avoid giving too uncertain results that may underestimate or overestimate the actual benefits, potentially affecting the development of the ASs, we decided not to proceed with ex-ante economic evaluations for most of the ASs. Only exception is the economic evaluation of AS6 (POLARIS), which is made ex-ante basis. Using historical vessel and price data, potential

annual avoided costs were assessed for every 1% saved in total fuel consumption. The evaluation involves assumptions and uncertainties that must be considered when interpreting the results. Anyhow, the evaluation provides initial insight into the potential benefits of AS6 and can be updated as the service matures and user numbers, geographic distribution and other relevant data become available. For AS8, the economic evaluation is conducted partly ex-post basis; actual use of the service has been documented via interviews with users who regularly use the service, surveys and Spatineo web traffic tools. To confirm the effectiveness of an economic evaluation of a climate service, it should be complemented with an ex-post assessment (Perrels, 2020). In general, to fully realise the services' potential and build a user base, continuous investigation is needed to identify the most promising stages and areas in the value chain. Increased engagement with end users, particularly through in-depth interviews or surveys, would be valuable in uncovering deeper insights into service usage. Engagement of the end users is critical to unlock the full potential of an information service: the value of a service is determined by the actions of the user.

The novelty of most of the services also limited the possibilities to conduct Spatineo web traffic tool analyses since no website/users naturally equals no user data. Besides the limitation related to the 'newness' of the services also persuading service providers to give WP5 access to web service usage data of their services for web traffic analysis with Spatineo tools appeared to be a challenge with already publicly available services (concerns over organisational data policies and GDPR). Fortunately, two of the newly developed services were mature enough, open for users and willing to share their web service's usage data with Spatineo to conduct web traffic analysis: AS2 - Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX) and AS8 - The Lake Ice Service (LIS). For these ASs, and in general, web traffic analyses were highly beneficial for understanding the usage of a service. For instance, Spatineo web traffic tool analyses supported locating the users geographically and provided information on different uses, level of use, and user groups of the service (government, business, citizen). These data were fed into the economic assessment of AS8 to complement the information collected through surveys and interviews (see Appendices 2, 4 and 5). If possible, more in-depth web traffic analyses to support economic evaluations could be conducted for the remainder of the services in the future.

Besides above mentioned difficulties in evaluating recently piloted information services, conducting socio-economic assessment is often constrained by limited resources, especially in cases where primary data collection is required, which is also the case in this deliverable. Research of revealed or stated preferences takes time and effort, particularly when a service is new and there is no established user base (e.g., AS3 which has not been published yet). In these cases, use of benefit transfer method may be convenient, although it is not guaranteed that there are existing studies (e.g., AS7). If no suitable studies are available, nor resources for conducting a primary study, an economic assessment is not possible. While we acknowledge the limits of economic evaluation, economic evaluations still provide important information to several actors, even when done in a less comprehensive manner.

Arctic Services in a bigger picture: value of information and information differentiation

When assessing the value of weather and climate services, valuation studies typically assume that decision makers have some level of prior climate knowledge and in the absence of updated information, decisions are made based on the prior knowledge (Katz & Lazo, 2012). Consequently, the concept of value of information (VoI) can be used to state that the value of the climate information, which is equal to the difference in benefits when updated information is used, compared to benefits when only prior knowledge is used. The magnitude of VoI is influenced by several interdependent factors: the stakes involved in the decision, the level of prior uncertainty, the precision of the new information and the users' degree of risk aversion. These factors together define the value of a piece of information, but their individual impact is not always unambiguous. For instance, higher stakes can lead to either lower or higher value of information depending on how uncertainty interacts with the decision environment. Similarly, risk-averse individuals often prefer the latest

information available to reduce uncertainty, while risk-tolerant individuals may delay acquiring new information, which affects their willingness to pay for the information (Birchler & Bütler, 2007). The realised benefit or Vol is also dependent on the nature of weather and climate related risks, the number and types of users and their capability to act upon the information to avoid harm or increase economic output (Anderson et al., 2015).

While the theoretical concept of the Vol is often used to describe the value of information products, most often information systems, this approach has also caused division between researchers about the intrinsic value of information and the value of the systems that deliver it. For instance, Hilton (1981) argues that the value of an information system is directly equivalent to the value of the information it provides, while Sassone (1981) and Repo (1987) argue that there is a clear distinction between information and information products by highlighting that in the presence of competing information delivery systems, the demand for these services does not reflect the demand for the information itself but is also influenced by the competitive context. However, as Ziolkowska (2018) highlights, evaluating the value of information in monetary terms must occur indirectly because of the intangible appearance of information. Information itself has no market but information services, on the other hand, have been marketed and assigned a value. This highlights a critical transition from valuing information in the abstract to creating *differentiation value* – the added value a specific service offers beyond what is already available from alternatives or prior knowledge. In this sense, realising Vol in practice depends not only on the informational content itself, but also on how uniquely and effectively it is delivered. Acknowledging differentiation value, whether through improved usability, timeliness, credibility, or integration with user workflow, is therefore essential when assessing the value of the service, and not the value of the information provided by the service.

Geopolitics and Arctic governance challenges

Political landscape and other environmental factors are likely to affect the benefits generated by the ASs and the pan-AOSS. While warming in the Arctic poses various and wide-ranging risks to the region, it also enables new economic opportunities, as the Arctic holds vast and relatively untapped natural resources. Thawing of permafrost will make previously inaccessible natural resources such as oil, gas and minerals more accessible, and the shrinking sea ice cover in addition will allow for greater exploitation of the Arctic shipping routes. Hence, the economic potential of the Arctic has attracted the interest of many actors, and geopolitical interest towards the region is likely to grow as new opportunities emerge. (Juhanko & Juvonen, 2024.) The geopolitics of the region has taken shape this far with multilateralism and diplomacy which is largely thanks to the Arctic Council (Lavengood, 2021). The Arctic Council has historically maintained peaceful relations even in times of tensions rising far from the Arctic Circle. The Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 and the following pause in Arctic Council activities have questioned the future of Arctic Council and Arctic governance in general. This comes at a critical time when increasing environmental and geopolitical pressures demand heightened cooperation rather than division (Dyck, 2024). The geopolitical situation, political tensions and relations, regulation, and cooperation will affect the magnitude of the benefits of Arctic services in the region as well. For example, the future of Arctic shipping is highly dependent on the geopolitics of the area since issues regarding economic access and environmental stewardship remain unresolved. Balancing the needs of local communities, Indigenous rights-holder, environmental protection, and economic development is a serious challenge in order to secure a sustainable future for the Arctic.

6. Conclusions

Through the work in this deliverable, we have demonstrated the wide variety of societal benefits generated by the Arctic Services developed in the Arctic PASSION project. We have assessed the value chain (VCA) of each AS and complemented the assessment by qualitative, quantitative and economic approaches, showing the stage-wise process of value adding steps in the case of an Arctic service and how the value (potentially) translates into benefits for the Indigenous people, local communities and other stakeholders such as the scientific audience. Most importantly, Arctic services are likely to contribute to addressing the growing need to better monitor and understand the vast changes the Arctic is facing due to the warming climate. An integrated pan-AOSS system will contribute to more informed decision-making and a deeper understanding of the Arctic, as it will make data more accessible and less fragmented, thus improving data availability and usability.

The process of developing this report has also underlined the complexities of assessing the societal and economic dimensions of climate information services and provided new lessons learned. Although we tried to create an evaluation process as flexible as possible in deliverable 5.2, recurring barriers limited the depth of our evaluations and results. The key barriers are mainly due to the difficulty of assessing benefits of a brand-new - or pilot phase - service, which does not have an established user base or usage data. Although this difficulty is present in all ex-ante evaluations, the uncertainty for conducting a formal CBA or other more detailed assessment can be too high including too many assumptions. Besides the issue of lack of utilisable data and novelty of the Arctic services, economic evaluations in general come with several complexities, especially when assessing the societal benefits of an information service. Monetising intangible benefits is a complex process, and sometimes not advisable (see AS1). Moreover, the assessment of value of information (VoI) is already affected by factors such as market context and competing information sources (the precision and differentiation value of the new information) and the prospective user's willingness to pay or obtain the newest information (the users' degree of risk aversion) (see Discussion).

Given the novelty of the services, it is essential that the data needs of societal benefit assessment are taken into account in the development of an information service to get as detailed assessment as possible. Ideally, service development and evaluation support each other to achieve the best outcome for both. Achieving this requires that analysts conducting the economic evaluations are included in the very early stages of service development, where initial discussions between service developers and potential service users take place. To attain this in Arctic PASSION, first discussions between WP5 and service developers were initiated already during the work of D5.1, and after the findings guided the economic evaluation toolset created in D5.2. Collaboration between developers, evaluators and end users helps to understand the end-user needs and the qualitative and/or quantitative impacts the service generates. This is important because, ultimately, the benefit of a service is determined by how well the service succeeds in answering these needs and what actions the end user takes based on the information provided. With some of the services, limited ability to interview and interact with actual end users (e.g. due to the development stage of the service) affected the level of comprehensiveness of the evaluations which further highlights another key takeaway: the starting point of an information service development should *always* be a certain need of an existing end-user group. Creating a service with no prospective end users or detected need for specific information entails a high risk of underutilisation and inefficient use of resources. Yet, recognising the practical applicability and relevance of a climate service is complicated when the end users are not aware of the existence of climate services and their possibilities, and therefore, awareness raising is important. This is particularly critical for newly created climate services that do not have similar, existing services available for the end users.

In conclusion, the rapid warming of the Arctic places increasing pressure on its fragile ecosystems, unique biodiversity, and the livelihoods of Indigenous peoples, underscoring the urgent need to support the adaptation efforts of local communities and other stakeholders in the region. Balancing between the needs of local communities, environmental responsibility, and emerging economic opportunities is a serious challenge to secure a sustainable future for the Arctic. To ensure meaningful, inclusive, and environmentally informed decision-making, it is essential to adopt a multidimensional and multidisciplinary approach when assessing long-term societal benefits. This is particularly important when evaluating intangible benefits affecting Indigenous Peoples and other minorities. To support this, WP5 emphasises that effective and comprehensive evaluation frameworks must integrate both quantitative and qualitative dimensions, alongside ethical, cultural, and environmental considerations. Through its work, WP5 contributes to advancing the understanding of the societal value of Arctic observations. By offering practical tools, initial insights, and recommendations, WP5 supports the development and assessment of future climate services in the Arctic and beyond.

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Appendices

1. Value Chain Analysis Survey

Respondent and the Pilot Service

The aim of this section is to provide a general overview of the information differentiation that the service provides, as well as its current and potential user groups. It is beneficial for service developers and evaluators to understand the scope of use and how it is being utilized. The value, or impacts, of a service can be estimated by analyzing how new information alters the decisions and actions of its current and potential users. Measuring these changes is essential for the economic analysis of the service.

1. Contact information: name, affiliation and email address.
2. On behalf of which Pilot Service you are completing the survey?
 - Pilot Service 1 - Arctic Event Database
 - Pilot Service 2 - Permafrost (ALEX)
 - Pilot Service 3 - State of the Arctic Environment
 - Pilot Service 4 - Wildfires (INFRA)
 - Pilot Service 5 - Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast
 - Pilot Service 6 - Polar Sea Ice (POLARIS)
 - Pilot Service 7 - Noise Pollution in Arctic Marine
 - Pilot Service 8 - Lake Ice (TARKKA)
3. What information does the service offer and in what format?
 - a) Add a short description of the information (constraint, communication, control, data, education, knowledge, meaning, understanding, mental stimuli, pattern, perception, proposition, representation) that the service offers / is estimated to offer.
 - b) In what format is the service offered?
4. What is the scope of potential use of the service?
 - a) Describe how the information provided by the service (communication, control, data, education, knowledge, meaning, understanding, mental stimuli, pattern, perception, proposition, representation etc.) can be utilised by the service users. Please, list what you think the service will be used for.
 - b) Is it possible to track how the service is used? If yes, what are the indicators to identify the use purposes?

Users of the Service

Gender and equality aspects are specific themes of the Arctic PASSION project. The aim of this section of the survey is to gain insights about the diverse user groups, their unique usage patterns, and how and for what purposes these different current and potential user segments are using your service.

5. What are the evidenced (current) and prospective user groups, and can they be distinctly segmented?
 - a) Describe who are currently using the pilot service or similar service that the pilot service is replacing or competing with.
 - b) Describe potential future user groups (quantitatively and qualitatively).

- c) Can the evidenced and prospective user groups be distinctly segmented according to demographics such as sex/gender, age, income, and so forth?
- d) Describe how the use of the service by different user groups can be measured/monitored.

6. Does the users have the same or different use purposes?

- a) Based on user group identification, do you expect differentiation in service use between user groups? For example, does governmental/NGO use differ from citizen use? Please provide examples.
- b) Is it possible to quantify the impacts of the service? For example, actions taken or not taken, due to the information provided by the service.

7. Is it possible to disaggregate the data to determine how different (demographic) user groups are utilizing the service? For instance, is it possible to identify whether the service use differs between genders? Is it possible to differentiate usage patterns between various organizations, such as environmental NGOs, women's organizations, or emergency/disaster risk reduction NGOs?

Production of the Service

The aim of this section is to describe the supply chain of the service. This is used to determine the actors involved, and how value and also costs of the service accumulate at each step of its process.

8. How is the information produced?

- a) What are the needed data inputs, skills, and equipment?
(e.g. coding skills, education, training, IT systems, research infrastructure, etc.)
- b) What are the subsequent stages of production?
- c) Are there intermediate and final information products?

9. Who are the actors/entities involved in each stage of production?

List the participating entities, research institutions, associations, user groups etc. How are these actors selected and what are the demographics of these groups?

10. Can the information be stratified or segmented in terms of quality level?

Dissemination of the Service

The aim of this section is to describe how users access the information and whether there are barriers for different groups in doing so.

11. Via what channels do the users receive (or fetch) the information?

- a) Does this involve third parties that can influence the reception and/or have own access requirements?
- b) Who are the primary consumers of this information and what are their demographics (age, income, gender/sex, etc.) based on the channel? Do demographics play a role in selecting this channel? If so, why and how?

12. Does the retrieval and use of the information demand special skills and/or particular equipment? If yes, please describe any potential barriers to receiving training for these special skills/use of equipment (e.g. no access to internet)

13. Do the users add information from other sources before gainful use can be made of the service information? If yes, please describe how essential this complementary information is. How is it resourced and/or does it exclude potentially interested users?

14. What factors have an impact on the eventual usefulness of the information? Are there any uncertainties in actual use of the service or regulatory factors/barriers affecting use, e.g. due to access rules and specific (and exclusive) responsibilities?

15. Does the value chain in the Pilot phase look different from the regular service?

2. AS2 – End-User Survey

Respondent

The Arctic PASSION project takes into account equality and different demographics of the user groups and thus the questions about respondents are included.

1. Gender
 - Male
 - Female
 - Other
 - Prefer not to say

2. Age
 - 0–18
 - 18–29
 - 30–39
 - 40–49
 - 50–59
 - 60–69
 - 70+

3. Geographic location
 - Alaska
 - USA (apart from Alaska)
 - Canada
 - Greenland
 - Iceland
 - Norway
 - Sweden
 - Finland
 - Germany
 - United Kingdom
 - Russia
 - China
 - Other

4. Annual income
 - 0–15 000€ / 0–16,500 USD
 - 15 000–30 000€ / 16,500–33,000 USD
 - 30 000–45 000€ / 33,000–49,500 USD
 - 45 000–60 000€ / 49,500–66,000 USD

- 60 000–75 000€ / 66,000–82,500 USD
 - >75 000€ / 82,000 USD
 - Prefer not to say
5. Which statement best describes your position?
- I work for a governmental institution
 - I work for a tribal institution, association or NGO
 - I work for a private company
 - I am a private person living in the Arctic
 - I am a private person living outside the Arctic
 - I am a post graduate researcher
 - I am a student
 - Other
6. How familiar are you with permafrost processes and landscape changes in the Arctic?
- I am an expert in the topic
 - I am well familiar with the topic
 - Intermediate
 - I have limited prior knowledge
 - I have no prior knowledge
7. How did you learn about ALEX?
- On the recommendation of a colleague / friend
 - Media / press release
 - Outreach or science communication event
 - E-mail list
 - Social media (Facebook, Instagram, X, etc.)
 - Search engine (such as Google)
 - Other

Usage and Impacts

8. How often do you use ALEX to get information about permafrost / landscape data?
- This is my first time
 - Weekly
 - Monthly
 - Seasonally
 - Yearly
9. In which context do you use permafrost data primarily? If you are using the ALEX for the first time, please choose in which context you would most likely use it.
- Private user
 - Business / professional users
10. For what purpose do you use the permafrost data provided by ALEX? If you are using the ALEX for the first time, please envision the most likely purposes of using the service.
- Curiosity and interest
 - Planning of leisure activities

- Planning of of subsistence activities (fishing, harvesting, hunting etc.)
- Climate research
- Infrastructure planning
- Environmental monitoring
- Natural resource management
- Hazard assessment
- Cultural heritage preservation
- Climate change adaptation
- Land management
- Other

11. If you wish, please specify here the purposes for which you use the permafrost data.

12. Does permafrost information influence your actions or decision-making? Choose on scale: 1 no, not at all - 5 yes, significantly.

13. If you wish, please specify how permafrost data by ALEX affects/has affected your activities and decisions. If you are using the ALEX for the first time, please envision likely impacts of using the service in the future.

14. What benefits you get from using permafrost data provided by ALEX? Benefits can include for example avoided risks and damage, better decision-making and understanding, more efficient resource optimization and community adaptation, or ecosystem protection and cultural heritage preservation in critical locations. If you are using the ALEX for the first time, you can list potential benefits or skip this question.

User experience

15. What geographic scale are you interested in?

- Local level (e.g., town, village, or camp site)
- Regional level (e.g., borough, hamlet, land management units)
- National level
- Pan-Arctic level

16. How useful do you find the permafrost data provided by ALEX?

Choose on scale: 1 not at all - 5 very useful

17. Are the colors used in the landscape change map understandable to you?

Choose on scale: 1 no, not at all - 5 yes, it's very clear

18. Do you have any improvement suggestions for the ALEX permafrost service? For example, new datasets, functionalities, higher resolution, better explanations, etc.

19. How likely are you to recommend using ALEX to a friend or colleague?

Choose on a scale: 0 Not at all likely - 10 Extremely likely

3. AS6 – End-User Survey

Following the 23rd meeting of the International Ice Charting Working group it has been decided to create a task team gathering ice service representatives, marine professionals and training centers on Polar Waters ice information and use of POLARIS as a decision-making tool.

Questionnaire

Related to those themes:

Information needed to co-develop the tools in collaboration with Pilot Service PS6 on improving safety for shipping in the polar seas’.

How crucially better information on ice conditions may affect ship operations (route, speed, other..).

What could be a differentiator in terms of information quality ?

Can we easily distinguish ship incident evaluation related to sea ice ?

User-friendliness of information products

1. Do you think that sea ice data improve the level of safety of the journey (eg. Reduction of collision probability and damages to the vessel)?
 - Yes, no, why not?
 - If yes, to what extent? Provide % ranges

2. Do you think that sea ice data provide economic benefit?
 - Yes, no, why not
 - If yes, in which field?
 - Fuel costs reduction
 - Navigation time reduction
 - Employees costs reduction and other costs related to the journey (with the exception of fuel)
 - Increase in the number of journeys that could be made in the same amount of time

Could you please estimate the % of reduction of the total costs? Provide % ranges.

3. In case of lack of data which route would you use?
 - The same route
 - The traditionally longest and safest one
 - The shortest one but less safe one
-

1. What is your role?
 - Ship captain
 - Ship crew
 - Ice pilot/navigator
 - Employee of Government Agency
 - Marine Pilot
 - Member of Scientific Community

- Educator
- Vessel Routing Service
- Tourism Industry Advocaat

2. In case of a ship captain or a crew member. What kind of vessel have you served on ice covered waters?

- Ice breaker
- Coast guard
- Container
- Bulk carrier
- Passenger
- Tanker
- Fishing/Trawler
- Multi-purpose
- Navy/Military
- Research
- Other

3. In case of a ship captain or a crew member. What is the vessel ice class (equivalents to the Swedish-Finnish ice classes) you served on in ice covered waters?

- No Ice Class
- 1C or less
- 1A Super, 1A, 1B
- PC5, PC6
- PC3, PC4
- PC1, PC2

4. What geographical region(s) do you navigate in and/or use sea ice information ?

- North Atlantic (including Svalbard and Greenland)
- Canadian Arctic
- Other Antarctic waters
- Weddell Sea/ Antarctic Peninsula
- Alaska including Bering Strait
- The Baltic Sea
- Russian Arctic
- Gulf of St. Lawrence/River
- South Georgia, Norway Fjords, Chilean coast
- North America Great Lakes
- Caspian Sea
- European Ice Waters (Rotterdam)

5. Please rate (*between 1 and 10*) the importance of benefits of real time sea ice observation and forecast data for:

- Safety
- Time saving
- Fuel saving

- Other savings, specify them:

6. Please rate (*between 1 and 10*) the importance of benefits of historical sea ice observation data for:

- Safety
- Time saving
- Fuel saving
- Designing new vessels ice class
- Planning of operations in the polar seas
- Other savings, specify them:

7. Please rate (*between 1 and 10*) the importance of benefits coming from GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) data for:

- Safety
- Time saving
- Fuel saving
- Other savings, specify them:

8. Please rate (*between 1 and 10*) the importance of benefits coming from Telecommunications satellites for:

- Safety
- Time saving
- Fuel saving
- Other savings, specify them:

9. Please rate (*from 1 to 10*) the importance of what feature should be developed to improve the benefits of sea ice observational data:

- Improve the quality of the observations and forecast data (accuracy, frequency, spatial resolution)
- Improve communication between the data providers and the users
- Improve the integration with GNSS data
- User friendliness of the products

4. AS8 – Interview Questions for Professional Users

ELY-centre

Discussion (via email) was built on previous interview.

- In which ways does the LIE service save working time?
- How much working time in-situ monitoring takes annually, and how extensively in-situ monitoring is done (km)?
- Can you estimate the need for in-situ monitoring trips without information on lake ice conditions?

Energy sector

Discussions were built on previous interview.

Via email.

- Can you estimate the need for in-situ monitoring trips without information on lake ice conditions?

- What is the need for in-situ monitoring despite information provided by the LIE service and similar services?
- How extensively are ice conditions monitored? What are the distances to the sites that are being monitored (km)?

In an online meeting. Previous interview was looked through briefly.

- Has the use of the service changed since last interview? Do you have anything to add?
- How many people are required in in-situ monitoring trips?
- How much do you use drone in these in-situ monitoring trips? What is the annual cost of drones?

Sea ice research

- What are the most important indicators to look for when assessing the safety of lake ice?
- How important is extent of lake ice cover on safety?
- How does information on lake ice influence actions of people utilising the ice?
- Do you know other users that need information on the extent of lake ice?

5. AS8 – End-User Survey (3/2023)

1. In which context do you use lake ice data primarily?
 - Housing, leisure time
 - Hobbies, associations
 - Public authority tasks, expert work
 - Rescue services
 - Business activities
 - Other, please specify:

6. For what purpose do you use the lake ice data provided by the service? You can choose multiple options.
 - Outdoor activities (walking, skiing, skating)
 - General ice monitoring
 - Route planning
 - Fishing
 - Reindeer husbandry
 - Monitoring the ecological balance of river system
 - Hydropower
 - Other, please specify:

7. How useful do you find the information provided by the service? Select the most appropriate option.
cannot say 1 not at all 2 little 3 somewhat 4 quite a lot 5 very
 Please specify the benefits you get from using lake ice data.

8. Does lake ice information influence your actions or decision-making? Select the most appropriate option.
cannot say 1 not at all 2 little 3 somewhat 4 quite a lot 5 a lot
 Please specify how lake ice data affects your activities.

9. How often do you use the service to get information on the ice situation at the time of ice break-off (approximately March-June).
 - Once a month or less often

- A few times a month
- Several times a month / About once a week
- Daily or almost daily

10. Do you have wishes for changes and improvements in the lake ice data service? E.g., new datasets or functionalities.